
DOCTORATE IN BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION (DBA) THESIS

WHAT IS THE IMPACT OF DIVERSITY AND WORKFORCE DIVERSITY MANAGEMENT PRACTICES ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN NURSING HOMES?

A Case Study of Care Homes in Middlesex-London.

(MASTERING DIVERSITY & WORKFORCE DIVERSITY MANAGEMENT PRACTICES)

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: -

This study investigates the perception of frontline healthcare staff (nurses, carers/healthcare assistants, receptionists, and cleaners) and managers (managers, assistant managers, supervisors) of diversity and workforce diversity management practices on employee performance in nursing homes in Middlesex-London.

Methodology/approach/design: -

This research revolved around an exploratory case study of selected nursing homes in the Middlesex area of London, using a reflective perspective based on a complete participant role. The primary study, adopted for this research was a mix-method research design, consisting of qualitative (semi-structured 12-items interviews guide/schedule, deploying a group discussion approach) and quantitative (based on a 22-item self-completion questionnaire) methodology in which five hundred frontline healthcare staff and managers surveyed. The massive data was collected and analysed using a software SPSS and Excel. The qualitative data grouped into themes, coded, and interpreted. The validity of the research instrument measured using content validity and about half of the questions were in a Likert scale format. Cronbach's Coefficient Alpha Model used to measure the reliability. Following data analysis and interpretations, the major findings were presented. The research improved on existing multidimensional workforce diversity management practices, widening it by combining diversity characteristics such as gender, age, ethnicity, and workforce diversity management practices (cross-cultural training, flexible working hours and employee motivational schemes) to re-design and upgrade to a new conceptual framework, known as a Multidimensional Workforce Diversity Management Practices Conceptual Framework (MWDMP CF). This improved framework is implementable, practicable, and sustainable, whilst still retaining a workplace friendliness that may lead to reductions in feelings of inequality within nursing homes. This new insightful extension was derived through a combination of literature, methodology and conceptual development, by adopting a mixed- approach.

Findings: -

The results showed that frontline healthcare staff employment support needs, have been unmet which had resulted to deficient performance levels and a great deal of additional support needed to improve performance. Specifically, the studies revealed that while gender, ethnicity, and motivational schemes have a strong and positive link with employee performance, cross-cultural training and flexible working hours showed a positive but weak link with employee performance. However, the relation between age diversity and employee performance was negative. These findings lead to the formulation of an integrated theoretical framework of diversity types and diversity management practices within formulated framework i.e., MWDMPCF.

Key words: Diversity and Equality, Workforce diversity, Nursing Homes, Care Homes, Health

& Social Care, Exclusion and Inclusion, Inequalities, Discrimination, Human Rights, Middlesex London

Declaration

I, Dorothy Wainsi Mbangsi, confirm that the thesis presented is, to the best of my knowledge, has not been submitted, for a degree at this or any other university. I accept that I have read the university's guidance, rules, and requirements, involving my higher degree research award and my thesis.

I assert that I have complied with the policy, rules, requirements, and procedures, as stipulated by the University of the West of Scotland.

DOROTHY WAINSI MBANGSI

Dedication

I want to dedicate my work to God Almighty for all the strength, perseverance, and commitment he bestowed upon me. Secondly to my parents, who taught me that even the largest task can be accomplished if it is done one step at a time. This thesis has been proof of my hard work and dedication.

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CHAPTER ONE

1.1) Introduction

This thesis investigates the impact of diversity and workforce diversity management practices on employee performance in nursing homes in the Middlesex-London region. The term 'diversity refers to: -

"...valuing everyone as individuals - as employees, customers, and clients" Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development (CIPD, 2006:1).

Whereas Wendling (2004: 166) defines diversity as: -

"...all the ways in which people differ, and it encompasses all the different characteristics that make one individual or group different from one another"

Griggs (1995), Kossek and Lobel, (1996) argue that diversity; is all-inclusive recognizing everyone and every group as part of the diversity that should be valued.

'Workforce diversity management practices' in the context of this thesis, is referred to as management practices, including policies and procedures that are put in place as a functional tool in guiding the operations of staff in this setting - care homes in Middlesex-London. There are many examples of workplace management practices which may include discrimination, racism, remuneration and benefits, harassment, stereotypical behaviours/attitudes, multiculturalism, inclusion, exclusion, inequality, etc. However, these may be too wide for this study. This research focuses on six specific aspects of workforce management, of which three are workforce dimensions (age, gender, ethnicity) and the others management practices, (flexible working, cross-cultural training, and motivational). This study aims to assess the extent to which diversity and workforce diversity management practices could impact employee performance in nursing homes in the Middlesex-London region. The research describes diverse workforce management practices as the process of setting up or managing a multicultural team of employees in such a comfortable and conducive atmosphere and/or environment where employees could work to achieve their best potential that would both benefit themselves, the organization employing them, the Middlesex-London region and the broader society at large, in an inclusive sense of the concept of diversity.

1.2) The Research Problem

Over the last few decades, Europe, including the UK has been facing the biggest influx of migrants. Deliberation has considered how member countries of the European Union are to cope with receiving and integrating an increased number of migrants (Gupta et al 2015). Challenges following influxes of new, unfamiliar cultures are disrupting an already shaken Union that is still recovering from the monetary crisis of 2008. Amid this crisis,

even more, doubts surround the challenges or the potential enriching opportunities of an ever-increasing diverse workforce (Montes & Shaw, 2003; Choi & Rainey 2010).

More specifically, in places of work, there seems to be an inadequate distribution of diversity characteristics such as age, gender, ethnicity at top/mid-management levels which has been noted in nursing homes. Equally, there seems to be limited understanding or inappropriate application of the various workforce diversity practices, especially in nursing care (Gupta et al., 2015). This limited understanding could partly be because of the changes in the mindset of stakeholders (Kaplan et al., 2011) and the fact that management issues such as diversity management which were rarely seen as corporate responsibility only a generation ago have become a key area for organisational survival (Fleming & Jones, 2013).

1.3) Research Background

The movement of immigrants from diverse backgrounds into the UK has rapidly increased (Johnson,2003). According to Knippenberg et al, (2004) immigrants mostly occupy low-paid jobs with its female population, constituting the associated healthcare workforce. Moreover, increasing workforce diversity will encourage patient access to care (Ellis et al.,2003; Glomb et al., 2005). Therefore, implementing workforce diversity practices can improve access to care and better patient outcomes.

The under-representation of minorities in managerial positions and the over-representation in lower-level staff positions may result in power imbalances which can result in racial tensions that hinder employee performance (Aydin 2016; Bendick et al., 2010; Benschop, 2001).According to Cox (1994), minorities in non-diverse companies are often less motivated and do not think they can be leaders of a majority-led organisation. Also, minorities in token leadership roles are usually marginalised, and undervalued. The heightened visibility of token members also brings attention to intergroup differences, which can cause polarisation (Cox, 1994; Cassel, 2000). The insufficient minority leadership representation may be particularly impactful in nursing homes because these organisations have a distinct hierarchal structure in which decisions are made in senior management positions with truly little input from bottom levels (Chappel& Humphrey (2014); Cirulla, 2012). Research on organizational inequalities stipulates that organizations tend to establish and promote social class hierarchies (Dijk et al., 2012). Organisational inequalities are characterized by inconsistency in benefits, pay, flexibility, autonomy, within the organization for minority employees. Not surprisingly, once a gender or racial group dominates a particular occupation, societal assumptions are created; therefore, the suitability of other groups working in the field becomes questionable (Chappel & Humphrey 2014). As a result of the high number of minority direct care workers, and the inadequate representation in healthcare leadership, there exist power imbalances in an environment already inundated by racial discrimination and bureaucracy (Dijk et al, 2012).

This increased heterogeneity of the workforce across the world has made it difficult for governments and employers to ignore the pervading impact of diversity within organisations (Charta der Vielfalt,2014). Moreover,

the global economy is becoming more diverse than ever before, and this might be attributed to immigration, globalisation, ethnic differences, gender, or religious issues (Avery & McKay, 2010; Kirton & Greene 2010). The large influx of migrants into the UK along with a declining rate of native working-age puts organisations in a situation where the available workforce is no longer as homogeneous as it has previously been (Bezrukova, 2016). Although attention is directed towards visible than invisible aspects of diversity, Jackson & Joshi (2004) think that the inability of some managers to fully understand the diverse dynamics of the workforce is inherent in personal prejudices. Besides, these authors think that diversity management is unimportant; and therefore, there is no need to invest in a diverse workforce.

On the other hand, the demand for equal rights from older/younger workers, disabled people, non-average weight people, as well as those with non-traditional gender expressions are on the rise, as a result, diversity management remains one of the pertinent management issues as creating a diverse and inclusive workspace is one of management's priorities. Employees are experiencing issues of exclusion at work, and they perceive themselves as not an integral part of the organisation information networks and decision-making processes (McKay & Avery, 2010). As a result, workers are demanding better working conditions where inclusiveness is one of the desired workplace attributes. Therefore, the author of the thesis sets out to investigate how selected diversity characteristics such as gender, age, ethnicity as well as diversity management practices (cross-cultural training, flexible work hours, and motivational schemes) could impact on employee performance.

1.4) The Rationale for Studying Diversity & Diversity management practices in Nursing homes/ in the Middlesex-London of UK.

One of the main reasons for choosing the Middlesex area of London as the location for this study, is due to its richly diverse population, as it is across London. Secondly, there have been quite several other well-deserving research efforts on this phenomena before but inequality persists i.e. improving patients' care and/or patient's access to care within a diverse workforce; implementation of diverse workforce practices; improving patients' satisfaction level and compliance (Ellis et al., 2003; Gombe et al., 2005; Wambari, 2014; tokenism leadership role or marginalisation and/or being undervalued, intergroup differences(Cox, 1994; Cassel, 2000; Wambari, 2014); inequalities within organisations; social class hierarchies(Dijk et al., 2012); insufficient minority Black, Asian Minority Ethnic group (BAME) in leadership roles (tokenism management role) (Chappel and Humphrey 2014; Cirulla, 2014). From literature searches, little or less study is focused on the Middlesex-London region concerning diversity workforce management practices within nursing homes in Middlesex-London.

Moreover, challenges still exist across the nursing homes sector, particularly, within the Middlesex-London region, concerning diversity/workforce diversity management practices' related issues. Another motivating factor is that the researcher does reside as well as work within the Middlesex-London sector, which had influenced the interest in undertaking this study. As with others, the nursing homes within this area are either

privately owned or owned by the local authority, varying in capacities. To be able to conduct this study, a list of all the nursing homes obtained from a Yell.com business directory. Emails were sent to all the nursing homes within this area (Copy of email in appendix). Additionally, the researcher visited those care homes that replied to the emails. Managers of the nursing homes contacted their colleagues who had not responded to the email encouraging them to participate in the study. It should be noted that many of the care homes declined and some never responded to the email.

Below is a table which highlights the number of care homes in the thirty-two boroughs that make up Greater London and more specifically those within Middlesex-London.

Table 1. 1 List of boroughs in Greater London/Care homes

Boroughs in London	No	Boroughs in London	No
Bexley	144	Richmond Upon Thames	25
Barnet	361	Southwark	9
Brent	100	Sutton	400
Ealing	361	Tower Hamlets	4
Bromley	441	Waltham Forest	9
Enfield	121	Wandsworth	144
Croydon	1024	Westminster	9
Greenwich	144	Newham	36
Hackney	8	Hillingdon	289
Hammersmith/Fulham	4	Redbridge	169
Havering	324	Merton	144
Islington	34	Lewisham	36
Kensington/Chelsea	8	Lambeth	121
Kingston Upon Thames	196	Camden	8
Lambeth	121	Barking/Dagenham	36
Harrow	100	Hounslow	81
TOTAL =	5001		

Table 1. 2 Middlesex boroughs/Care homes

List of London boroughs	No of Care homes
Barnet	361
Brent	100
Ealing	361
Enfield	121
Haringey	1
Harrow	100
Hillingdon	289
Hounslow	81
Bexley	144
Total	1558

Source: Care Quality Commission (CQC, 2019); (NHS England, 2019); (Care UK, 2019); (Yellow.com, 2020)

The table above reflects vital information about the nursing/care homes within the London area. Within the Greater London area, there are thirty-two boroughs and within these localities, there are approximately 5001 care homes. In the Middlesex borough where this study is conducted, there are 1558 care homes distributed among the eight boroughs that make up Middlesex London (Barnet 361, Brent 100, Ealing 361, Enfield 121, Haringey 1, Harrow 100, Hillingdon, 289, Hounslow 81) compared with a total of 5001 care homes across

London with a potential accommodation capacity over between 30-150 clients (ONS, 2017, 2018, 2019). According to the researcher should not all Middlesex-London care homes did participate or respond to the survey/interview. Despite the limited responses from these care homes as well as issues with coordination and bureaucracies the author still found it necessary to embark on this research because there is no study without challenges.

A further reason for this study is that of motivation for improving employees' performance and organizational productivity in a multicultural workplace setting for care homes or nursing homes. One of the main goals of any organisation employing a diverse workforce is to improve outcomes. Workforce diversity differs from organisation to organisation based on the guidelines, policies, and practices.

According to Patrick and Kumar (2012), organisational attributes such as company type, organisational culture, company location are adopted when investigating diverse workforce. The company type plays a significant role in deciding whether to employ a diverse workforce or not, and this is because organisations employ people based on size or customers they serve. The company culture usually includes a set of values, practices, people, place,

and history. The location of the company is a factor because some countries respond to the concept of diversity differently (Welbourne, 2017). Therefore, another influencing reason for studying diversity in London nursing homes is in line with the above organization attributes and according to the Guardian, (2010) and Welbourne, (2017), the UK is one of the most diverse countries in the world. The U.K workforce is rapidly changing not only in its demography but is projected to increase in spatial representation throughout the national territory by 2051(The Guardian, 2010). The Office of National Statistics (ONS), estimates show that by the year 2051, the ethnic minority population will increase by well over 20% (Welbourne, 2017). London has one of the biggest minority communities, and almost half of the individuals visiting a healthcare setting represent an ethnic minority group (ONS, 2017, 2018, 2019). Moreover, life expectancy in the older adult population has increased because of medical science and healthier lifestyles of the population (Joshi, 2002). According to ONS (2010, 2017, 2018,2019), the number of persons aged sixty-five and older grew by 15% from 2000 to 2010. By 2051, it is estimated that the older population will double by increasing to 88.5 million, a figure accounting for 20.1% of the entire population (The Guardian, 2010).

Furthermore, there has been a steady increase in the use of nursing homes by Black people, Asians, and minority ethnic groups (BAME) (Smith et al., 2007, 2008; ONS (2010, 2017, 2018,2019). As a result, nursing homes that are not diverse would find it difficult to adopt the required policies, practices, and service delivery systems to properly care for the minority residents (Betancourt et al, 2003; CQC,2015). Therefore, there is a need for the U.K. care industry to respond not only to the increasing number of minorities' population but also to replicate the patient population demographically in their workforce (Joshi, 2009; CQC 2015).

1.5) Limitation of the study

This research has limitations and/or constraints, as with most other studies. Below specific experiences explained as follows:

1.5.1) Study area/ region:

This study concentrated exclusively only on the narrow sector of the industry as well as a region of London, which is – nursing homes (or care homes) within Middlesex-London. This means different nursing (or care homes) outside of this region are not covered or included in this research. However, the research is envisaging engaging in similar research or future study that would focus on other regions of the wider Greater London areas. This proposes a suggested future research commitment for those who may be interested.

1.5.2) Research Findings:

As outlined above in connection with one, the findings of this research relate only to investigating the impact of diversity/workforce diversity management practices on employee performance in nursing homes Middlesex in London.

Again, this means that since it did not cover or extend to

(i) other aspects of the health and care industry and

(ii) other regions of London and beyond, it automatically opens the possibility for interested future researchers to explore such potential and scope for further research on same subject elsewhere.

1.5.3) Health & social care/NHS industry:

This research is not about the entire health and social care industry, nor the NHS. Although nursing homes/care homes are part of the health and social care industry, this study does not extend to the entire industry, as already stated above. It is important to understand this closeness but at the same time the narrower specification of this area/region of research.

1.5.4) Perceptions and opinions:

This study is predicated upon the perceptions and opinions of the respondents who participated in the empirical aspect of the study. It is important to note that perceptions and opinions are different from their actual actions and practices would be, so it is important to allow such a difference between reality and perception. This means it is important to respect and/or appreciate such limitations and constraints connected with opinion surveys.

1.6) Research Gap

As noted above research gap, therefore, arose from the fact that despite the several previous studies on different aspects of diversity/workforce diversity management practices as they affect employees generally: on the challenges/opportunities (Montes & Shaw, 2003; Choi & Rainey, 2010); on inappropriate application/limitations in understanding of the concept (Gupta, 2015); on lack of understanding of the changes/dynamism of the concept in the mindset of stakeholders (Kaplan et al, 2015); and/or on lack of comprehension as diversity issues were rarely seen as part of corporate responsibility of stakeholders (Fleming & Jones), etc. Similar studies that focused on the nursing homes concerning nursing homes in the Middlesex-London region, were scarce. Similarly, the extant literature relating to the same were equally weak or scarce. Hence, the researcher opted to choose to undertake this research which focuses on diversity/workforce diversity management practices and their impact on employee performance.

1.7) Aim of the study

The study aims to investigate critically the impact of diversity and workforce diversity management practices on employee performance in nursing homes in Middlesex-London.

1.8) Research Questions

New Overarching Research Question is -what is the impact of diversity and workforce diversity management practices on employee performance in nursing homes in Middlesex-London?

The specific research questions.

1. What is the impact of diversity on employee performance in nursing homes in Middlesex-London?
2. What is the impact of workforce diversity management practices on employee performance in nursing homes in Middlesex-London?

1.9) Research objectives

- 1.) To critically assess and analyse what is the impact of diversity on employee performance in nursing homes in Middlesex-London.
- 2.) To critically examine and analyse what is the impact of workforce diversity management practices on employee performance in nursing homes in Middlesex-London.
- 3.) To identify and analyse ways in which policymakers (such as government officials, as well as nursing management and frontline workers agree on how to implement identified best diversity/workforce, workforce diversity management practices required to improve(maximise) employee performance and reduce, (minimise) employee turnover.
- 4.) To formulate a new and/or improved conceptual framework for nursing homes.
- 5.) To encourage the application of a combination of diversity and workforce diversity management practices in nursing homes within Middlesex-London

1.10) Research Contributions

To literature development - This research has contributed to literature development in the areas of diversity/workforce diversity management practices in the nursing homes in Middlesex-London. This was achieved by specifically introducing/re-emphasising the need for nursing homes in Middlesex in London to focus on three key diversity characteristics, including variables: age, gender, and ethnicity as well as three diversity workforce practices (cross-cultural training, motivational practices, and flexible working schemes) which will reflect or highlight the current diversity structure of the Middlesex - London community. As a result, re-directing

attention to the three essential diversity characteristics (or variables), and their contribution to fill the gap literature.

To methodology development - This research has also contributed to methodology development in the areas of diversity/workforce diversity management practices in the nursing homes in Middlesex-London. This was achieved especially through the design and development of a new conceptual framework, which is new and enhanced as it incorporates not only the three diversity characteristics (or variables – age, gender, and ethnicity on one hand, but also contained the three-diversity workforce management practice variables namely: motivational schemes, flexible working hours and cross-cultural training). Again, by purposely redrawing attention to these six issues and incorporated the same into one meaningful purposive conceptual framework, this research has contributed towards methodology. This is so unique as these six diversity issues were identified through the fieldwork data collecting and analysis process, as these aspects are most important and relevant in running nursing homes within the Middlesex-London region.

To future researchers, this research contributes to the enhancement of the body of knowledge and provides information that forms a basis for further research on workforce diversity and employee performance and diversity/workforce diversity management practices in nursing homes in the Middlesex-London region, more broadly. Just as this work was influenced by the literature and methodology of previous researchers, so also this research has not only added to the same but also has created the base upon which future researchers could continue.

To practice, the management of nursing homes, the research provided additional insights into the relationship between workforce diversity practices and employee performance, more specifically in nursing homes in general. The researcher feels this is also an important contribution to knowledge in this field of diversity/workforce diversity management practices within nursing homes in the Middlesex-London region.

Lastly, to policymakers and policy implementers - this research also contributes to policy formulating in the diversity/workforce diversity management practices sector within nursing homes in the Middlesex-London region. From the integration of diversity characteristics and diversity management practices perspective, this contribution is by designing a new conceptual framework specifically for the nursing homes sector to improve diverse workforce management practices. This is because the new knowledge gained should provide insight into the debate on policymaking that could result in improving the quality of workforce diversity management processes. The study provides vital insights on how effective management of distinct aspects of diversity within an organisational setting can influence performance.

1.11) An Overview of the Thesis

This thesis is organised into six chapters as follows: -

Chapter 1: This chapter presents an overview of the thesis. And contains the main introduction and background to the study, the research problem, as well as sets out the research questions, research aim, research objectives, research contributions, and research gaps identified from the study.

Chapter 2: Focuses on review of the literature on diversity/workforce diversity management practices in general, equality, a global perspective of diversity, differences between workforce/employee, past studies on diversity, and the researchers integrated workforce diversity management framework. It provides the theoretical framework extracted from a wide range of literature related to the subject of diversity/workforce diversity management practices. In a table form, the author brings out the consequences of poor diversity within the health and social care sector and examines poor career planning, unsupportive work environment, lack of mentor, inclusion. Besides, the writer explores the ethical case of diversity, strategies to promote inclusivity, benefits of diversity, change management, and the summary of the chapter.

Chapter 3: This is the methodology section. This chapter examines how the research will be conducted, including the research design, research approach, and research philosophy. It also addresses the issues relating to population, sampling method, and data collection techniques such as questionnaires and interview guides/schedules, as well as ethical issues concerning the research.

Chapter 4: This chapter involves data analysis and interpretations of the findings of the research. This chapter is divided into two parts; analysis of the quantitative data and minutes or records of the qualitative data based on the interview schedules/guides. It explains how the analysis is organized and presented with the bulk of data obtained in chapter three, enabling the researcher to conduct the complex statistical analysis of the themes to interpret meanings.

Chapter 5: This chapter focuses on the issues of interpretation and discussions and divided into three parts: Part (i) covers the interpretation and discussion of the quantitative data. Part(ii) covers the interpretation and discussion of the records/minutes of the qualitative data, while part (iii) covers the interpretation and discussion of how both sets of data achieved the research questions using triangulation. This reflects the use of a mixed-method research design.

Chapter 6: presents the summary, conclusion, and recommendations. This chapter highlights the key findings of the theory in summary. It also presents the conclusion and inferences from the earlier chapters, and based on these, it makes recommendations regarding potential future work.

1.12) Summary

As seen above, this chapter set out the basis of the research which was to: investigate the impact of diversity and workforce diversity management practices on employee performance in nursing homes in the Middlesex-London region, it further defined the basic principles and their meanings to achieve clarity and better understanding, using

different perspectives. As well as highlighting the major contributions of the research, the chapter also clearly set out the location setting of the research, where the research was conducted, its research objectives, research aims, research problems stated, including the limitations. Towards the end of the chapter, the researcher engaged on how the whole research would be arranged or the overview of the research, which showed how each chapter will be completed. Then the researcher embarks on chapter two which is the literature section of the studies.

CHAPTER TWO

2) LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1) Introduction

According to Smart 2003, Webster & Waston 2002 a literature review is the systematic collection and synthesis of previous research studies. To ensure appropriate literature is accurately covered, the researcher must be transparent about the process from designing, conducting, analysing, and writing up the literature section (Knippenberg & Mell 2016). By designing, the researcher first had to find out if there was need for academic research in the area (Diversity/diversity management and its impact of performance in care homes). From the researcher experience, reading journals, and working across London in the health sector, she found out that diversity and diversity management are contemporary issues and set out to investigate. According to Milliken & Martins 1996 researchers must always use leading journals from their area of studies so they can understand existing literature and where to add or challenge. As a result, the researcher explored leading human resource journals as well as resources on organisational behaviour. Using words such as dimensions of diversity, heterogenous workforce, diversity management, demographic diversity, demographic characteristics and employee performance, diversity management and heterogenous workforce yielded over 80 articles relevant to the research question. Then the researcher conducted a review of the articles by grouping articles by year of publication, type of articles. Thereafter a more detailed review was conducted, by reading abstracts, and reviewing entire articles. These journals were grouped into Academy of management journal, Academy of management review, Journal of management, Administrative Science quarterly, Human relations, journal of Organisational behaviour, group and organisational management, organisational behaviour and human decisions processes, strategic management journal, journal of public administration, research and theory, human resource management theory, journal of Applied psychology and international journal of human resource management for easy identification and analysis and documentation.

Employee performance, inclusion/exclusion, and implementation of change management in nursing homes in the UK examined. Other topics like the changing nature of health care diversity with the UK workforce, theories of diversity, the meaning of workforce versus employee, consequences of diversity management, inclusion, and strategies to improve inclusivity added in this section. A detailed analysis of the Researcher's Integrated Diversity/Workforce Diversity Management Practice Model for Nursing Homes in Middlesex-London (RI-

DWDMPNHML) as seen in chapter 2. Finally, change management, theories of performance, the importance, and setbacks of diversity as well summary included in the chapter.

2.2) Diversity

As previously stated (chapter 1), according to the UK's Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development (CIPD, 2006:1;2017), Diversity is “...*valuing everyone as individuals - as employees, customers, and clients*”.

For total inclusivity, people's (individuals or groups) differences are to be recognised respected, appreciated, valued, and utilised to their full potential, to allow their feelings of belonging, which in turn would enable the people to work harder more productively, being happier as to put in their possible best for the organisation.

Wentling (2004: 166) defines diversity as: -

“...all the ways in which people differ, and it encompasses all the different characteristics that make an individual or group different from the another.”

Furthermore, Griggs (1995) and Kossek, and Lobel (1996) added that diversity is an all-inclusive term and recognises everyone and every group as part of the diversity that should be valued as cited in Wentling (2004). Yet other scholars see it as: -

“...the presence of differences among members of a social unit” (Jackson et al., 1995; as cited in D'Netto and Sohal (1999:1).

However, with the harmonisation into a single effective Act (Equality Act 2010, as amended), this legislation is applicable, relevant, and encompasses all forms of discrimination on the grounds of race, sex, disability, religion, thus giving a broader definition still.

From the perspective of the NHS, which is more industry-specific, Diversity means appreciating the differences between people and treating people's values, beliefs, cultures, and lifestyles with respect. This means diversity is about recognising and valuing differences through inclusion, regardless of age, disability, gender, racial origin, religion, belief, sexual orientation, commitments outside of work, part-time or shift work, language, union activity, HIV status, perspectives, opinions, and person value (NHS, version, 2020).

From the perspective of Health and Social care (HSC) diversity in health care matters – it is about ensuring all backgrounds, beliefs, ethnicities, and perspectives are correctly represented in the medical field. It is about providing the best possible care for a variety of people by enlisting a variety of providers (Healthcare Health & Social care version, 2020).

For this research, this definition (the NHS/the Health and Social Care's definition is adopted). The justification for this narrower definition is that, from a macroeconomics perspective, this research concerns an industry, health, and social care industry in this context, which is only a unit or branch of the entire UK's economy (Companies' House, 2020).

Invariably, based on the above review it all implies that the meaning of diversity constitutes some inherent division of ideas based on peoples' perceptions and/or perspectives, which is, in turn, is based on their social, economic, political, legal, cultural, and geographical, psychological or cognitive characteristics or backgrounds, etc. This leads to the idea that contextualisation becomes fundamentally critical when it comes to the discourse surrounding the theory of diversity.

2.3) Diversity in nursing homes and the changing nature of health care diversity in the workforce in the UK

Care homes are gradually becoming more diverse places than ever before for both staff and care home residents (Pitts & Jarry, 2007). The demand for care homes for racial and ethnic groups is increasing steadily (Philips & Malone, 2014), while a recent study suggests that problems exist in the delivery of quality care to non-whites in these facilities (Whitman & Valpuesta, 2010). Equally, long term care facilities are unable to cope and/or meet the growing needs of diverse users such as special diets, observance of religious practices, interpretation services because of the lack of awareness of how the needs embedded in living arrangements, communication barriers with ethnic minorities and inadequate training of carers involved in direct care roles. As the diversity among nursing home residents continued to surge, demographic projections show that in the next 15-25years long-term-care (LTC) residents will rely on workers of colour and immigrants to offer hands-on care (Pitts and Jarry, 2007; Whitman & Valpuesta,2010).

The growing diversity among staff and residents requires an urgent and escalating need to improve the capability of the staff in long term facilities to work across boundaries of religion, ethnicity, race, and language. Inevitably, this rises in diversity among the UK workforce in terms of ethnicity or multiculturalism has given rise to the need for better understanding of ethnicity and/or multiculturalism and indeed cultural competence, a term used to describe culturally correct interactions between and among workers and care home residents in long term care facilities and employee (Branfied & Beresford, 2013; Hunt et al., 2015).

Improving diversity in the healthcare workforce is a vital form of inclusion and social justice perspective and a means of decreasing disparities in health care (Williams, Walker, & Egede, 2016; Jackson & Gracia, 2014; Department of health and human services (DHHS), 2011. The association of American Medical Colleges (2014), emphasize the diversity role in reducing health differences in research, proposing that health professionals from

underrepresented groups are likely to care for clients from underrepresented groups and serve in deprived areas, therefore, decreasing access for the disadvantaged population.

Another critical factor in diversity learning is that the workforce in this sector has grown by 13.5% since 2009, despite cuts to the social care expenditure (Office of National Statistics, 2013b). The public sector that was once the main employer in the social care sector, had significantly reduced their role and responsibility in the sector. This means that the social care jobs are now with independent providers. Conversely, this shift in responsibility for the social care sector from the public to the private sector also implies the need to learn more about the diverse nature of the sector. Importantly, it is critical to also understand what type of occupations or job descriptions constitutes, nursing homework. According to (The Health Foundation, 2012) nursing homes or care homes workforce comprises a broad range of care related occupations which include:

- Social services managers and directors
- Residential, day, and domiciliary care managers and proprietors
- Occupational therapists
- Social workers
- Welfare and housing associate professionals
- Nursing auxiliaries and assistants
- Residential wardens
- Nurses

2.4) Theories of diversity

Although there have been previous studies and/or efforts as highlighted above Wentling (2004: 166); Griggs (1995) and (Kossek and Lobel, (1996) (CIPD, 2006:1); Act (Equality Act 2010, as amended), based on perception which according to Kotler et al., 2005:917; 2012, 2014; Eguruze, (2017:1) is seen: -

“...as a process by which people select, organise and interpret information to form a meaningful picture of the word, or as they deem fit or on their terms.”

To this end, diversity as a theory is deployed on a piece meal basis and so it has not been universally accepted. This explains the dearth of literature and/or insight on the subject. This makes this study even more necessary.

Table 2.1 below highlights and summarises some relevant theories and their meanings together with their origin and references or authorities, which the researcher believes may be useful in advancing this review further.

Table 2. 1 Outline of Relevant theories linking the meaning of Diversity to their origins and consequences and influences across the World; Contrasting two major diversity approaches

Serial No.	Diversity Theory; Meanings/Causes/ Methods	Measurement Types; Inherent Variables	Impact/Consequences on Society and at Workplaces	Approximate Periods
1.	Darwinism Evolutionary theory of creation (1859(1809-1882); Natural Divisions of Labour; Natural Selection; Ethnicity; Socially constructed; Survival of the fittest (weak dies out; while the strong lives on/conquer/dominate. Adam Smith (1776), Ricardo (1859, etc.)	Colonies/Territories Standards of living; 1 st ,2 nd ,3 rd World-level- ofdevelopment; Trade & Investment; Sea/Naval Power; Wage levels; Fitness levels; Human-Capital Infrastructural facilities; etc. Driven by Power and Greed; profit maximization for the owners/shareholders	Conquer and dominate; Dominance; Slavery/Slave labour; Capitalism; Less freedom; Colonialism, Neocolonialism; Explore/ Exploitation; comparative advantages; Migration/ resettlements; Choices; Unfortunately, these are single dimensionally based.1 st World;2 nd World;3 rd World; Nazism; fascism; Supremacists, etc.; Slavery (these can be in various forms: forced labour/unfree labour, slavery wages, chattel (which is like an individual property (Dan, 20011), human trafficking, domestic servants, forced marriage, child labour	1500-1900; to Date Dan, 2011; UNDP, 1979, 2005, MDGS, 2005; UDHR, 1948 ICESCR, 1996, 2006; Hodal, 2016; Marek, 2017; Sen, 1999; Eguruze, 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, 2019, 2020; Oxford English dictionary, 1989

			(UNDP, 1979, 2005, Oxford English Dictionary, 1989; Bales, 2004;	
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			MDGs, 2005, 210; UDHR, 1948, ICESCR, 1996, 2006; Hodal, 2016; Marek, 2017); most of them living below the poverty line or extreme poverty and/or cumulative poverty (UNDP, 1979, Sen, 1999, 1978; Eguruze, 2014,2015, 2016, 2017, 2019,2020) and so on.	
2.	Adam/Even Evolutionary Theory on creation; which is based on traditional/Biblical perspective on creation that: Male and female needed each other or vice versa; to cohabit/value of co-existence;	Reproductions/Children; growth of families, towns, communities; Driven by Necessity/ Need; Driven by the owners; Concerning Adam/Eve – what was it for/for what purpose; why was it significant?	Faith Conflicts; Catholic/ Protestantism, Islamic, etc. This reflects on the evolution of humanity how humankind is believed to have emerged over centuries and for what specific-reason(s)/ purpose(s); The failure of understanding the value of respecting natural divisions.	Genesis 1:27-28; Genesis 2:7, 18, 2123;

3.	Social grading and/or social classification are methods of breaking down society or communities into smaller units or segments by governments or businesspeople for different purposes. The usual social groups include ABCC1 or C2DE respectively.	The main segmentation variables include geographic, demographic, psychographic and behavioural, etc. Establishment of Class Systems: Upper class, Middle class, Working Class, etc. Alternatively, may be by Socio-Economic or	The social classifications and marketing segmentations are being driven by marketing purposes: cost effectiveness and profit maximization motives; driven by owners/leaders. However, it also re-in forced or highlight the uniqueness of diversity. It makes	Dates back 50 years, post WWII or 1950s
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	These are taken to equate to the middle class and working class, respectively	Demographic characteristics: age, gender, race, geography, income, etc. Alternatively, it may be by lifestyle driven by consumption (veganism, vegetarianism, obesity, etc., income, profession, occupation, sexual (heterogeneity, same-sex or transgender); or religion, etc. preferences;	the people are different, but all peoples are needed for varied reasons: consumers, voters, tax payment, workers, reproductions, etc. Diversity is an increasingly important factor in organisational life as organisations worldwide become more diverse in terms of the gender, race, ethnicity, age, national origin, and other	
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			personal characteristics of their members (Shaw and Barrett Power, 1998). Thus, it is imperative to learn these implications.	
4.	Behaviourists Humanists' theories/approaches Management/ Leadership Styles:	Douglas McGregor, Blake & Mouton; Abraham Maslow's Hierarchy of Need; Theory X & Y; Fredrick Herzberg, AI theories; DNA models; Chris Argyris (1964) Maturity v Immaturity Theory; etc.	The focus was on how behaviours and attitudes are different and could change over time; by different causes or influences that leaders could decide to deploy to effect change or impact on how people perform in a work environment or otherwise. Could be a positive or negative impact	1940s, 1960s to Date

5.	International Trade theories; Comparative advantages of	The main variables: comparative advantages -	Highlights significance of survival; perseverance, etc., in the	1600; 1990s, Porter, 1980, 1985,
	nations; Diamond Theory	nations are endowed differently by nature or evolution: some have technological superiority; military superiority, mineral natural resources, or agricultural natural resources. No one is self-sufficient so there is a rationale to trade fairly and competitively.	face of fierce opposition or competition; it highlights the value of competitiveness of world nations or organisations; to competitive advantages, as well no human being/state/nation is self- sufficient as Porter, 1980, 1990, 2008);	1990, 2008, etc.
6.	Globally: The United Nations (UN) Model; UNDP HDI; MDGs; Sustainable Development; UDHR, ICESSR,	Different strategies: 1 st ,2 nd ,3 rd World-level- ofdevelopment; developing vs developed countries; Eurocentric versus Afrocentric perspectives, etc.	Before 1945, the world experienced several global or regional wars with devastating consequences. Following World War II, the world's nations experienced unparalleled levels of devastation, ruin, and damages to property, and millions of lives were lost, etc.	1945; 1948; 1996/2006 UDHR, 1948;

7.	<p>‘Workforce diversity is about Multiculturalism’ in that that multiculturalism is one of the key components and/or one of the most important aspects of workforce diversity (D’Netto, 1994; D’Netto and Sohal, 1999:532), 1999:530).</p>	<p>It means that a diverse workforce comprises people who are different and share different attitudes, needs, desires, values, and work behaviours (Deluca and McDowell, 1992; Morrison, 1992; Rosen and Lovelace,</p>	<p>The results of this research will provide a significant contribution to the effective management of workforce diversity in Middlesex-London care Homes as well as the broader society. Lack of such study may lead to lack of clarity and misconception,</p>	<p>Deluca and McDowell, 1992; Morrison, 1992; Rosen and Lovelace, 199; D’Netto and Sohal, 1999;532, D’Netto, 1994;</p>
		<p>199; D’Netto and Sohal,1999;532, D’Netto, 1994);</p>	<p>as well as to underutilisation of skills, experience, and potentials of a diverse workforce, etc</p>	
8.	<p>Stakeholders’ Theory: highlights the fact we are all in this global environment together and needed each other while being socially responsible to each other through the stakeholder theory model.</p>	<p>Value of difference and value of mutuality; governments, employees, management, employers, shareholders, the wider society, etc.; Profitability vs welfare, wellness, and wellbeing of all globally.</p>	<p>It highlights the value of action of one affecting the other: the phenomenon of social inclusivity: what one does do affect the other and vice versa. We should be mindful of the climate change impact, so there is a need to respect profit and welfare, and wellbeing.</p>	<p>Freeman, (1984;1982; Fried man, 1979; Dodd,1932; Smith, 1776; Caroll1979; Doob, 2013)</p>

9.	<p>Globalisation as with the Stakeholders model, the concept of globalisation is another critical influence as it perceives/promotes the world as a single unit or component to do business, trade, employment, technology, etc. (Eguruze, forth coming)</p>	<p>The emphasis on “The removal of barriers between countries, either culturally, technologically, or economically, globalization allows the free trade of goods, services, information, and money both within and between nations” (Scott,2001:288</p>	<p>It re-inforces the value of this subject matter of research: diversity is all about working together; bringing people of different text closer, collaborating and promoting team spirit with respect for each other and regardless of who and how we look, or where one locates/resides, gender, etc</p>	<p>Scot, 2001; Eguruze, forthcoming</p>
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Source: Adapted from Eguruze, 2016,2017;2020); Significantly Improved by Researchers, 2020

As noted in table 2.1 above the review observed two major contrasting diversity management theories/approaches that various world leaders had deployed to govern, control people and resources over time: between the periods pre-1500s-1900s and between 1900 to date. Regrettably, in the first phase or era, the world did experience bitter human brutality against fellow humans. That was simply because people are different: difference in terms of race or colour, gender, culture and religion, geographical location. (which are characteristics of diversity).

The period covering from pre-colonial to colonial times up to the end of the second world war (WWII); around 1945, and subsequently justified the introduction of the United Nations (UN) as an International Governing Organisation, and then the subsequent formation of the Universal Declaration of human rights was enacted by the United Nations (UDHR, 1948, Art25). This then followed with the International Convention on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights (ICESCR, 1996, 2006).

These are crucial international instruments that are being used to control the excesses of humankind against fellow human beings across the world; ultimately to maintain world peace and foster a spirit of harmony (UN, 1945; UDHR, 1848; ICESCR, 1996, 2006). As noted, during the period (covering the 16th century (1500s) -20th centuries (1900s), three old, experienced diversity theories made based on Darwinism theory (1859) Natural Divisions of Labour; Natural Selection; Ethnicity; Socially constructed; Survival of the fittest (weak dies out; while the strong lives on/conquer/dominate. Unfortunately, this period depicted series of inhuman diversity management practices that were rejected: conquer and dominate; dominance; slavery/slave labour, capitalism versus socialism, less freedom; colonialism, Neo-colonialism; Explore/ Exploitation; comparative advantages; Migrations/ resettlements; fewer choices, and the subsequent divisions of the world into 1st, 2nd. & 3rd World; developing versus developed nations, etc.

This also aligns with the findings of Agyris (1964) in his Maturity and Immaturity Personality Development Model in which he found seven changes should take place in the personality of an individual if he/she is to develop into a fully mature person.

This author explored passive to increased activity; dependence to independence; behaviour in a limited way to capable of behaving in diverse ways; being erratic and shallow to a deeper thinking and stronger person. These changes build stronger personality development, improved self-confidence, and self-esteem.

Similarly, this new framework/model may offer a new constructive way forward which could be useful in social class measurement and provide a stronger basis for diversity management practices and learning. Learning is about changes: change brought about by developing new skills, understanding new ways of working together or learning something new; in attitude and behaviour, as well as through collectively working together as a team (Reece and Walker, 2003, 2007; Eguruze, 2017: 43). Like the behaviourists, the researcher believes that through

positive learning from being in a state of need or the experience of a state of lack of everything, motivation could bring about positive situational change which is one of the important aspects under investigation.

2.5) Equality

Equality is fairness. The main goal of promoting equality is to attain the highest levels of justice among individuals or groups and most importantly within the group of people with protected characteristics. For these groups to achieve equality, governments, employers, and policy maker must ensure that those who are disadvantaged acquire tools needed to access opportunities as their peers (World Economic Forum Report, 2020:1).

On the other hand, there is a frustrating quandary over the raising levels of inequality around increasing diversity inequality is rising even in those countries that have experienced rapid growth. The social and economic consequences of inequality are profound and far reaching: a growing sense of unfairness, perceived loss of identity and dignity, weakening of social fabrics, eroding trust in institutions, disenchantment with political processes and on erosion of the social contract” (World Economic Forum Report, 2020:1). This is why studies of this nature are vital to highlight the issues and find sustainable solutions, one of which is that comprehensive effective management of diverse force management practices approach is necessary to tackle inequality in society globally. This is supported by the view narrative that the response to inequality must include a concerted effort to create new pathways to socio-economic mobility, ensuring again, studies such as this current one is vital in creating better awareness of the need to tackle diversity issues globally, and not necessary for the Middlesex-London care homes or UK health and social care industry.

To this, there is the main legislation that provides guidance to equality in the UK: The Equality Act 2010 (as amended); it works very closely with the other instruments such as The Human Rights Act, 1988 and The Commission of Equality and Human Rights (EHRC) which is an independent body for enforcement purposes over breach of human rights and equality issues. Before the Equality of Act 2010, legislations were in operation separately.

These include among others: The Equal Pay Act 1970; The Sex Discrimination Sex Discrimination Act 1975 (c. 65); The Race Relations Act of 1976; The Disability Discrimination Act 1995. The Equality Act 2010 provides protection against discrimination for people who possess one or more of the nine specific protected characteristics: age, disability, marriage and civil partnership, pregnancy and maternity, race, religion and belief, sex, gender reassignment and sexual orientation. In fact, the Equality Law makes it unlawful to discriminate based on race, age, gender, sexual orientation, religion, disability, marital status, etc.

2.6) An Outline of International Perspectives/Comparisons on Equality and Diversity Management Tools

This research believes that since diversity is a global issue that is affecting several countries across the world, it would be useful to highlight the diverse ways in which different countries engage efforts in trying to tackle the challenges posed by lack of diversity or inequality in the various workplaces or society (Joplin & Daus,1997). This is presented below in table 2.2.

Table 2. 2 Summary of Equality and Diversity Management Legal Instruments/Impact across the World

Serial. No.	Country	The Relevant Diversity & Equality Legislation	Impact/Consequences at the Workplaces	Approximate Periods
1.	USA	The Civil Rights Act of 1964, (Particularly Title VII), (The CRA), as well as the Age Discrimination in Employment Act of 1967, etc.	Diversity management gained momentum during the 1960s (through to the 1980s) with the passing of The Civil Rights Act of 1964, (particularly Title VII), (The CRA), as well as the Age Discrimination in Employment Act of 1967, etc. when the US saw the need to formally promote workplace diversity. Before the CRA, President John F. Kennedy in 1961 recognised a President's Committee on Equal Employment Prospect intending to end discrimination in employment by the government. (Armstrong, 2010:3).	1960s-1980s
2.	The European Union (EU)	Article 13 of the Amsterdam Treaty (1997)	In fact, in the European Union (EU), the comparative legal instrument was Article 13 of the Amsterdam Treaty (1997), which provided the European Union with necessary powerful legal platform through which struggle against discrimination and the support of equality and promotion for diversity at workplaces were	1997

			strengthened, as also cited by Armstrong (2010:1)	
3.	The Republic of Ireland	the Employment Equality Act (1998) and later the Equality Act (2004), including the Article 13 of the Amsterdam Treaty (1997), as member of the EU.	The Irish legislation that ensures workplace equality derives mainly from the Employment Equality Act (1998) and later the Equality Act (2004), which forbids discrimination against employees and those seeking employment in relation to gender, age, race, religious affiliation, disability, marital status, family status, sexual orientation, and membership in the traveller community (an indigenous ethnic Irish group), as also cited in Armstrong, 2010:2).	1997 -2004

4.	India	The Equal Remuneration Act (1976), with Disabilities Act (1995) and the (Indian, Equal Remuneration Act 1976), etc.	<p>By contrast, the relevant legislation in promoted diversity and equality issues; it enforces equal pay for men and women, while The Persons with Disabilities Act (1995), focuses on disability, whereas.</p> <p>The Indian, Equal Remuneration Act 1976) legislation specifically sets out an employment target of 3% for persons with disabilities in government organizations. India also adopted some stringent affirmative action rules to undo damage associated with the caste system (Armstrong, 2010:3)</p>	1976/1995
5.	China	the Employment Promotion	By contrast, in China, the relevant legislation	1991, 1995/2008

		<p>Law (2008), as per (Armstrong, 2010:3). It was stated this piece of Chinese Employment Promotion Law (2008)</p>	<p>was noted to be the Employment Promotion Law (2008). It was stated this piece of Chinese Employment Promotion Law (2008) which also incorporated previous legislations, clearly prohibited discrimination based on race, ethnicity, sex, and religion has been prohibited since 1995. Further, discrimination against disabled persons has been prohibited since 1991, hepatitis B carriers since 2007, and human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) carriers, acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS) sufferers, and their family members, etc. (Armstrong, 2010:3).</p>	
6.	Globally: The United Nations (UN)	<p>The United Nations Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR, 1948 (Art25); International Convention on the Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR, 1996, 2006).</p>	<p>These two fundamental International Treaties Instruments are the basic sources of International; that created the conducive environment, which made it possible for the world to work together to tackle diversity issues/challenges including equality, oppression, discrimination, racism, poverty, access to education, health and social cares, access to affordable housing, etc.</p>	1948,1996/2006

7.	The UK	The Equality Act 2010 (as amended); The Human Rights Act, 1988 and The Commission of Equality and Human Rights (EHRC)	Before the Equality of Act 2010, several legislations were in operation separately: The Equal Pay Act 1970; The Sex Discrimination Act 1975 (c. 65) The Race Relations Act of 1976 The Disability Discrimination Act 1995. The Equality Act 2010 provides protection against discrimination for people who possess one or more of the nine specific protected characteristics: age, disability, marriage and civil partnership, pregnancy and maternity, race, religion and belief, sex, gender reassignment and sexual orientation.	1970s/2010
		(which is an Independent Body for enforcement purposes over breach of human rights/equality issues		

Source: The Researcher's Construction, 2020

As noted above the table 2.2 depicts an outline of international comparisons on the concept of diversity management. It provides an opportunity for learning how the key world countries have managed the challenges relating to diversity and equality in their respective countries. It suggests diversity is indeed a global phenomenon and not just a matter for the UK. In fact, this justifies the significance of incorporating this table 2.1.

The review noted that the diversity and equality movement has started over the years in several countries, while the common message this review found is that, across several countries around the globe, the ideas, knowledge and values that are being shared in relation to diversity and equality study is that: -

“...people cannot be treated less favourably on the basis of any of these criteria (age, gender, disability, sexual orientation, religion, etc.,) at their workplaces over issues such as dismissal, pay, harassment and sexual harassment, working conditions, promotion, access to employment, and several other areas” (Armstrong, 2010:3; CIPD, 2006)

2.7) Workforce and/or Employee

The term workforce (or alternatively called a labour force) refers to all the employees in this research. Although it may also include the unemployed in another context, as well as include those working for either a single organisation or industrial sector or a wider geographical area, city, state or even a country, or the world (Seager, 2008). In the context of diversity management perspective, workforce comprises people who are different and share different attitudes, needs, desires, values, and work behaviours (Deluca and McDowell, 1992; Morrison, 1992; Rosen and Lovelace, 1991). Within a company, its value can be labelled as its "Workforce in Place". The workforce of a country includes both the employed and the unemployed labour force (Seager, 2008). In this research all these terms: workforce or labour force or employee are used interchangeably.

An employee is person who works for another person for compensation such as a wage or salary for his or her services rendered. This may include a manager, but not an owner, or another below an executive level. Scholars' definition is that an employee is someone who works for a remuneration or gets paid for the work or services he or she renders to an employer in the form of compensation, which may be a wages or salaries (Dakin and Armstrong, 1989:187-94); Armstrong, 2006, 2012; CIPD, 2006, 2017,2018). However, for tax purposes, the Government definition is that: -

“...an employee is someone who works under an employment contract” (Gov.UK, 2020). In, addition to wages and/or salary, employee may be entitled to a wide range of employee benefits, which may be in different forms including: wages, salary, bonus or even share options, gratuities, disability insurance, the use of facilities such as gym/recreational facilities, holiday or vacation entitlements(paid or unpaid), sick leave, maternity/paternity entitlements, motor vehicle/car insurance, housing entitlements, health insurance, dental insurance, life assurance, disability income protection, funding for education or training and development, travelling

allowances, profit sharing, social security, among others. Often, since an employment is a relationship between two parties (employer and employee), the relationship is being regulated by employment law and the day-to-day administration of an employment is guided by contract of employment (Dakin and Armstrong, 1989:187-94); Armstrong, 2006,2012; CIPD, 2006, 2017, 2018; Keynes, 1935, 1936). It is important also to remark; tax payment out of the wages and/or salary, is a crucial element of the social responsibility and duty of an employee (Gov.UK, 2020). While it equally vital to look after employee welfare and wellbeing (Keynes, 1935, 1936; Smith, 1776; Karl, 1887; Ricardo, 1859).

2.8) Previous studies on Diversity and Equality

In fact, earlier researchers have already queried the lack of result as relatively little hard data supports the claim that diversity and equality initiatives influence firm performance (Monks, 2007). Some scholars have examined companies' performances in great depth and have noted that there are financial improvements to be gained such as return on investment, revenue, costs, and profits through effective utilization of diverse/workforce diversity management practices (Jayne & Dipboye, 2004; Seager, 2008; Armstrong, 2010). Others argued, organisations frequently protect such hard data because it is potentially commercially sensitive (Monks; Armstrong, 2010).

This review remarked that the ability to translate equality and diversity policies into improved and positive performance are highly contextualised but useful and relevant (Armstrong, 2010; Jayne & Dipboye, 2004; Kochan et al., 2003). Previously research has tended to be context specific (e.g., Jackson & Joshi, 2004; Kochan et al., 2003). Some focused on how the diversity and equality movement shifted from initial thoughts "equal opportunity" into legislative instruments (Wilson, 1996; Armstrong, 2010). Others saw it as to be treated as a strategic business priority for improving performance (Carnevale & Stone, 1994; European Commission, 2005; Armstrong, 2010), while other scholars view it as a just and fair way to utilise business resources despite little tangible evidence showing that equal opportunity initiatives are an appropriate use of resources (Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development (CIPD), 2006; Jayne & Dipboye, 2004, in Armstrong, 2010:3). Currently, managing diversity is enjoying a high profile in organisational debate, partly due to changes in workforce demographics, increased globalisation, and changes in organizational structures" (Armstrong, 2010:3). In fact, by contrast, others were even focused on tackling inequalities using variables such as poverty arising from lack of diversity/workforce diversity management practices that resulted in low pay, pay gaps and zero-hour contracts which are unfair and had resulted in working-poverty and inequalities, (Eguruze, 2016, 2017, 2019, 2020). Yet specific research has not yet been made towards the benefits and challenges with respect to the nursing homes in Middlesex-London regions, which highlights the research gap as well as justification for the research.

Previous studies relating to diversity inequality around the globe have been equally explored. To this the review noted the considerable research and legal efforts that has been put into diversity and equality issues since the 1960s through to the 1980s and 1990s to date, that has been undertaken (Griggs, 1995; Kossek and Lobel; (1996; Joplin & Daus, 1997; Wentling, 2004; Monks, 2007; Seager, 2008; Armstrong, 2010; Eguruze, 2016, 2017; as well as international diversity legislative efforts have been examined. The Equality Act, 2010; Equality and Human Rights (EHRC, 2009; ICESCR, 1996, 2006; The European Union (EU)

Article 13 of the Amsterdam Treaty 1997; The Chinese Employment Promotion Law 2008;

The Indian, Equal Remuneration Act 1976/The Indian, Persons with Disabilities Act 1995;

The Irish Employment Equality Act 1998/The Equality Act (2004); as well as The US The

Civil Rights Act of 1964 (particularly Title VII)/ (The CRA)

The Age Discrimination in Employment Act of 1967,

Nevertheless, fewer positive outcomes have been achieved with respect to diversity and equality challenges at workplace over all these long years. In fact, an analysis of these empirical/scholarly efforts and legislative instruments found that: -

- (i) Neither using or only focusing on a few variables (or acting in isolationists strategy) to tackle diversity/workforce diversity management practices are yielding very little or less than desired impact and hence diversity/workforce diversity management challenges with employee performance issues such as high turnover, absenteeism and burnout, etc. issues are persisting.
- (ii) Although focusing on a single or a few factor variables in tackling such diversity/workforce diversity management challenges do result in some or limited outcomes but not sufficiently enough to eliminate workforce diversity management practices challenges; and
- (iii) It was also noted that using a multidimensional variables and collaborative model may have the probability of succeeding in overcoming inequality. It appears truly little use or less is made the multidimensional and collaborative approach, and which is why this research is attempting to adopt, explore/and experiment this new model/framework for intervention. It is believed that this new model/framework would be able to bring about an improved employee performance and ultimately better productivity for the Middlesex-London based Nursing Homes.

2.9) Researcher's Integrated Diversity/Workforce Diversity Management Practice Model for Nursing Homes in Middlesex-London (RI- DWDMPNHML)

Based on the above findings, there is a diagrammatic representation of the researcher idea on diversity management.

2.9.1 New Conceptual Framework - Researcher's Integrated Diversity Management Approach for Nursing Homes in Middlesex London

Conceptual Framework Figure 2. 1 Researcher's Integrated Diversity Management Approach for Nursing Homes in Middlesex-London (Source: The Researcher's Construction 2020)

Variable codes:

- 1) Diversity/diversity management practices
- 2) Selected diversity dimension
- 3) Selected diversity management practice
- 4) Age; (4a= More facts on age diversity promotion)
- 5) Gender; (5a= Results from data on gender diversity)
- 6) Ethnicity: (6a= Data on ethnicity and performance),
- 7) Motivational Schemes; (7a More proposed information on motivational approaches)
- 8) Flexible working: (8a= responses on Flexibly working)
- 9) cross-cultural training (9a= what employees proposed about cross-cultural training)
- 10) Enhanced employee Performance.

2.9.2) Phase 1- Diversity and diversity management practices

Phase one of the framework shows the diversity dimensions and the practices within nursing homes. The list of legislation, policies/ procedures, practices, and the dimensions of diversity included. It is important that as with others, nursing homes in Middlesex-London region are managed in such a way in compliance with the current law relating to diversity and inequality (Equality Act 2010, as amended), which covers nine protected groups. It is crucial to remember it is unlawful to discriminate against or exclude persons based on race (and ethnicity), region, gender, age, disability, sexual orientation, etc. In support of this, scholars have argued it would boost performance if employers adopted an inclusive or participative, involving and engaging approach rather than an exclusive approach (Armstrong, 2012; Dunnette). As represented the researchers Selects the diversity dimensions as well as management practices applicable within the nursing homes and further explored the six ideas from the employee perspective.

2.9.3) Phase 2- Diversity Characteristics

The diversity variable is relevant and useful factor in the model. As previously stated, diversity is about respecting and positively embracing difference of people. “Valuing everyone as individuals - as employees, customers, and clients” and although this view tends to imply inclusivity, it implies a lack of respect for diversity, there is no inclusion, or social exclusion prevails (CIPD, 2006). So, the concern here is whether there is inclusion, that it raises the question whether people’s (individuals or groups differences are respected, appreciated, valued or recognised, and utilised to their full potential, so as to make them feel belong and which in turn would enable the people to work harder and happier as to put in their possible best for the organisation. The solution to this is to adopt inclusive strategies to overcome this change as some scholars already suggested (Wenling, 2004; Griggs,

1995) and Kossek and Lobel,1996); not only would it be deemed discriminatory, but also it would be a breach of their human rights to not respect and/or discriminate on basis of their race, disability, gender, age, sexual orientation, religion, etc.(Equality Act 2010, as amended); Human Rights 1988). Further, other scholars have argued that there would be benefits to embrace diversity approach for the purpose of improving patients' care and/or patient's access to care within a diverse workforce; implementation of diverse workforce practices; improving patients' satisfaction level and compliance (Ellis et al., 2003; Gombe et al., 2005; Wambari, 2014). This research suggests that Middlesex-London Nursing should embrace diversity approaches.

2.9.4) Phase 3 The Concept of Diversity management practices

The management of diversity is a social discipline that deals with the behaviour of people and human insights (Sanders 1991). As already stated above it originated from North America to replace the stereotypical nature of affirmative action (AA) and equal employment opportunity (EEO) by helping disadvantaged groups of people gain access to a variety of roles not previously opened to them (Summers,1991). With the increasing diversity of the global workforce, organisations are working with policies and programmes to enhance recruitment, inclusion promotion and retention of employees who are different from the normal by creating level playing fields and opportunities for those groups that were previously excluded from them (O'Hare,1993). This study suggests that nursing homes will benefit from embracing diverse management practices that are positively motivating, flexible and culturally aware and/or accommodating.

2.9.5) Phase 4 Age diversity and employee performance

As with gender and diversity variables, age is equally critical and relevant in the framework. Age is one of the vital characteristics of physical activity. As a person advances in age, there is the propensity to lose strength and energy, so is with engagement of older employees and performance (DiPietro et al. 2001). However, these patterns may be highly dependent on the type of physical activity (Bijnen et al. 1998, DiPietro et al. 1989, 2001). In nursing homes where the job requires the use of considerable physical work especially in front line roles, the results above could be used to justify this literature. As the employees get older their numbers reduce dramatically, their work patterns the relationship to health and function changes.

It is also noted that younger workers are more likely to represent the future, more likely to be innovative, as well as may have had positive impact on the life expectancy of the organization in terms of succession planning (Dychtwald et al., 2004). According to Barrington and Troske (2001), age heterogeneity may have potential benefits in terms of productivity. Additionally, extant literature pointing to the fact age is factor of organisational performance and productivity: age-diverse teams can improve firms' financial performance (Ararat et al., 2010; Kim & Lim, 2010; Mahadeo et al., 2012), although there are scholars who found otherwise.

There are also a set of counter studies that found that age diversity may weaken firm's social performance (Hafsi & Turgut, 2013), profitability (Ali et al., 2014), and strategic changes (Tarus &Aime, 2014). In fact, some

researchers have found a relationship between age and risk. They have found that younger employees have higher tendency to make risky decisions (Cheng, Chan, & Leung, 2010) to signal to the market that they possess superior abilities (Prendergast & Stole, 1996). So, it is important to be critical of this. On the other hand, older employees prefer lower risk due to the threat to financial security and are associated with lower financial leverage, lower capital expenditures, and higher cash holdings (Berger, Kick, & Schaeck, 2014; Bertrand & Schoar, 2003).

Further, in terms of career development, more issues are considered; younger employees may be more risk-averse since they face more uncertainty about their future careers than their older counterparts (Holmstrom, 1999), while older employees are not afraid of career concerns due to their cumulative human capital (Nguyen, Hagendor, & Eshraghi, 2015). However, researchers also stated results suggesting that both older and younger employees must work together to form a coherent and viable corporate culture, as well as for purpose of critical succession planning (Dychtwald et al, 2004), as stated earlier. Age heterogeneity on its own has a negative influence on individual productivity especially in the case of routine tasks, where there are no considerable gains from age heterogeneity that could offset the increasing costs resulting from greater age heterogeneity (Gellner & Veen, 2009). Therefore, one can be tempted to state that in companies where some or part of the job description is routine types of work, an increasing age heterogeneity overall leads to a decline in productivity. It is important to state that age diversity in the health care sector has received scanty attention and because age diversity may impact the process of equality and decision making, age diversity and its influence on performance will be studied. Hence suggesting inclusion approach is preferable at nursing homes within the Middlesex-London region.

2.9.6) Phase 5- Gender diversity and employee performance

As with the diversity, the gender factor within the model is crucial and relevant. This has also generated research interests. According to Abbas and Hameed (2010), there exist three elements of gender discrimination: gender discrimination in recruitment, gender discrimination in promotion, and gender discrimination in the provision of goods and facilities. However, there are contrary studies that points to otherwise; studies have persistently found that gender composition of the workforce will impact on the individual, organisational, or group performance (Gupta, 2013; Svyantek & Bott 2004; Joshi & Erhardt 2003; industry (Jackson & Schuler 1995). Additionally, it was found that women are proficient in verbal and interpersonal skills, therefore having female leaders in organisations could lead to higher engagement and better retention of a diverse workforce (Nkomo & Cox, 1996), whereas men are good at mathematics (Nkomo & Cox, 1996), so a combination of these various skills are both needed and could make a difference. Furthermore, according to Emiki & Eunmi (2009), the considerable number of workforce diversity remains ineffective if gender issues are not first recognised and managed. In fact, tokenism leadership role or marginalisation and/or being undervalued, within workforce may not help (Cox, 1994; Cassel, 2000; Wambari, 2014). Therefore, this research suggests that Middlesex-London nursing may gain by learning

from these. Based on these, recognising, and embracing the skills of women would make a positive impact on employee performance and indeed organisational productivity.

2.9.7) Phase 6- Ethnicity diversity and employee performance

As with diversity, gender and age, ethnicity is another crucial variable. In fact, according to scholars, ethnicity refers to the identification of a group based on perceived cultural uniqueness or as individuals belonging to a group of people with the same nationality or ethnic origin, or race (Noon, 2007; Morgan & Vandy, 2009). Although others may perceive ethnicity differently, for example, it is known in multiple ways and has been identified to portray race, nationality, or ethnicity (Niederle, 2013). Other scholars see it as racial differences (Allport 1954, p. 192) while others see cultural diversity more in terms of nationality. And as previously stated, in these ethnically diverse situations, according to literature evidence, cross-cultural training is important; cross-cultural training addresses the differences in cultures in areas for example of food handling and preparation (Kosher, Halla), training around forced marriages and genital mutilation. Employees with such cross-cultural training will enhance awareness within the team and reduce intercultural conflict (Naumann, 1992; Friedlander & Walton 2000). As previously stated, tokenism leadership role or marginalisation and/or being undervalued, within workforce may not help (Cox, 1994; Cassel, 2000; Wambari, 2014).

Over the last few decades organisations were highly homogenous but today employees are more diverse in terms of ethnicity which could be an aspect of compliance or a way of integration of migrants into the UK society (Jewson, Mason, Drewet & Rossiter, 1995; De Vries, et al., 2005; Ely & Thomas, 2001). However, Ely & Thomas (2001) matching an employee with a client from their ethnic background will facilitate a better understanding of the client's needs. Opstal (2009) highlights a beneficial role of ethnicity and states organizational performance does not only concern (strategic) outcomes such as competitive advantage but also the way these outcomes are achieved; the desired way of working in the organisation like the efficient use of all resources. As organisations become more diverse along ethnic lines, it makes more sense to pay attention to how distinct groups interact with one another at work (Pitts et al., 2010). Organisations must be able to manage their diverse workforce in such a way that they can maximise the merits of this diversity and minimise its disadvantages (Opstal, 2009). Therefore, it becomes more important to study why ethnic diversity can sometimes positively or negatively impact on work-related outcomes leading to the formulation of the third research question. Thus, incorporating the variable in the framework would indeed be beneficial to improving management of nursing home within Middlesex-London region.

2.9.8) Phase 7 Motivational Schemes and employee performance

As presented in the framework, this is the first management practice variable to be examined. Motivation is in fact, seen as a process of stimulating people to take a desired course of action or in other words, any act which inspires employees to work better or harder (Cole, 2004, 2005; Schein, 2010, Armstrong, 2012). These may be

rewards in cash or financial or even in kind including social rewards (Dailey and Kirk, 1992; Gupta, 1998). These motivational incentives may even be resource based in that an enriched and well-resourced organisational diversity practice should be valuable to the individuals receiving it. It is important to support workers with all the necessary tools: adequate wages, good working conditions and environment, holiday opportunity, promotional opportunity, participative and involvement in policy decision opportunities, promotion/training, and development, etc., as these may have impact on their performances. As scholars outlined; Maslow's hierarchy of needs model in the study of motivation and personality study, have indicated that if employees sense of feeling of belonging needs is not addressed, then, they (employees) are less likely to achieve to the best of their own potential and vice versa (Maslow, 1943, 1954, 1970) as well as their two way motivating and hygiene studies (Herzberg 1959), as well as supported by other studies in leadership/management context, McGregor's theory X and Y (1960), Human Side of Enterprise project (1960) equally exerted a profound impact on the learning of an employment or leadership practices that may positively or negatively influence workplace setting such as nursing homes. It pointed out that if workers are supported and motivated, they are likely to excel in their performances. Similarly, if nursing employees are included in policy formulation and implementation processes, they too have enhanced performance (McGregor, 1960). It is critical to know more as to why the practice is not popular within the nursing home setting in the UK.

More broadly, Herzberg's states that factors that lead to motivation/job satisfaction at workplace setting include recognition, of efforts praises, creativity, innovation, commitment achievement e.g., promotion, status, working conditions creative interesting work environment that everyone will love/respect/be happy, supportive-supervision responsibility (delegation), growth (including providing opportunities for professional development/training), etc. These are also referred to as intrinsic elements of the work. On the other hand, the extrinsic factors, Hygiene factors/Dissatisfaction and frustration, include, salary (pay and benefits; honest salary), supervision (supportive/effective), company policies, job security, relations with supervisors and with other employees, and status within the company, etc. (or extrinsic elements) relating to work.

2.9.9) Phase 8 Flexible working and employee performance

This is another example of diversity management practice. Extant literature pointed to the fact that built in flexibility into the policy; avoid favouritism and/or discrimination when applying or implementing policies to different employees; there needs to be great consistency and transparency in policy and action/practice (Equality Act 2010, as amended). It might be very difficult to ignore an employee facing outside challenges and for the interest of workers welfare and wellbeing versus a company's performance and productivity, it would make sense to be flexible working, so that employees feel that they are part of the company and decisions taken with their opinions in mind (Hertzberg, 1959). However, it must be noted that there should be consistency in policy administration in order not breach the Equality legislation for being accused of discrimination. It was noted that

tokenism leadership role or marginalization and/or being undervalued, intergroup differences will not be useful in terms of boosting employee performance (Cox, 1994; Cassel, 2000; Wambari, 2014). Nursing homes could benefit from this knowledge in the running of Middlesex-London region.

2.9.10) Phase 9 Cross Cultural Training and employee performance

Some scholars may favour training on diversity lines as it may lead to competitiveness and in fact, competitive advantages (Porter, 1985, 2008; Armstrong, 2012). Similarly, creating and providing opportunities for professional development, including training and developments of employees is always a job-satisfier, according to Herzberg (1959).

As previously stated, organizational attributes such as company type, organisational culture, company location should be considered when adopting a diverse workforce (Patrick and Kumar, 2012). The company type plays a significant role in deciding whether to employ a diverse workforce or not, and this is because organisations employ people based on size or customers they serve. The company culture usually includes a set of values, practices, people, place, and history and it is crucial to reflect and recognise this critical variable in the management practices (Patrick and Kumar, 2012; Melbourne, 2017). interesting – maybe if there was more diversity in specific selling locations, it may increase sales as a whole market is not being tapped by reducing diversity of staff and therefore customers!! The location of the company is considered because some countries respond to the concept of diversity differently (Welbourne, 2017). Therefore, another influencing reason for studying diversity in London nursing homes is in line with the above organization attributes and according to the Guardian, (2010) and Melbourne, (2017), the UK is one of the most diverse countries in the world. As previously stated, there is also evidence of the idea that employers tend to promote favouritism based on individuals or people they know or look like them are well documented over the years (Avery, 1979; Bernmardin & Beatly, 1984; Brewer & Kramer, 1985; Cascio, 1982; Tisui-Egan & O'Reilly, 1992, Wexley & Nemeroff, 1974 & Motowidlo, 1992; Hymowitz, 1989; Rosener, 1986; Schwartze, 1989).

2.9.11) Phase 10 Enhanced employee Performance

This is perceived to mean a possible increase in value form in relation to performance and/or productivity levels. Is it; fit-for-purpose, reaching quality measures; meeting and exceeding targets? This could be measured in terms of productivity -what an employee or an organisation achieves over time in terms of output. Performance is the process of quantifying both efficiency and effectiveness of actions in ways that serve the purposes of monitoring performance and identifying areas that need attention, enhance motivation, improving communications and reinforcing accountability (Eddy, 1998). Financial indicators were the main performance indicators which were used to measure performance, but recently, non-financial indicators are commonplace as a result some of these

indicators would be incorporated in the questionnaire for the measurement of employee performance as part of the study (Kaplan & Norton, 1992).

2.10) Perceptions on the Consequences of Poor Diversity/Workforce Diversity Management Practices within The Health and Social Care Industry

Table 2. 3 Linking various forms of discrimination/exclusion their impact/consequences on employee’s performance and organization productivity/ society – social realities.

Type of Workplace Diversity Challenges	Description of Poor diversity management practices	Consequences/Impact on Employees performance/Organisational Productivity	Inclusion Strategy/ Benefit	Benefits References
Discrimination/Racism	Discrimination occurs when organisations, governments, or individuals treat people differently because of personal characteristics like sexual preferences, age, sex, or race rather than their ability to perform their jobs and these actions have negative effects with	Inequalities; Disadvantages; Training cost of some programmes (White,1999) Unfortunately do hold people back, depriving people of achieving their optimum potential socially, economically, physically, mentally, culturally, cognitively, etc.; “Depicts/ tolerates “the narrative of the survival of the fittest, which implies the weak/ the unfit will lose or die out based	By adapting Effective diversity/workforce diversity management practices Tolerating others Valuing differences Redistributive legislation (Equality Act, 2010, as amended	White, 1999; Mor Barack, 2005; Darwinism, 1859; Eguruze, 2016, 2017, 2019, 2020)

	<p>access to employment, promotions, or compensation (Mor Barak,2005). Surveys conducted by Fernandez (1993) have found that most employees have perceived the following examples of discrimination in their companies. Women have a much harder time finding a mentor than men. Men often exclude many women from informal networks; customers do not accept a woman's authority as much as they accept men in similar situations. Women must</p>	<p>on the theory of the Darwinism (Eguruze,2016:13,2017; Darwinism, 1859;) Burning out; low morale; high turnover, low performance/productivity; lack of engagement; Class-war; Cumulative Poverty</p>		
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	<p>be better performers than men to go higher, and many women encounter some sexual harassment on the job; women are placed in jobs with no future, and women are penalised more for mistakes than men. Fernandez (1988) found that Fortune 500 CEOs approved that women in their organisations faced barriers that men did not in getting to the top. However, there are still obvious and some unobvious forms of discrimination that remain intact, even though discrimination in</p>			
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	<p>the workplace is outlawed. The national study conducted by the Families and Work Institute (Galinsky et al., 1993) revealed that women and minorities 27% (out of the 3400 participants) claimed to have been discriminated against at some time during their work lives.</p>			
<p>Pay-Gap (Pay disparities)</p>	<p>This may be a wage/salary differential between male/female works doing similar position or job description or responsibility</p>	<p>Training cost of some programmes; most common disparities come from one feeling superior. If management ignores such tensions, the company's performance may reduce (White, 1999); Unfortunately, do hold people back, depriving people of achieving their optimum potential</p>	<p>Ensuring social impact Adopting social marketing values</p>	<p>White, 1999</p>

		socially, economically, physically, mentally, culturally, cognitively, Class war; etc.		
Harassment	Harassment is any action or comment which can be subtle or obvious, based on sexual, racial, or any other inferences employees may make that is likely to cause offense and humiliation (Poole,1997). The Black's Law Dictionary (Black, 1990) defines sexual harassment as; "...a type of employment discrimination, which includes sexual advances, requests for sexual favours, and other verbal or physical	Training cost of some programmes (White, 1999); Unfortunately, do hold people back, depriving people of achieving their optimum potential socially, economically, physically, mentally, culturally, cognitively, etc.; Racism/Harassment has many negative effects and can be very costly to an employer in productivity as well as in cost of litigation and settlements (Tang & McCollum, 1996). Harassment distracts employees from focusing on task-related responsibilities, reduces productivity, and can lead to increased turnover.	Encouraging empowerment. Adopting mentoring schemes Effective communication (See Coles, 2004,2005) Employee voice	White, 1999

	<p>conduct of a sexual nature prohibited by Federal Law" (p. 1375). Sexual harassment ranges from unwanted casual touching to persistent appeals for sexual favours. Racial or ethnic harassment may include hostility or verbal abuse. In the business world, sexual harassment is widespread (Collins and Blodgett, 1981). Harassment has many negative effects and can be very costly to an employer in productivity as well as in the cost of litigation and settlements (Tang &</p>			
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	<p>McCollum, 1996). Harassment distracts employees from focusing on task-related responsibilities, reduces productivity, and can lead to increased turnover. Thacker and Gohmann (1996) conducted a study to determine the consequences of sexual harassment. They surveyed over eight thousand federal employees and found that harassment contributed to emotional and psychological trauma. Poole (1997) reported that harassment</p>			
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	<p>could harm the following five areas: physiological, emotional, career path, self-perception, social, and interpersonal relations. Regarding balancing work and family, many women who work in corporations face difficulties in balancing their work and their families. The study conducted by Morrison (1992) revealed the following findings regarding this issue. The struggle to balance home and work is a difficult situation that women must deal with, and often</p>			
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	<p>they must decide to postpone and even stop their career advancement. Having and taking care of children often conflicts with full-time dedication to a career; it is unfeasible for many women to continue to work evenings and weekends or frequently travel once they have children. Many organizational executives do not have much understanding or sympathy for work/family conflicts that women must solve. In addition to taking care</p>			
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	<p>of children, many other outside responsibilities of women, such as household chores, social obligations, and significant relationships, make it harder for them to meet the high-performance standards required for advancement (Stoner & Hartman, 1990). The conflict between work and family responsibilities continues to be a barrier, forcing some working women to quit their jobs and limiting the contributions of many talented women who stay (Morrison,</p>			
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	<p>1992; Stoner & Hartman, 1990). Although there is the belief that if family commitments are interfering with work-life then there is a need to train spouses to be more productive in the home. So that there is equality at home. By achieving this there, will equality at home. As a result, more equality is achieved at the workplace due to having fewer external commitments and more educated males in the workplace.</p>			
Prejudices	<p>Prejudices and Derogatory comments (based on race, gender,</p>	<p>Training cost of some programs; most common disagreement comes from one feeling superior.</p>	<p>“Capitalism would succeed without exploitation of the</p>	<p>(White, 1999); Haworth, 2018:17) Morrison, 1992;</p>

	<p>religion, sexual orientation, disability, etc.) - Due to ignorance, prejudice, feelings, or derogatory comments can give rise to negative feeling such as ethnocentrism, stereotyping, and cultural tensions. A belief that all stereotypes are a correct depiction of all members belonging to a certain group (Morrison, 1992; Noon 2007.</p>	<p>If management ignores such tensions, the company's performance may reduce (White,1999); Unfortunately, do hold people back, depriving people of achieving their optimum potential socially, economically, physically, mentally, culturally, cognitively, etc.; Burnout; high turnover, low performance/productivity lack of engagement.</p> <p>Prejudice is the inclination to make a negative remark towards people who are different in terms of ethnicity their background and/or racial characteristics (Morrison, 1992). According to Noon (2007), prejudice means making assumptions without any evidence.</p>	<p>working-class” (Haworth, 2018:17”</p> <p>“For businesses taking the opportunity to create efficiencies/ improve productivity is critical” (Haworth, 2018:17)</p>	<p>Noon 2007</p>
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Bullying		Training cost of some programs; most common disagreement comes from one feeling superior. If management ignores such tensions, the company's performance may reduce (White 1999); Unfortunately, do hold people back, depriving people of achieving their optimum potential socially, economically, physically, mentally, culturally, cognitively, etc.; Burnout	Adopting a marketing orientation approach is critical	White, 1999
Sexism	A form of discrimination but based on gender. "misogyny" misogynist/chauvinistic " a hatred of women." Vice versa: Etymologically speaking, that is right on the money, as the word combines the Greek root	Training cost of programs; most common disagreement comes from one feeling superior. If management ignores such tensions, the company's performance may reduce (White,1999); Burnout;	Inclusion/ more robust inclusive approach is needed.	White, 1999; Merriam-Webster's discretionary, 2014

	<p>for "woman" with the prefix</p> <p>“miso” meaning “hatred”</p> <p>(also found in "misandry," a hatred of men, and</p> <p>"(Webster dictionary, 2014)</p>			
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Xenophobia	Hate Speech; Antimigrant sentiments; long-held prejudices particularly among poor/workingclass refugees/migrants; sentiments /long-held prejudices particularly among poor and working-class; refugees/ migrants; manipulate public opinion around race, ethnicity, and origin; inflame tensions	Lack of clarity on the definition of xenophobia/hate speech; Training cost of some programs; most common disagreement comes from one feeling superior. If management ignores such tensions, the company's performance may reduce (White, 1999); Unfortunately, do hold people back, depriving people of achieving their optimum potential socially, economically, physically, mentally, culturally, cognitively, etc.; Inequalities; Disadvantages;	<p>The Strategies to Promote Inclusiveness:</p> <p>(Inclusivity)Acknowledge Differences; Offer Implicit Bias Training -- for Everyone; Provide Mentors; Let People Learn by Doing; Encourage-personal Evaluation; Ask Questions; Value All Diversity;</p>	White, 1999 UNHCR,2019;2020UDHR , 1948; ICESCR,1996;2006 Merinder-Webster dictionary.com, 2020
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	around race relations by driving the narrative of “White capital monopoly”; spread disinformation aimed at instigating hatred and inciting violence,	Extreme/ Cumulative Poverty; Eguruze, 216,2017, 2019;2020; UnitedNationsHigh Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), 2019,2020; “ <i>Xenophobia</i> is the fear and hatred of strangers or foreigners” Xenocentrism (Meridian-Webster dictionary.com, 2020)		
Culture clash: Conflict of interests in the context of workplace barriers	The conflict between work and family (among employees, including management versus employees ‘in the form of class conflict; as) responsibilities continues to be a barrier, forcing some working women to quit their jobs and limiting the contributions of many talented women	An increase in conflicts is detrimental to any team. When two or more individuals or groups do not agree on a course of action, conflicts arise; Training cost of some programs; most common disagreement comes from one feeling superior. If management ignores such tensions, the company's performance may (White, 1999); Unfortunately, do hold people back, depriving	Equal employment opportunity (EEO) originated from the USA, and it refers to the protection job candidates have against discrimination in any part of the employment process due to race, colour, marital status, disability, gender, age, country of origin, or any	White, 1999; Morrison,1992; Stoner & Hartman,1990; (Koys 2001).

	who stay (Morrison, 1992; Stoner & Hartman, 1990).	people of achieving their optimum potential socially, economically, physically, mentally, culturally, cognitively, etc., Burnout;	protected characteristics (Koys 2001).	
Low Wages	Pay rates are so low or at or below national minimum rates that make people who are working unable “to afford basic items for their day-to-day living due to low levels of their earnings, wages or salaries” (Eguruze, 2016:17, 2017); Like “Employing people for the sake of (and/or for the appearance of) keeping them in jobs to benefit the owners (capitalists); slave pays;	In-work Poverty; Zero Hours Contracts(are inhumane; depicts inhumanity; Poor employment terms; Unfortunately do hold people back, depriving people from achieving their optimum potential socially, economically, physically, mentally, culturally, cognitively, etc.; They would probably engage in two or more different jobs to meet their budgetary; This may hurt their welfare, wellness, and wellbeing; Leading to Burnout, Slave labour; Morrison (1992) stated that poor career planning and development	“When faced with alternative courses of action, choices had to be made; ultimately, society would be better off when corporations maximise profit and maximising the well-being of their employees with decent wages (and/or salaries)/associated benefits” (Eguruze, 2016:13, 2017; Keynes, 1935/1936)	Eguruze, 2016, 2017; 2019; Keynes, 1935,1936); TUC, 2017; Guimarin,2017; Oxfam, 2016, 2017, 2018; IMF/World Bank, 2016, 2017); Haworth, 2018

	(Haworth, 2018); “Zerohour contracts: companies are making millions, whilst paying as little as possible and paying low wages grudgingly” Poor employment-terms (TUC, 2017; Guimarin, 2017)	is mostly associated with a lack of opportunity for women and minorities to get the kind of work experiences that will qualify them for top-level positions; Lack of flexibility; 1% of the world rich controlling 99% of the global wealth (Oxfam, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019,2020; World Bank/IMF, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020); “Capitalism would succeed without exploitation of the working class” (Haworth, 2018:17)		
Racism	Is racism has come to seem a peculiarly arbitrary and awful form of oppression, one practice that it encouraged and justified has come to represent	Like discrimination, Racism/Harassment has many negative effects and can be very costly to an employer in productivity as well as in the cost of litigation and settlements (Tang & McCollum, 1996). Harassment	Affirmative action is active use of policies/procedures by the government to improve employment opportunities for females/minorities in	Collins and Blodgett, 1981; Poole, 1997; Merinder-Webster dictionary.com, 2020 Gostsis & Kortezi, 2010 Idan, 2020

	<p>that oppression at its most unspeakable, namely the practice of slavery Like discrimination, Racial or ethnic harassment may include hostility or verbal abuse. In the business world, sexual harassment is widespread.</p> <p>(Collins and Blodgett, 1981). “<i>Racism</i> has a broader meaning set including "a belief that racial differences produce the inherent superiority of a particular race." Racism is a classic example of a hate crime</p> <p>(Idan, 2020:14)</p>	<p>distracts employees from focusing on task-related responsibilities, reduces productivity, and can lead to increased turnover (). Harassment could harm the following five areas: physiological, emotional, career path, self-perception, social, and interpersonal relations.</p> <p>(Poole,1997).</p> <p>“...Hate crime affects all society: it could leave victim feeling shocked, angry, fearful and anxious; emotionally, psychologically, barriers, glass ceilings. It is crime that is based on hostility because of a person’s race, nationality, religion, sexual orientation, transgender identity or disability.” (Idan, 2020; p14)</p>	<p>employment to fight long-standing discrimination in these groups (Gostsis & Kortezi, 2010).</p> <p>Inclusivity/Inclusion,</p>	
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<p>Stereotypical behaviours.</p>	<p>A stereotype is "an exaggerated perception of a category" (Allport 1954, p. 191) to rationale one's conduct about that category. Stereotypes standardise qualities that are seen to be characteristics of a particular group; these traits are generalised to all individuals within that category (Ladkin, 2006). To this, there is numerous empirical evidence: the idea that employers tend to promote favouritism based on individuals or people they know or look like them are well</p>	<p>Stereotypes assigned to groups are usually simplistic, untrue, information that can hurt the personal and social identities of individuals (Ladkin, 2006). As noted by McKay et al., 2009, stereotyping has a damaging effect resulting from nonrecognition of the differences in social groups leading to inaccurate perceptions towards people. Not all stereotypes are wrong; some stereotypes have an aspect of truth (Morgan &Vandy, 2009).</p>	<p>Inclusion/ more robust inclusive approach is needed.</p>	<p>(Allport 1954, p. 191); (Ladkin, 2006). McKay et al., 2009; Morgan &Vandy, 2009).</p>
<p>Bias/favouritism,</p>		<p>Scholars argued that 'diverse employees' or less favoured employees are more likely to perform less and those 'affected often feel neglected' may not</p>	<p>Inclusion/ more robust inclusive approach is needed.</p>	<p>Avery, 1979; D'Netto, 1994; D'Netto and Sohal, 1999</p>

	<p>documented over the years (Avery, 1979; Bernmardin & Beatly, 1984; Brewer & Kramer, 1985; Cascio, 1982; Tisui-Egan & O'Reilly, 1992, Wexley & Nemeroff, 1974).</p>	<p>benefit from any main career paths (D.'Netto, 1994; D'Netto and Sohal,1999:532)</p>		
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Source: The Researcher's Construction, 2020

As noted above, Table 2.3, represents a summary that outlines some of the common forms that may result from poor diversity/workforce diversity management practices, which may have a negative impact on employees' performance, which may in turn impact on organisational productivity, as well as on societal welfare and wellbeing through its implicit influence on the gross domestic product (GDP). These may include among others, discrimination, harassment, pay gap (pay discrimination/disparities), prejudices, bullying, sexism, bias, favouritism racism, social exclusions, xenophobia, low wages, workplace conflicts (culture clash), etc. are common incidences at 21st-century workplaces² around the globe, not just in the UK, as noted by the wide range of extant literature(Collins and Blodgett, 1981, (Tang & McCollum, 1996; (White,1999); (Poole,1997); (Mor Barak,2005). Eguruze, 2016, 2017; Haworth, 2018; TUC, 2017; Guimarin, 2017)

Unfortunately, people are held back, depriving people to achieve their optimum potential socially, economically, physically, mentally, culturally, cognitively, etc. One of the remarkably impactful consequences is the phenomenon of xenophobia.

"...*xenophobia* is the fear and hatred of strangers or foreigners, whereas *racism* has a broader meaning set including" a belief that racial differences produce the inherent superiority of a particular race." Although they are similar, they are different enough that one can be both xenophobic and racist" (Meridian-Webster dictionary, 2020).

These disadvantages do exist and unfortunately do hold people back, depriving people to achieve their optimum potential socially, economically, physically, mentally, culturally, cognitively. It is something that individuals and organisations and, more so, governments will have to act together collectively to bring about positive changes to the industry and the wider society. Making constructive efforts towards valuing lives and valuing difference and respecting difference is like saving lives and saving improving the welfare, wellness, and wellbeing of people is deemed a win-win for all stakeholders (Eguruze, 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, 2019, 2020). To this end, it is worthwhile to make the necessary changes that are fundamentally critical towards achieving these ends. This would have a positive impact on employee performance and in turn improve organisational productivity, which in turn would improve the gross domestic product (GDP) (Eguruze, 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, 2019, 2020). The review also noted that workplace diversity management sometimes came with a high management cost (Armstrong,2010; Armstrong, 2006,2010; CIPD, 2006). Some types of diversity/workplace diversity management practices are discussed in more detail below.

2.11) Poor Career Planning and development

Morrison (1992) stated that poor career planning and development is mostly associated with a lack of opportunity for women and minorities to get the kind of work experiences that will qualify them for top-level positions. Poor career planning is one of the most frequent barriers among women and minorities. Also, Morrison observed that

organisational decision-makers are often reluctant to assign women and minorities to the challenging, high-profile jobs that are required to add credibility to their work record. Women and minorities often find that managers do not feel comfortable comparably assuming responsibility for their advancement to white males, partly because they are viewed as being less capable and, therefore, a higher risk (Gibbs, 1991; Jamieson & O'Mara, 1991; Mabry et al., 1990; Rosener, 1986; Thomas & Alderfer, 1989). Morrison (1992) found that women and minorities are usually given assignments that are less challenging, less visible, and not as important as the ones given to counterparts. According to Catalyst (1993), credential building experiences and career enhancing assignments are often unavailable to minorities and women. Wentling (1992) and Catalyst (1990) also found that the lack of career planning and planned job assignments for women is a serious barrier to their advancement. Women and minorities often do not know what is expected of them for upward advancement (Morrison, 1992).

2.12) Unsupportive work environment

Morrison (1992) found that women and minorities are often treated differently than their male colleagues. For example, they may be excluded from luncheons, social events, and even informal gatherings within the office. Also, they may not have access to the information they need to make informed decisions (Wentling, 1992). Women and people of colour are constantly under scrutiny; therefore, they must consistently demonstrate competency on the job, for they are under enormous pressure to do outstanding work continuously (Wentling, 1992). This creates a fundamental problem in that; if they need help, they cannot admit it and ask for help for fear of being marked as incompetent. Because of the pressure to be consistently outstanding and the need to avoid serious mistakes, they are not asking for help can result in detrimental consequences (Morrison, 1992; Wentling, 1992). Another factor that contributes to an unsupportive work environment for women and people of colour is a lack of role models and mentors, especially for those moving above middle management positions. Most people want to surround themselves with others like themselves. Even though people from different backgrounds may be just as competent as those who look, talk, and behave the same, often managers tend to hire and promote people like themselves (Carnevale & Stone, 1994). White men are usually not devoted to assisting and supporting someone with an unfamiliar perspective or values and may find it difficult to associate with such an individual (Morrison, 1992). This tendency adversely affects women and people of colour who are more likely to be different from the decision-makers who are making recommendations that affect their career advancement (Hanover, 1993).

2.13) Lack of mentors

Mentors are higher ranking, influential, senior organisational members with advanced experience and knowledge who are committed to providing upward mobility and support to a protégé's professional career (Collins, 1983; Kram, 1985; Roche, 1979). Since most high ranking, influential, senior organisational members with advanced experience are white males, and they are in the position to be mentors. White male mentors may not even

consider women or people of colour as candidates for protégé roles because they may be more comfortable in developing a professional and personal relationship with another white male. Several studies have found that a key element in the selection process is the degree to which the mentor identifies with the protégé and perceives the protégé as a younger version of himself (Blackburn, Chapman, & Cameron, 1981; Bowers, 1984; Lunding, Clements, & Perkins, 1978). The selection process may, therefore, be biased by the tendency of white male mentors to choose other white males over females or people of colour. The reluctance to sponsor a female or an ethnic minority may be because they perceive them as being a greater risk than their white male counterparts (Fitt & Newton, 1989).

Given that women and people of colour are numerically rare in top-level management positions, they may be a bigger risk to sponsor by a mentor. Lack of mentors and role models are barriers for many women and ethnic minorities. Mentors are extremely important to women and people of colour, especially since they need the guidance, encouragement, and advocacy that mentors can provide to overcome such obstacles as isolation, lack of credibility, and lack of political savvy (Jeruchim & Shapiro, 1992; Morrison, 1992). Not having a mentor who is trustworthy and knowledgeable about career mobility is a factor that further contributes to the problem of unwise career decisions (Morrison, 1992).

2.14) Inclusion

As noted throughout this discourse, thus far, the main crux of the conversation over diversity was predicated by divisions and conflicts without a resolve. So, at this moment, the review is committed to addressing the issue of exclusion, which is nothing rather than the concept of inclusion. From the perspective of the NHS, inclusion means that all people, regardless of their abilities, disabilities, or all people with health care needs, etc have the right to be respected and appreciated as valuable members of their communities (NHS, 2020). This implies inclusion, and is the extent to which diversity/workforce diversity management practices are prepared to acknowledge and appreciate? Alternatively, to tolerate and embrace differences for the good of all stakeholders. However, broader meaning of social inclusion may imply a process of considering all interests involved in a much fairer way; or improving the terms on which individuals and groups take part in society to improve the ability, opportunity, and dignity of those disadvantaged based on their identity (Armstrong, 2006, 2009, 2012; Royal College of Nursing 2020; NHS, 2020; Martin and Henderson, 2004; Clark and Copcutt, 1997). So, Social inclusion is about making all groups of people feel included or involving, engaging and participative, etc., where individuals or groups of individuals are excluded.

2.15) Exploration of the Ethical Case of Diversity

There are also the inherent ethical implications of diversity, which may not be that obvious. These may include elements of bias, consent to treatment by patient or in the process of writing a power of attorney, etc.,

responsibility, and data protection, reliability, and validity, moral, or it may also imply an element of carrying out social responsibility in governance as efficiently or effectively, as possible. So, in this sense, ethical diversity means diversity reflects the different values and beliefs people hold and adhere to. At one level this can be reflected in the total lack of ethics in the governance of nursing homes in the way and way employees of different racial backgrounds or age or gender or religion or even sexual orientation, etc. are frequently treated. It may be viewed unethical to discriminate for example against an employee based on the protected characteristic, as there may be widespread differences between individuals in terms of how employees are being treated overtly or subtly while carrying out their duties at work or it might be more prominent in the decision-making processes that exclude or include. As already stated, diversity indicates the way people are different and how one appreciates those differences, whereas ethics relates to how managers in this context may be seen to be keeping their employment contractual duties or social responsibilities: treating employees fairly and equally in terms of opportunities or pay differentials, making right and wrong decisions that discriminate against some employees or not based on gender or religious differences, in not following proper or open and fair recruitment processes, or in implementing certain business practices that are perceived to be right or wrong, etc.

Which is where the term inclusion may become necessary or relevant? The idea that employees of diverse ethnicities or ages or gender or religion should be included fairly in the decision-making process to avoid being discriminated against. Inclusion, therefore, is the process of resolving or tackling issues relating to diversity and equality. As previously stated, inclusion may be said to be the effort in setting up boundaries and social responsibilities in society to maintain some balance: a society free of discrimination or unfair treatment at the place of work: equal opportunities policy statements or diversity and equality policy statement, equal pay for men and women, minimum wages, efforts in relieving poverty or sickness or the needs of the old age, an organisation might concentrate on building the capacity of people in poverty (or people who are sick or old) to enable them to be included in society as a means of relieving their needs and promoting social inclusion. Additional strategies in which organisations such as nursing homes could do to reduce social exclusion (i.e., diversity and equality) or promote inclusion may include:

- Acknowledge/appreciating differences.
- Offer Implicit Bias Training-- for everyone e.g., multicultural training.
- Provide Mentors.
- Let People Learn by Doing. ... leadership by examples/by doing.
- Encourage Personal Evaluation, e.g., by undertaking 360 performance appraisals.

- Ask to Questions/encourage, e.g., freedom to speak and/or ask questions.
- Value All Diversity, e.g., valuing or respecting other cultures and/or traditions way of lives, etc.

As noted above, inclusion means that all people, regardless of their abilities, disabilities, or health care needs, have the right to:

- Be respected and appreciated as valuable members of their communities.
- Participate in recreational activities in neighbourhood settings (Royal College of Nursing 2020 14/01/2020; NHS, 2020)

2.16) The Strategies to Promote Inclusiveness

Acknowledge Differences, offer Implicit Bias Training -- for Everyone; Provide Mentors; Let People Learn by Doing; Encourage Personal Evaluation; Ask Questions; Value All Diversity; The research observed four critical diversity areas: What are the 4 types of diversity? The four types of diversity that will be examined are occupation, differences in skills and abilities, personality traits, and values and attitudes. For each type of diversity, the impact on individual behaviour will be described. One type of diversity is occupation. In fact, how best and how most effective and most efficient ways in which these various skills are used to achieve the best for the patients is most critical – in matters surrounding diversity and equality, and inclusion. What type of diversity can be found in the workplace? Workplace diversity comes in forms such as: race and ethnicity, age and generation, gender and gender identity, sexual orientation, religion, and spirituality.

2.17) Implementation approaches for Managers/Leaders of diversity

There are several approaches to cultivating and managing diversity in organisations (Stevens, Plaut, and Sanchez-Burks, 2008), These authors assume that some organisations demonstrate their commitment to promoting diversity via a range of 'diversity initiatives' that are implemented into daily practice, whereas others choose to adopt a 'colour-blind' approach to diversity. The colour-blind approach focuses on realigning workforce group identities with an overarching identity (Hogg and Terry, 2000), intending to decrease the emphasis on individual differences. It stems from the notion of 'treating everyone the same,' but this is criticised for being exclusionary and appealing only to nonminority groups (Markus et al., 2000). In contrast, the multi-cultural approach assumes that the differences between people are a source of strength for organisations, and these differences need to be embraced and nurtured (Stevens, Plaut, and Sanchez-Burks, 2008). With such an approach, a range of strategies are used to promote diversity including targeted networking and mentoring

programmes aimed at specific minority groups, 'diversity days' where the cultural background of diverse groups of staff is celebrated, and the provision of targeted and generic diversity training (Paluck, 2006).

However, using both approaches, organisations face challenges in that all staff will welcome neither approach. According to Verkuyten, (2005), The multicultural approach might be posing a threat to their social identity, and the colour-blind approach does not account for the structural disadvantages faced by minority groups (Noon, 2007). To overcome these limitations, Stevens, Plaut, and Sanchez-Burks (2008) propose an innovative approach to managing diversity, which is the 'all-inclusive multi-culturalism.' These authors think that this approach offers an alternative to the more traditional colour blind and multicultural ideologies by having a specific focus on employee inclusion, and the formation of high-quality authentic relationships between employees that are resilient, transparent, and which promote on-going learning. They further state that to implement such an approach, organisations need to create environments that are more inclusive of all members of the workforce with the implementation of policies and practices that are framed as benefitting everyone and more importantly communicating in a manner that does not label different groups or single them out.

Similarly, Richard, Kirby, and Chadwick (2013) argue that for diversity management to be implemented, organisations must develop mechanisms whereby cooperation and collaboration across all roles are supported, creating an inclusive environment that promotes togetherness. According to Ewoh (2013: 114), for such an environment to be created where diversity could be effectively managed, leaders across an organisation must be identified and supported. Besides, clear objectives relating to diversity must be communicated alongside the provision of appropriate training to help managers and leaders deliver these. He further reiterates that support and commitment from 'the top' are essential along with the recognition that 'bottom-up' input and engagement from diverse workers is needed to enhance the quality of decision making and the development of more innovative and sustainable policies. In agreement with this, Guillaume et al. (2014), argue that effective leadership is essential to making any strategy for managing diversity in organisation work.

To sum up, there is an increasing focus on the issue of diversity within the workplace because of increasing globalisation, changes in the labour market, and external regulatory diversity. In this present changing world, a diverse workforce brings high values to the organisation. In a society like the UK respecting the nationalities in the workplace will benefit the organisation by creating a competitive edge and enhancing productivity (DeSouza 2008). Most companies have diverse cultures because of their diverse workforce; therefore, managing diversity creates a safe environment for everyone and provides fair access to opportunities in the company. Nevertheless, there are also several challenges for organisations trying to implement diversity management effectively. Some of the identified drawbacks include increased staff turnover, which subsequently results in reduced organisational outcomes. Moreover, the ambiguity around the term 'managing diversity' itself adds another level of complexity for organisations and individual managers in implementing this agenda effectively. Therefore,

strategies and approaches are identified for implementing the effective management of diversity, and all focus on creating inclusive cultures within organisations, which require strong leadership and reinforcement in practice. Some of the approaches are discussed in more detail below.

2.18) Implementing changes that might come along with Conceptual Framework (Model)

Having brought about changes to the Nursing homes, it is expected that there may be changes against the status quo (the current mode of operations about diversity and inequality issues). So, it is important that significant changes might occur with the implementation of the suggested conceptual Framework or Model. Some of these potential changes are briefly analysed below.

2.19) Change and implications for the leadership of the Nursing Homes Management

Change management is a constant and an essential part of most organisations (Szamosi& Duxbury (2002). Due to rapid changes in demographics as well as cuts in funding in health and social care, organisations within this sector, for example, the public-funded care homes face from their counterparts in the private sector nationally and internationally. There may be various kinds of change: -

“...Change is almost inevitable due to the variety of factors either internal or external” (Eguruze, 2016:28, 2017).

These factors may arise from the implementation of this current (2.9 Researcher’s Integrated Diversity/Workforce Diversity Management Practice Model for Nursing Homes in Middlesex-London (RI-DWDMP-NHML) or these factors may include expansion, mergers or acquisitions, new technology, new leadership that may arise from the implementation of this new researcher’s model/framework. Alternatively, it may be due to changes relating to the political, legal, environmental, economic, technological, social, cultural, etc. factors (Eguruze, 2016,2017, 2019; Porters, 2008; Armstrong, 2006, 2012).

Change management as one of the contemporary diversity management practices is vital to practice being implemented by human resources to maintain a competitive advantage. According to Burnes, (1996a, 1996b) organisations that effectively manage change are better placed than their competitors. However, change management like change is a difficult term to describe Thus “change management” could be considered to have two different meanings. i.e.,

“...Making changes in a planned and systematic way and the response to changes which the organisation has no control over them” (Nickols, 2004p.1)

Therefore, in this sense to recognise organisational change has become a challenging and crucial responsibility of organisations (Pettigrew, Woodman, and Cameroon 2001). In the past, where organisations were more stable

and operated in predictable environments (Beckhard & Pritchard 1992) balance sheets, locations, or organisational structure to predict and control their destinies. Organisations of today face different challenges imposed on them by globalisations, immigration, or global warming as results they have been forced to establish and manage change to prosper or more importantly to survive (Kotter, 1996p 18). According to Kotter, change has enabled some organisations to adapt from a managerial perspective to acquiring a competitive edge with their competitors as well as provide an organisation with a stable future.

On the other hand, change management in some organisations have been less successful, leaving employees frustrated, scared, or with burnout (Kotter 1996 p 3). To substantiate he describes that the following have contributed to the downside of change management:

Negative Impact/Aspect of Change

- Allowing too much complacency in the organisation.
- Failure to create clear and powerful guidelines.
- Restricted vision in terms of future planning.
- Lack of communication in the organisation.
- Failure to deal with problems immediately as and when they arise.

Concentration on long term gains at the expense of short-term benefits.

- Acknowledging change victory sooner than it is achieved; A failure to firmly anchor changes in the corporate culture of the organization.

2.19.1) To solve the above issues, Kotter suggested the following:

- The management of change practices and strategies should be well implemented.
- All acquisitions must be planned to be in keeping with the expected outcomes, (Synergies).
- Re-engineering should occur in the shortest space of time for the change to be effective, be cost-effective, and aligned closely to the change.
- Downsizing should occur in a controlled and cost-saving manner.
- Quality programmes should be carefully selected so that the organisation will achieve the desired results.

2.20) Change Management and its implications

In the context of this research, the change is inevitable. Change is inherently involved in a very deeper sense and the implication ought to be highlighted. This means the incidence and consequences of change that may result from the process of diversity/workforce diversity management practice processes concerning the impact it may have on employee's performance and organisational productivity are unavoidable.

2.20.1) Types of Change Theories Associated with Implementing Workforce management Practices

Two fundamental changes usually occur with changes, and they are “operational and strategic” (Burnes, 2004, 2009c; Cole, 2004, 2005; Eguruze, 2016:28, 2017). The former is small or not too important or may be deemed routine (operational) (Pettigrew, 1991,1998), while the latter form of change(strategic) is usually long-range and require strategic planning or major and significant changes (Lynch, 2006). Strategic changes may require proactive long-range planning, while strategic planning or long-range planning maybe defined as “... *the proactive management of change in organisations to achieve clear strategic objectives*” (Lynch, 2006:753 and cited in Eguruze, 2016:28). Changes that may need to occur the following implementation of the researcher's framework/model may be deemed a strategic form of change. If so, it is important also to learn that change must be introduced gradually slowly, and/or incrementally, to avoid a breakdown in communication among the workforce (lynch, 2006, Eguruze, 2016).

It is also important to suggest that a strategic form of change such as changes in workforce diversity management practices within nursing homes may be an ongoing management situation, so it also needs to be gradual and incremental as such. On the other hand, there is another form of organisational change that may need to be introduced and implemented rather fast or suddenly or ‘radically’ (Lynch, 2006:753), such as the current (2.9 Researcher's Integrated Diversity/Workforce Diversity Management Practice Model for Nursing Homes in Middlesex-London (RI- DWDMP-NHML, see 2.9 above). It is important to learn positive lessons from the potentialities associated with the change in the context of this research.

2.20.2) Resistance to Change during the Implementation process of the Model.

It is also critical to note the significance of the need to be careful in managing change arose from the fact that change does come along with resistance, reactions, or disruptions, etc. whenever it occurs and whether the change is small or minor or large or strategic. This leads us to the phenomenon of resistance to change.

Resistance to change, as the name suggests the tendency for the workforce or followers to resist or oppose any form of change that may occur (i.e., exhibition of an emotional reaction or response (known as Sarah's Model, Folkman (2010, cited in Eguruze, 2016:28). According to Folkman's (2010, as cited in Eguruze, 2016:28). Sarah's Model constitutes three basic reactions or categories of reactions: Shock, Anger, Reaction, and Acceptance (Sara, for short). This is important for the management of nursing to note that in the process of

introducing and implementing any changes, as certain emotional reactions may occur, which is inevitable in the context of diversity/workforce diversity management practices within nursing homes in the Middlesex-London region.

Similarly, another critical aspect of changes that associate with the implementation of change is as follows: Lewin (1950) and Yuki (2020) and Kotter (1995), etc. Lewin (1951) introduced the three-phases model of change process relating to implementing change: phase 1 is the need to unfreeze the existing situation; phase 2 focuses on moving carefully to a balance of equilibrium, and phase 3 relates to the need to refreeze. This is a postimplementation of any change reaction, according to Lewin (1951, as also cited by Eguruze, 2016:29).

On the contrary, there is the Yuki (2010) two phases resistance model. Phase 1 argues the fact that people may be affected and the workforce within the Middlesex-London nursing homes may come to terms with changes that may occur, which may change or affect their lives, for good one way or another. Phase 1 of Lewin's model (1951) also means the present diverse/work diverse workforce might be encouraged/need to work in different ways never experienced before, if changes had to be made that may change the current "modus operandi", meaning policy changes in connection with decision-making processes, which may affect lives (Eguruze, 2016: 29). Whereas Phase 2 of Lewin's model (1951) depicts the need to explore new and innovative ways of doing things or be prepared to adapt to new ways of doing old things or even new ways that are entirely novel to what was the status quo or 'modus operandi', as illustrated by (Eguruze, 2016:29). So, lessons ought to be gathered from this. The third related model is Kotter's (1995) Model, which constituted 8 phases of change:

Phase 1 focuses on the need to creating urgency for the organization.

Phase 2 concentrated on the need to form a powerful coalition of like minds within the organisation or society.

Phase 3 relates to the idea of creating a clear simple vision, which is necessary and simple.

Phase 4 must be about how best the vision be effectively communicated to the followers, in this case, diverse workforce team.

Phase 5 is about the need to remove or avoid any obstacle that might be obstructive on the way.

Phase 6 is the reflections to creating short term wins to have a perception or psychological impact on the rest of the changes process to occur successfully.

Phase 7 is to ensure building the change successfully as possible.

Phase 8 is making the change stick.

As noted above, reasons for resisting change are numerous but oftentimes not clear cut or apparent. They may be summarized as follows: the belief or perception that change may be unnecessary, lack of trust of the people who propose it; fear of personal failures; scepticism/fear of information relating to the change process; the influence of the person or group that might have been negatively affected by the change process; the threat of values, ideas due to the possible radical changes in attitude, behaviour, and perceptions; the threat of litigation and the thought or fear of possible prosecution for unethical practices or noncompliance or potential breaches of the law, etc., whilst it is important to note that it is not an exhaustive list of concerns, which might be associated with resistance to change processes (Pettinger, 2003; Yuki, 2010, Burnes and Jackson, 2011; Eguruze, 2016:31, 2017). It should also be noted that organisational change inspired by organisational culture or corporate culture might be another critical factor for rising or perpetrating change (Eguruze, 2016, 2017), so also the need for effective communication is necessary to successfully implement change (Ibid). Again, management of nursing homes may draw important lessons from these processes and adapt accordingly in their context: for examples; change from attitudes such as discrimination, low wages, wages/salary gaps, bullying, harassment, racism, etc., which may be deemed unethical or unlawful (Equality Act,2010, as amended; UDHR, 1948; ICESCR,1996,2006).

2.20.3) Overcoming resistance relating to change and leadership role in this process.

Given that diverse workforce management within nursing homes in the Middlesex-London region may resist these challenges: discrimination, low wages, wages/salary gaps, bullying, harassment, racism, it is important to learn how to overcome such resistance. That is where the following theories may become critical with the application of change. To this several scholars have offered further suggestions. These include amongst others the followings:

- i) Effective leadership-** good leadership is important to this process. Some opined an “effective leadership is critical to a change management” (Eguruze, 2016:33; Schein, 2010; Peterson, 2011). By leadership, it is referred to as “getting things done through people”; so, in this sense involving a diverse workforce in the management practices process, not isolating them, and is crucial (Eguruze, 2016:33, 2017). Others suggested being aware of the cultural change process is vital (Brown, 1998), whereas, according to Hills and Jones, 1998, 2009) strategic leadership is also critical: which is viewed as the ability to articulate a strategic vision for an organisation, and to motivate others to adapt or assimilate into the vision, as cited in Eguruze, 2016:33). Hills and Jones identified 5 factors of good or effective leadership; i) vision; ii) eloquency/consistency; iii) being well informed; iv) willingness to delegate and empower; and v) effective utilisation of power (cited in Eguruze, 2016:33).
- ii) Management styles-** To this, Blake and Mouton(1964) identify five crucial aspects of leadership style to be noted: i)country-club leadership that offers higher concern for people than for productivity;

ii) team-leadership offers high priority equally for people as well as productivity; iii) middle-of-the-road-style also gives equal concern for both people and productivity; iv) task-leader offers higher concern for productivity than it is for people; v) impoverished-leader offers low priority equally for both people and productivity and so engages in the act of indecisiveness which in turn could lead to a management dilemma in situations that might require effective leadership. The lesson for nursing homes management is to choose whichever management style they deem appropriate or best applicable to their change management circumstances, as also illustrated (Eguruze, 2016:34)

iii) Effective Communication- having established good leadership, it is important to be able to communicate the vision effectively. The ability to communicate with all the stakeholders is crucial. According to Cole, (2004, 2005), communicating openly enhances the changes that may occur, and impacts would be critical and inevitable in this process of the change process. This would be important for the welfare and wellbeing of all the stakeholders. To this, Cole(2004, 2005) suggested a possible process to follow to achieve that communication goal: i) using formal channels; ii) committee structure, authority levels, communication policies/procedures; iii) disciplinary issues; iv) informal ways although may be resisted or unacceptable but useful and critical e.g. grapevines; v) eliminate barriers of communication such as the bias or subjectivity elements of the individual, culture, and values, positions, or status differences, lack of trust, an overload of information, verbal contradictions, etc., as also illustrated by (Eguruze, 2016:32). Other aspects of effective communication that may be necessary include the ability to listen, write, speak, lead, negotiate, manage a team, problem solving, recognising verbal and non-verbal aspects, etc.

2.21) Theories on Employee Performance

Performance is a multi-dimensional and dynamic concept, often composed of behavioural and outcome aspects. (McMahon, 2010; Simmons, 2008) critiqued along with three perspectives: the individual, situational, and a performance regulatory perspective. What an individual does in the work situation that is relevant to organisational goals makes up the behavioural aspect of performance and most often only actions that can be measured, are considered to constitute performance (Pavlov & Bourne, 2005). The outcome aspect is the consequence or result of the individual's behaviour as outcomes depend on other factors, not just behaviour.

Despite the general agreement that the behavioural and the outcome aspect of performance must be differentiated, authors do not entirely agree about which of these two aspects should be labelled performance, making its measurement more complex as not all activities contribute to the technical core of activities which are the main activities needed to accomplish a given task (Paul & Browne, 2005). Performance is also a dynamic process because of its instability, which may result from its learning processes, long-term and temporary changes

to performance. Studies showed that performance might change with time spent in a job (Avolio, Waldman, McMahon, 2010; Simmons, 2008). There is short-term variability in performance, which is due to changes in an individual's psycho-physiological state, or because of long working hours.

As already stated, earlier researchers have adopted various perspectives for studying performance. The individual differences perspective focuses on performance differences between individuals and seeks to identify better performing individuals as performance can be linked to motivation or personality. According to Paul & Browne, 2005, performance is a function of three determinants. A declarative knowledge about facts, goals is assumed to be a function of a person's abilities, education, and training. The situational perspective refers to factors in individuals' environment but incorporates specific motivational approaches aimed at enhancing performance or sometimes by simply establishing perceptions of fairness and equity (Pavlov & Bourne, 2005). In a workplace environment workplace factor and their link to individual performance could be differentiated along with two major approaches:

- 1) Those that focus on a situational factor to foster performance and
- 2) Those that emphasize situational factors that obstruct performance.

According to the first category, job design specifies workplace factors that enhance performance. Work systems that are made up of social and technical subsystems suggest that performance improvement can only occur following the optimisation of both subsystems (Pavlov & Bourne, 2005). Moreover, Meta-analytic findings suggest that there is a positive link between job characteristic and job performance (Eddy, 1998) and the fact that people who show high performance get better jobs. The second category focuses on factors that have detrimental effects on performance. A recent meta-analysis found a negative relationship between role ambiguity and performance in managerial and professional milieus arising from a result of role conflict characterised by stressors that hinder performance (Pitt & Tucker, 2008). Other situational constraints that indirectly affect performance can be additional regulation capacity over and above the one needed to accomplish the task (Niven, 2002). The regulation perspective addresses core questions on the performance process or what happens when someone is performing. Rodney & Mohamed (2010) recommended a broad method to performance regulation, in which he combined the action theory approach as one of five perspectives leaving out the other four components of performance regulation which are: energetic regulation, emotional regulation, vitality regulation, and self-image regulation. The process regulation perspective connects to precise performance improvement interventions. The most important interventions are goal setting (Rodney & Mohamed, 2010) and feedback interventions (Pitt & Tucker, 2008). The basic idea of goal setting as a performance improvement intervention is that setting goals results in better performance than 'no' or 'do your-best' goals (Pavlov & Bourne, 2005). The

goal-setting theory assumes that goals affect performance via four mediating mechanisms: effort, persistence, direction, and task strategies. The benefits of goal setting on performance are in many empirical studies (Pavlov & Bourne, 2005; Pitt & Tucker, 2008). Meta-analyses showed that goal setting belongs to one of the most powerful work-related intervention programmes. The performance regulation perspective suggests that an improvement of the action process itself improves performance. As a result, individuals should be encouraged to set long-term goals and to engage in appropriate planning, feedback-seeking, and feedback processing (Rodney & Mohamed, 2010). Therefore, training interventions can be useful in attaining such changes.

A different method of performance regulation is the behaviour adjustment perspective. Based on reinforcement theory (Niven, 2002), this approach is not primarily interested in the processes within the individual which control performance but in regulative interventions from outside the individual, particularly positive reinforcement. Such reinforcements can include financial interventions, non-financial interventions such as performance feedback, social rewards such as attention and recognition, or a combination of all these types of reinforcements. Meta-analytic findings suggest that such behaviour modification interventions have a positive effect on task performance, both in the manufacturing and in the service sector (Pitt & Tucker, 2008). Researchers often mix two or more approaches when explaining performance. For example, there is a combination between the individual differences and the situational perspective (Pitt & Tucker, 2008; Rodney & Mohamed, 2010). The job characteristic model assumes that a mixture of situational factors and individual differences factors is vital for individual performance (Rodney & Mohamed, 2010). Similarly, Waldman (1994) suggested a model of performance that combines the individual differences perspective with the situational perspective. This author thinks that both personal factors (i.e., individual difference variables) and system factors (i.e., situational variables) influence job performance and even goes further to assume that system factors moderate the effects of the personal factor.

2.22) Benefits for diversity

When people get comfortable at work, they perform better. With globalisation it is difficult to find organisations with employees from similar backgrounds, cultures, or ethnicities. As a result of differences, people might be fearful of others and might become unproductive. This could mean that diversity is bad for untrue business. When businesses focus on diversity their chances of success are high.

According to Buckingham, (2012), there is increased adaptability resulting from a pool of personnel from divergent backgrounds. Employing from a diverse population widens the scope of eligibility for people to hire employees because a culturally stable employee can easily adapt to different situations. When employers recognise and accommodate differences there is a sense of harmony which instils a sense of inclusion and belonging. Moreover, work practices are created that will be inclusive of all cultures and no one is left out. This

in turn results in increased productivity, creativity as well as problem-solving among employees (McLauren, 2012).

A diverse workforce encourages effective execution of plans as it allows employers to assign different goals to different employees with a specific set of skills which helps to create a work plan that optimises productivity, distribution of work and allows for goal achievement (Kapoor, 2011).

Some scholars believe that teams from divergent backgrounds tend to have less conflict as they bring together a variety of skills that accent each other. Individuals have a unique way of learning, thinking, and processing, and as a result, a group composed of different minds may have several solutions to a problem. Such teams tend to see things from different angles and can spot errors that arise quicker (Le, 2008). Organisations with diverse staff have a lower turnover rate and are inclined to produce many creative techniques as opposed to their competitors. An unhealthy work atmosphere is often the cause of high conflict levels in companies, so people need to feel safe and secured. On the other hand, teams with the same backgrounds tend to have many internal issues from pride and competitiveness amongst one another that may reduce productivity processes due to unmet decisions by the group.

2.23) Summary

As noted above, the review of extant literature was on diversity and workforce diversity management practices as they impacted employees' performance. It also reviewed inclusion and change management in the context of the implementation of change that might have followed the introduction of a new integrated conceptual framework model for nursing homes in the UK, using care homes in the Middlesex-London region as a case study.

The researcher noted that the essence of learning diversity was predicated upon valuing differences amongst people. It learns that it would be a substantial value to the nursing home care management, which is an integral part of the health and social care and the NHS system in the country. According to the UK's Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development (CIPD, 2006:1; 2017), Diversity is "valuing everyone as individuals - as employees, customers, and clients" and this view tends to imply inclusivity. Besides, the review compared the version of the (Healthcare Health & Social care version, 2020). For this research, the definition of the NHS/the Health and Social Care definition is adopted. The justification for this narrower definition is that, from a macroeconomics perspective, this research concerns an industry that is a health and social care industry in this context, being only a unit or branch of the entire UK's economy (Companies' House, 2020).

The review briefly gave an outline of the changing nature of the care sector in terms of the demographic component given the rise among people of colour or ethnic minority and therefore the need to understand multicultural approach.

The thesis offered some theories of diversity. Although there have been previous studies and/or efforts as highlighted above (Wentling 2004: 166; Griggs (1995) and (Kossek and Lobel, (1996) (CIPD, 2006:1); Act (Equality Act 2010, as amended), based on perceptions (which is seen as “process by which people select, organize and interpret information to form a meaningful picture of the world”, or as they deem fit or on their terms (Kotler et al., 2005:917; Kotler, 2012, 2014) and see also Eguruz, 2017:1). To this end, diversity as a theory has been deployed on a piecemeal basis and so it has not been universally accepted. This explains the dearth of literature and/or insight on the subject and as a result, makes this study more necessary. Table 2.2 Summarised/highlighted the relevant theories linking the meaning of diversity to their origins and consequences and influences/authorities across the world, Contrasting diversity and equality.

The researcher also learned about the concept of equality. From the perspective of the NHS and/or Health and Social Care industry workplace context, equality is not about treating everyone the same, which is very impractical. People are different. What counts in understanding equality - is how people of differences may need to live peacefully and amicably together? So, equality primarily is about ensuring that access to opportunities is available to all by taking account of people's differing needs and capabilities. The laws governing equality and diversity phenomena in the UK was: The Equality Act 2010 (as amended); it works very closely with the other instruments such as The Human Rights Act, 1988 and The Commission of Equality and Human Rights (EHRC)

The review provided table 2.3, in the form of a summary of equality and diversity management legal instruments/ impact across the world as they are different; the purpose was to better understand the benchmark or best practices across the world. Countries such as the UK, SA, EU, Ireland, China, and India, and including The United Nations, were benchmarked, in terms of their perspective on equality and diversity.

The meaning of the concept of Workforce/Employee was also provided; while drawing lessons from the context of diversity management perspective, the workforce comprises people who are different and share different attitudes, needs, desires, values, and work behaviours (Deluca and McDowell, 1992; Morrison, 1992; Rosen and Lovelace, 1991). Although it may also include the unemployed in another context, as well as include those working for either a single organisation or industrial sector or a wider geographical area, city, state or even a country, or the world (Seager, 2008). Scholars' definition is that an employee is someone who works for remuneration or gets paid for the work or services he or she renders to an employer in the form of compensation, which may be wages or salaries (Dakin and Armstrong, 1989:187-94); Armstrong, 2006, 2012; CIPD, 2006, 2017,2018). However, for tax purposes, But the Government definition is that “*an employee is someone who works under an employment contract*” (Gov.UK, 2020). While it is equally vital to look after employee welfare and wellbeing (Keynes, 1935, 1936; Smith, 1776; Karl, 1887; Ricardo, 1859).

The review touched on exploring/acknowledging the extent to which previous studies on Diversity and Equality. Some scholars have examined companies' performances in great depth and have noted that there are financial improvements to be gained such as return on investment, revenue, costs, and profits through effective utilisation of diverse/workforce diversity management practices (Jayne & Dipboye, 2004; Seager, 2008; Armstrong, 2010). Others argued that organisations frequently protect such hard data because it is potentially commercially sensitive (Monks; Armstrong, 2010). Scores of benefits for learning diversity and equality were provided improved and positive performances are highly contextualised but useful and relevant (Armstrong, 2010; Jayne & Dipboye, 2004; Kochan et al., 2003). Previously research has tended to be context-specific (e.g., Jackson & Joshi, 2004; Kochan et al., 2003). Some focused on how the diversity and equality movement shifted from initial thoughts of "*equal opportunity*" into legislative instruments (Wilson, 1996; Armstrong, 2010). Others saw it as a strategic business priority for improving performance (Carnevale & Stone, 1994; European Commission, 2005; Armstrong, 2010), while other scholars view it as a just and fair way to utilise business resources despite little tangible evidence showing that equal opportunity initiatives are an appropriate use of resources (Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development (CIPD), 2006; Jayne & Dipboye, 2004, in Armstrong, 2010:3). Currently, managing diversity is enjoying a high profile in the organisational debate, partly due to changes in workforce demographics, increased globalization.

It also touched on the consequences of failure in effectively understanding or deploying diversity and equality: discrimination, harassment, racism, xenophobia, bias, low wages (slave labour; working poor); favouritism, bullying, culture clash, stereotypical behaviours; etc.

Having noticed the gap in knowledge and the dangers and consequences and implications of not employing equality and diversity and the review provided a conceptual framework/model in Figure 1 entitled - Researcher's Integrated Diversity/Workforce Diversity Management Practice Model for Nursing Homes in Middlesex-London (RI- DWDMP-NHML). It focused on the variables such as diversity in age and employee performance, gender and employee performance, ethnicity and employee performance, and management practice variables such as motivational schemes and performance, flexible working and employee performance, cultural training, enhanced performances, etc.... How these variables may have affected performance?

Thereafter, the challenges and processes of inevitable changes that may occur: the concept of change management was explored; including implementing change, leadership styles to cope with changes, theories of change management, resistance to change, management/leadership styles to cope with change, inclusion, the business case for diversity, etc. were covered.

Therefore, it is inevitable that diversity and equality practices are regarded as the centre focus of all health and social operations as it is at the bigger level, the NHS. As with the NHS, it is also important that the private health and social care sector also adopt a marketing-oriented approach, which treats or perceives customers as the heart of care, and recognise that their patients, not just their employees, are of diverse background: social, economic, cultural, ethnicity, age, and as such their needs are also widely diverse as possible. So, putting diversity and equality principles and practices in place means adapting the marketing orientation approach into practice, and which means everything is done to ensure every patient and employees' needs are met with satisfaction as much as possible. Doing the best to attain such goals and objectives would help service delivery achieve equality in terms of access and fairness provision, meaning achieving all of these without discriminating or fear or favour of one employee over another. Everyone had to be treated fairly.

This is important because patients have individual needs and circumstances and are different in terms of disability, illness, age, fitness, as well as the food they would want to eat, exercising, learning of new skills, special transportation needs, recreational needs, amount of support every patient might require, etc. may differ. It is important to understand that being under the health and social care of nursing homes, as in the NHS, commands huge responsibilities and duties. Patients must be kept safely and kept well – away from any form of harm or barriers.

So, respecting, recognising, and practising diversity and equality work practices/principles – basically means being open, fair, accessible, and supportive, and enabling nursing homes (health and social care) practice settings or provision means it is an attempt to process of avoiding or reducing or preventing the risk of discrimination, which is unlawful in the UK (Equality Act, 2010, as amended). It is also important to remark that – discrimination may be subtle, silent (indirect), open or obvious (direct) all of which are equally unacceptable and is to be spotted and eliminated, avoided, and prevented as much as possible. That is the ideal setting in the context of the issues being researched in this thesis. Ultimately the benefits for adopting diversity management practices may include an increase in employee performance, profitability, sales-turnover, lower employee turnover and higher retention rates, reduction in the phenomenon of burnout, etc.

As the researcher concludes chapter two of the thesis, which is the literature review, the next section to embark on will be the research methodology, which is chapter three.

CHAPTER THREE

3) RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1) Introduction

Research according to Saunders & Lewis (2014:38) is "...a process of creating new knowledge, resulting in a logical consequence of the emergence of a question yet to be answered or the re-examination of an already existing concept either to gain more understanding or challenge the existing status quo. The choice of the method used in answering a research question depends on a variety of reasons and purpose of the studies (Flick 2009:14). Although qualitative research has gained a lot of popularity lately, the researcher will not just limit herself to qualitative research approaches but will also use quantitative approaches within the same study to acquire clear, in-depth, reliable, and valid knowledge that will be beneficial to the field of health and social care.

This section of the studies explored various approaches to emphasise on the methodological stance. The researcher started by presenting the research methods, research design, research paradigms, methodology. Then she proceeded to data collection methods, data analysis and synthesis, ethical consideration, issues of trustworthiness, limitations of the study and then finally summary of the chapter.

3.2) Research Paradigms

The initial research considerations may start with three main research paradigms which include: -

- The reality or nature of the research being conducted (ontology).
- The truth about the research (epistemology)
- Research methodology is the plan on how to resolve the research problem which entails the researchers approach to ensure validity, reliability. RM addresses the aim/objectives and offers a plan on how the studies will be tackled.

Research paradigms are such issues as personal or contextual factors such as personal beliefs, values, interests, socio-economic, cultural backgrounds, etc. that are likely to influence how you choose to conduct your research, gather data, analyse, and interpret the outcome of the study (Bryman and Bell, 2007:24; Bryman, 1988a:4). That is why, some scholars argued "a sound understanding of research decisions and how they are deployed (Eguruze, 2016, 2017) is critical (Mills, 1972; Facault,1972, cited in Eguruze, 2016, 2017). Although there may be more, the main research paradigms to be considered here may include ontology, epistemology, research methodology. Finally, the methods are the best ways to gather data for the study, which can be focused groups, questionnaires, observations, surveys, interview.

3.2.1) Ontology

The ontology of research enables the researcher to understand from the onset, the nature of the phenomenon being investigated. Ontology is usually the beginning of the research with philosophies which can either be

realism (objective) or relativism (Blaike, 2000). Realism is the direct opposite of relativism. While realists believe that only one truth exists which can be investigated objectively, relativists believe in multiple versions of reality and hold the view that reality depends on experiences (Robson, 2002 and Trau, 2013). The overriding belief of the realists is that nature and social sciences can co-exist and can function side by side. It implies that the categories created by scientists refer to real objects in the natural or social world. Realism can be direct or critical. Direct realism can be considered a naïve realism where the world is perceived through human senses. Critical realists think that images and sensation can be deceptive and do not represent the world as it really is (Saunders et al, 2012)

3.2.2) Epistemology

Ontology believes will detect epistemology. Through the epistemological process, new knowledge could be developed or discovered. This means that once the researcher resolves this ontological question, new knowledge is being formed (Guba,1990). That is why scholars argue, “epistemology focuses on the process of knowledge gathering and the kind of relationship the researcher intends to develop with the study (Bryman and Bell, 2007:719).

3.2.3) The methodology

This is the process in which the researcher goes about investigating that reality. The methodology is the logical systematic approach adopted to find the reality (Creswell, 2003; 2007; Saunders et al., 2003; 2012).

That is how the research will find the answers to the problem the set out to examine. In the context of this research, a key question was ...From the researcher’s experience, and observation, diversity could be seen more in frontline roles compared to senior roles despite research on how beneficial diversity is to organisations. As a result of the researcher’s observation, she set out to explore truth using care homes in the Middlesex London. The researcher made a lot of considerations. Firstly, would the philosophical ontology be relativism or realism? How would she relate with the study they were carrying out? Would she want to take an outside view (Objective) or would she want to get involved in the studies while carrying out the research (epistemology). Then, was there a possibility to obtain the truth from interviewing staff in nursing homes or distributing questionnaires, using observations or focus group discussion (methods). Also note that within epistemology, assumptions are about the essence of “knowledge” that presents how the researcher understands social reality, (Burrell and Morgan,1979; Robson, 2002) and what attitudes they hold to view what they are studying (Hussy and Hussy, 1979).

Therefore, to be logical in any studies, ontology dictates epistemology which would then dictate the methodological stance and finally the methods used to explore the phenomenon. For these studies the research methodology will be carefully dissected as the researcher progressed.

3.2.4) Other research Paradigms

3.2.4.1) Axiology

Axiology represents the personal values or beliefs that the researcher holds (Oxford Dictionary, 2015). The point about beliefs is that every researcher does have some degree of personal values or beliefs that may unavoidably have some influence on the conduct of any specific piece of research (Baranowski, 2011). Axiology is ethical bias or value systems embedded within the researcher's personality that have some influence on the way research is undertaken and are often impossible to eliminate although can be limited (Baranoski, 2011). Note that interpretivist scholars argue that it is almost impossible to conduct research free of influence from the researcher's axiology (Saunders et al, 2012). This supports the assumption that no research is free of bias element. The positivists believe that researchers must perform their research in an atmosphere devoid of value interference to have a research outcome that is valid, objective, or neutral (Creswell, 2003; 2007; Saunders et al., 2003; 2012).

3.3) Methodology

3.3.1) Methodological Approaches

This section discusses various methodological approaches of positivism (quantitative philosophy, using deductive approach). interpretivism (qualitative philosophy, using inductive approach), mixed-method research, the multiple-research methods, and mono-research methods (Ghauri and Gronhaug, 2005).

3.3.2) Positivism

Advocates of positivism are strictly quantitative researchers with the view that reality can be quantified. The overriding positivists' belief is that valid knowledge is only obtained through the process of careful, direct observation, measuring, and recording of the outcomes; somehow in a controlled environment or process for the outcome to be valid (Creswell, 2003; 2007; Saunders et al., 2003; 2012).

3.3.2.1) Deductive Approach

A deductive approach is suitable when a large body of well-established literature on the research topic is available (Burrell and Morgan, 1979; Gauri and Gronhaug, 2005). In the context of this research, it is thought that there is a substantial amount of reliable literature on diversity/diversity management practices as well as the employee and many theories have already been developed. Hence, a 'true' or 'false' type of question is usually deduced from the exploration of research questions and related theories (Cresswell, 1994, 2003; Gauri and Gronhaug, 2005). Moreover, concerning a deductive approach, Robson (1993; 2002; 2011) argued researchers would likely involve a progression through five stages, which comprise of: -

- deducing a hypothesis,

- expressing the hypothesis,
- suggesting linkages between two variables,
- testing the operational hypotheses and
- subsequent examination of the outcome.

Further, researchers can modify the hypothesis based on the results, if and where required (Creswell, 2003; 2007; Saunders et al., 2003; 2012). Thus, this approach helps the researchers to explain the causal relationships between the variables as well as to develop the hypothesis. The deductive approach is usually best for quantitative data collection along with a highly structured methodology to allow testing of the hypothesis. Although in the context of this research there was no use of hypotheses, this is because research questions were used instead.

As a result, the research approach will be deductive as they will use questionnaires to obtain the data for the study.

3.3.3) *Interpretivism*

Interpretivists are qualitative researchers who think reality cannot be investigated in isolation of its context. Two researchers may not always agree on the same thing. What holds for an individual may not necessarily hold the same or true for another individual. Just as people see things differently, so are their interpretations of things are different. That is how those who believe in interpretivism see the social world. To the interpretivists, the social world is being presented or perceived and then interpreted differently by people who are carrying on with their lives.

So, what diversity management practices today may no longer be the same in the future. Perhaps it might have been different in the past. Within the context of the interpretivism philosophy, an inductive approach is commonly utilized to build or formulate a theory based on data collected (Saunders et al., 2003, 2012; Creswell, 2003; 2007).

3.3.3.1) *Inductive Approach*

The inductive approach is frequently used by researchers who attempt to build a theory based on the data collected. In other words, the researcher here tries to explain a social reality from personal observations and subjective views (Robson,2002;2007;2011; Saunders et al., 2003; 2012). Induction emphasizes the insight into how individuals interpret their social world and the meaning they attach to events. Therefore, an inductive approach was particularly considered with the context in which certain events are taking place and may therefore discover different cause and effect links. Following an inductive approach, qualitative methods and small

samples are commonly used. Besides, the research process starts with data, goes from observations to findings, and ends up at theory building. Hence, the theory generating process is composed of using the personal views and subjective judgments of researchers (Bryman and Bell, 2003; Ghauri and Gronhaug, 2005). In this study the researcher used questionnaires as a data collection tool.

3.3.4) Mixed-Method Research

Mixed-methods are world view or several world’s views, as it allows the application of more than one single method in a study (Monlina-Azorin and Cameron, 2010; Plano-Clark et al., 2007). The justification for mixed-method research was borne out of the fact that mixed-method enables the researcher to be more: -

“...flexible, integrative, holistic, and rigorous in their investigative techniques as they seek to answer a range of complex research questions that come forth”.

Leech and Onwuegbuzie, (2010:66) in their guidelines for conducting and reporting mixed research in the field of counselling and beyond as cited in Eguruze,2016:62), who also applied mixed-method research in his recent study on tackling poverty. The researcher used a mixed method for different parts of the research, here mixed methods where simultaneously applied during the data collection and analysis phase as both quantitative and qualitative paradigms are adopted for the (Eguruze, 2016:66; Cameron, 2010; Bryman and Bell, 2011; Monlina-Azorin and Cameron, 2010).

Collecting primary data would help the researcher respond to the key research question: What is the impact of diversity and workforce diversity management practices on the employee performance in nursing homes in the UK: *A Case Study of Care Homes in Middlesex-London*. A qualitative approach designed was used to collect data in the form of words, recording, texts, while the quantitative data is collected in the form of numbers or figures (Eguruze, 2016:66). Although mixed methods are more complicated to use a combination of these in one study enables a better insight and synergic outcome, as they complement and reinforce each other (Saunders et al., 2012; Greenberg, 2007

Table 3. 1 Quantitative and Qualitative Approaches to research Adapted from Mariott, (2008:13) and Bryman and Bell, 2003:302)

Quantitative	Qualitative
Theory testing	Theory emergent
Structured	Unstructured
Hard, reliable	Deep rich data
Researcher’s remote	Researcher close
Researcher’s view	Respondent’s view

How many?	How much?
Macro	Micro
Measure in numerical variables	Symbol phrases, patterns
Relates to Numbers, e.g., Counts in value Nos	Words or text e.g., Names or codes
Static	Process
Generalization	Contextual compare
Artificial setting	Natural setting
Objective view	Subjective view
Positive paradigm	Interpretivism
Deductive approach	Inductive approach

Mixed-methods Research Model

3.3.5) Dominant approach

Despite all these divisions, there is still the dominant approach. It should be noted that mixed-method research is neither a replacement nor an alternative to quantitative or qualitative strategies. Irrespective of these differences, both quantitative and qualitative research methods are still useful research instruments in their rights in both business and management studies, particularly in organisational strategy formulations. Studies also found that between these two research methods, the use of a quantitative research method is still predominant in both management studies and organizational behavioural studies (Greenberg, 2007). Despite the dominance of quantitative and qualitative research methods, it appears there is a growing interest in using mixed-method research as well as multi-disciplinary influences (Easterby-Smith et al., 2008).

3.3.6) Mono Research Method

Unlike the mixed-method research method, the mono research-method study is the use of only one type of method involving one quantitative study that provides numerical data or one qualitative study providing a textual data form. Despite calls for the combined use of quantitative and qualitative research in management and organisational studies, there is comparatively less use of the mixed-method research in business and management studies (Monilla-Azorin, 2010).

3.4) Research Design

The research design refers to the entire research process. It represents the overall research outline or framework that links every part of the research process together thereby giving the research process some form of logical and coherent picture. According to Robson

(1993;2002; 2011:70-71): -

“... a design is concerned with turning research questions into projects” or deals primarily with the aims, purposes, intentions, and plans within the practical constraints of location, time, money, and availability of staff”.

This enables the researcher to see the research process more clearly: commencing with identification of the research problem (or statement of the research problem), followed by data collection and data analysis, reporting (discussion and interpreting), and then finally the conclusion and recommendations. However, as Apere (2004:41) suggested a research design *“is the programme that guides the investigator in the process of collecting, analysing, and interpreting observation”*. It is a logical model of proof that allows the researcher to draw inferences concerning causal relationships among the variables under investigation.

3.4.1 Experimental Research Design

An experimental design is normally linked to the positivism paradigm and quantitative methods. Experimental research or experimentation is the most scientifically sophisticated research method. The main purpose of experimentation is to derive verified functional relationships among phenomena under controlled conditions, that is, to identify the conditions underlying the occurrence of a given phenomenon (Saunders et al, (2012)

3.4.1.1 Advantages of Experimental Design

According to Creswell, (2007) and Saunders et al., (2012), the experimental research advantages could be summarised as follows: -

It allows the researcher to maintain control over the variables that are linked to the problem of the research; It enables the researcher to design research, which allows the researcher to know exactly the conditions under which the research is being carried out; and it also has greater flexibility/reliability than other forms of research such as descriptive research. This means that could be applied where other forms are unable to be utilised.

3.4.1.2) Disadvantages of Experimental Research Design

Similarly, according to many scholars (Apere, 2004; Creswell, 2003; 2007; Saunders et al., 2003; 2012), the disadvantages could be summarised as follows: It is most effective on a short-term basis. In other words, it is a short-term research facility due to the changing possibilities of the working conditions that may be beyond the control of the researcher. It is not applicable and may not work well under certain locations or environmental settings. It can only be experimented on non-humans due to health and safety and general well-being factors.

3.5) Case Study Research Design

A case study is a detailed exploration of an event or related events. Yin (2014) defines a case study as an empirical inquiry that examines a current phenomenon in a real-life context, especially where the boundaries between the aspect and the context are not obvious. According to Yin a case study strategy should be applied when the researcher deliberately wants to study a phenomenon in a particular context. A case study strategy was particularly suitable for these studies because the research was within the context of care homes in a particular region in London with the aim of studying the impact of diversity on performance. According to Yin (2014) and Stake (2000) a case study can employ the best of both qualitative and quantitative methods and not to be confused with qualitative research. Yin, 2014 further posits that a case study is a comprehensive strategy that deals with situations with more variables of interest than data points and rely on multiple sources of evidence with data needing to meet in a triangulation fashion. According to Yin, three types of case studies exist which depends on the type of research question being investigated. 'What' are exploratory, 'how' and 'why' questions explanatory and a descriptive study relying on conveying background information and an accurate description of the case in question. As for Yin's typologies this study can be considered an exploratory case study because it attempts to answer what questions as posed by the studies.

Considering the issue of generalisation, the purpose of case study according to Yin argues is for analytical generalisation to expand theory. However, Stake (1995) states that researchers make naturalistic generalisations which are different from deductive generalisations based on statistical analysis. Gomm et al on the other hand argue that boundary of cases should be clarified to make appropriate generalisation. These scholars further explained that the selection of cases should be carefully carried out depending on whether the researcher hopes to claim that the cases investigated are typical (or atypical) in relevant aspects. In this study, using Gomm et al (2000) and Yin's 2014 argument about generalisations, I believe that results can provide grounds for generalisation about the case studies to other similar cases as well as offer analytical basis for theory expansion.

3.5.1) Descriptive Research Design (*descriptive study*)

Descriptive research design (descriptive study) is where the study aims to generate new facts (Aperre, 2004). The descriptive designs are widely used in social and management sciences because of the complex relationships that exist between variables, which are not usually subject to manipulation.

Descriptive research design tends to relate to the question - what is going on in the real world? (Aperre, 2004;41; Robson, 2002, 2007). In the context of this research, what is the impact of diversity and diversity management practices on employee performance in nursing homes within the Middlesex area? Alternatively, how does diversity and diversity management practices impact employee performance in nursing homes in London Middlesex? Descriptive researchers believe that by accurately describing the content or substance of a real social

world problem, and by implication, the theme of the research problem (statement of the problem), the problem can then be resolved or tackled relatively more accurately with ease. In other words, the more accurately the problem is diagnosed, the more likely the problem could be tackled. The main forms of descriptive research are survey and longitudinal (historical) research designs. Their main difference is the fact of time. While historical or longitudinal research is concerned with the past, survey research is about the present time. A survey can also be distinguished from experimental research. These are discussed below.

There are two main types of descriptive research design: cross-sectional and longitudinal designs. The cross-sectional design is further divided into either field study or sample survey, and longitudinal designs.

The survey relies on a sample of elements from the population of interest, which are measured at a single point in time (Robson, 2002, 2007). The field survey, as a kind of cross-sectional survey, is a detailed analysis of a selected number of cases. It is a small sample approach that is particularly useful when examining the interrelationships among some variables. The sample survey, on the other hand, is a large cross-sectional survey so that the numbers are representative of the population of interest. Surveys are treated in detail below.

3.5.2) Survey Research Design

“...Survey research is a form of descriptive research that is aimed at collecting large and small samples from the population to examine the distribution of incidence and interaction of sociological and psychological variables” (Apere: 2004:30; Robson, 2002).

Surveys can be either cross-sectional or longitudinal. Surveys allow comparisons to be made. Surveys also rely on samples taken from the population under study, which are measured at a point in time.

3.5.2.1) Advantages of Survey Research Design

The survey research (or sample survey) is more representative and therefore more economical: the mass population will be too expensive to study. A study of representative samples will permit inferences from and generalisations to be made to populations. It allows accurate assessment of the characteristics of the entire population - this leads to cost and time savings. It also attempts to determine the incidence, distribution, and interactions of variables such as people's perceptions, values, opinions, beliefs, attitudes, motivation, and behaviour.

It helps to identify current needs and wants, or conditions and compares present needs and wants for various categories of people for making better policy-decision making. It provides data for in-depth discussion and interpretation of the implications and inter-relationships of variables. It also allows investigation of the phenomena to take place in natural settings.

3.5.2.2) Disadvantages of Survey Research Design

Surveys are not appropriate for testing specific hypotheses as they concentrate on explaining inter-relationships amongst phenomena. In this way, in the context of this research, it is more realistic to use a survey (descriptive) rather than an experimental design.

3.5.3) Longitudinal Research Design

This is a type of sampling method,

“...where a sample of observations are collected over a specific period or several periods” (Pass et al, 1991: 541).

For example, in the context of this research embracing a wide range of data on all frontline staff of employees of Middlesex nursing homes with a wide variety of demographic characteristics and with different perceptions and attitudes towards the concept of diversity and diversity management and to select the diversity aspects that will impact on employee performance in nursing homes which will act as a guide to all stakeholders involved in diversity management. The main feature of the longitudinal design is its use or reliance on panel data. By definition, a panel is simply a fixed sample of individuals or some other entities from who repeated measurements are taken. There are two distinct kinds of panels - panels in which the same measurement is taken in each measurement period (omnibus panel).

The main feature of the longitudinal analysis is that it involves continuous or intermittent observations made over time, recording data to describe changes that take place within a given environment (Creswell, 2003; Apere, 2004; Saunders et al., 2003; 2012).

3.5.3.1) Advantages Longitudinal Research Design

Despite the inherent shortfalls in the descriptive design by not being able to manipulate the independent variables, it has certain advantages:

Longitudinal studies can take many years whereas experimental design does not. It is also expensive. Longitudinal studies are rich in validity but are not dependable in the sense that you cannot repeat it exactly or attribute findings to all the population.

The benefits are that it is a rich, in-depth study of a group or individuals over time and in a natural environment. Descriptive studies are also – generally more broadly representative of a larger target population than are the findings from experimental studies. It is also better to use a descriptive design where there is a considerable time

lag between the application of the independent variable and the appearance of a response in the dependent variable (Cresswell, 2003; Apere, 2004: 50-53; Saunders et al., 2003; 2012)

3.5.3.2) Disadvantages of longitudinal research design

The approach cannot establish causal relationships with the same degree of confidence, as can be the experimental approach. The approach is not particularly useful in the development of theories, ideas, and principles as it is not suited to test out a newly developed product, programme, or procedure.

A descriptive design might use an interview or questionnaire with its associated weaknesses (Cresswell, 2003; Apere: 2004: 50-53; Saunders et al., 2003; 2012).

3.5.4) Cross-Sectional Research Design

A cross-sectional survey is a type of sampling method, “where sample observations are collected at a particular point in time” (Pass et al., 1991: 541). In this context of this study, engaging all categories of employees from all backgrounds within a wide range of demographic characteristics and with different perceptions and attitudes towards approaches to work within a workplace environment such as a nursing home or care home, is fundamentally critical and useful in a cross-sectional study context.

A cross-sectional survey can be further divided into field surveys and sample surveys. Robson (1993;2002;2007;2011; Apere, 2004) made the distinction very clearly. A sample survey is a large cross-sectional survey, and it is more representative of the population under study, whereas a field survey allows more in-depth or detailed analysis of the situation. Field survey is particularly useful when examining the inter-relationships among several variables (e.g., different demographic groups income, age groups, ethnicity, occupation, gender, socioeconomic groups, but more importantly it involves surveying of a specific target sample (Cresswell, 2003; Apere, 2004; Saunders et al., 2003; 2012). In the context of this study, the specific target group constitutes 18-65-year-old employees in nursing homes across Middlesex, using questionnaires and interview methods to collect data on a one-off basis. In contrast, a longitudinal survey is a long-term-based survey that is repetitive or periodic or inconsistent use of surveying the same sample over an extended period using questionnaires or interviewing methods. The former is (i.e., cross-sectional survey) is utilised (Creswell, 2003; Saunders et al., 2012)

3.5.6) Explanatory Research Design

Explanatory research design in contrast tends to raise the question - why is it so in the real world? (Robson, 2002, 2007; Apere, 2004). Hence, it is often referred to as explanatory research. Again, in the context of this research, an appropriate explanatory research question will be, “*Why do nursing homes in London Middlesex does not practice diversity or implement diversity management practices?*” So, explanatory research is to do with asking a why set of questions, which is not relevant to this current research. This current research is not about asking the why type of questions. It is about looking at specific diversity and diversity management practices and their impact on employee performance. So, if the research design is misunderstood and misplaced, then there will be a fundamental problem with the rest of the research.

Several scholars have argued that the role of research design fundamentally is to kick start the research process by defining the research problem or phenomenon (Robson, 2002; 2007; Cresswell, et al., 2003). Research design gives the entire research process a framework to make it logically linked together for easier and practical conduct. This gives it the necessary structure; research design is not about data collection methods such as questionnaires or interview methods. All forms of research design will need a data collection method or any specific type of data collection whether it is quantitative data or qualitative data. All research designs will need data collection, research designs allow smooth data enquiry.

And that is why some scholars tend to describe research design as “*the source structure of an empirical investigation or enquiry*” aimed at “*avoiding*” mistakes along the line or enhancing the validity as well as reliability of the outcome of the research (Bell, 1999; Robson, 2002; 2007; 2011; Cresswell, 2003; Gorard, 2012). The research design is descriptive. The research designs generally acknowledged are experimental, case study, and action research, and survey.

3.6) Data Collection methods

Based on the epistemological requirement of this contextualized study, data collection methods that needed to be employed in this study engaged and/or embraced both quantitative and qualitative methodologies (mixed-method research). As stated, this is in line with the epistemological needs of the data collection process with this research. This means, the two main data collection methods: questionnaires and interviews were deployed.

3.6.1) Interviews

The researcher used interview methodology despite it being more expensive than the questionnaire approach. As already stated, focus or discussion groups would be key instruments of being used, as a qualitative approach is adopted. An interview is an in-depth, flexible, and adaptable survey technique that involved a one-to-one conversation between the interviewer and the interviewee to extract data or ‘to find out things’ (Gilbert, 2001; Robson, 2002, Henn et al., 2009) also cited by Eguruze, 2016:75). Therefore, there was impartiality involved – are you trying to say that impartiality was involved or not? This follows the epistemological requirement for

justified belief (i.e., the task of finding out the truth), as this cannot be compromised (Cresswell, 2003, 2007; Cresswell et al., 2003; Saunders et al., 2003; 2012; Eguruze, 2016, 2017). The researcher was involved and committed to the entire data collection process as expected in obtaining maximum information relating to attitude and opinions, while collecting the qualitative data, using the interview schedule and interview guides, as instruments for data collection.

Questionnaires and interviews were the primary methods of data collection used in this study. This helped in eliciting the opinions of carers, managers, receptionists, nurses, and cleaners. Participants were invited via email to participate. In line with ethical requirements, interview schedule/guides were used as data collection instruments. Using the interview schedule/interview guide instruments, before discussions (i.e., interviews) took place, the researcher gained more positive interview outcomes from the sessions. This was because these meetings were pre-arranged with the potential participants/respondents, to be held at their work or natural community. The copies of the interview schedule/guide relating to the interview/discussion group were also sent to them (the participants/respondents) in advance before the interview/discussion session. As already stated, this enabled potential participants/respondents to familiarise themselves with the contents before the discussion /interview took place, which yielded better outcomes in terms of participation level and interest, and prior knowledge of the contents. The reason for this was to eliminate any surprises, as that would be unethical according to the rules of ethical conduct with data collection (Henn et. al, 2009; Eguruze, 2016, 2017).

A research interview is a planned conversation between an interviewer and an interviewee, whereby the former asks precise purposeful questions to which the latter carefully listens and replies accordingly (Yin, 2014). Interviews may be structured that is using standardised questions, unstructured/ informal where there is no predetermined list of questions, or semi structured interview (SSI). It is important to note that when conducting interviews one can rarely examine all relevant information for the phenomenon under investigation (Jacoben 2002)

In this thesis, the writer used a semi-structured interview. As diversity can be understood differently by different people purposefully selecting respondents (managers, deputies, human resource managers, and their assistants) which according to Jacoben (2002) means that the analysis is based on the fact that most appropriate candidates are picked to highlight the phenomenon which in this case is diversity management. The researcher intends to obtain a deeper understanding of some specific aspects of diversity management and how they influence employee performance. Such quality of knowledge based on experience is of excellent value to the researcher as she will gain a better understanding of diversity and compare it with theory to offer a useful conclusion to the organisation which could enhance practice.

Before the meetings, the interviewer will make sure they follow ethical procedures, and explanations provided to the interviewee in advance as well as signing consent forms. Alternatively, the telephone interviews were done where the respondent could not be met in person.

At the start of the interviews, the researcher would 'state that she is a Doctorate student at the University of the West of Scotland investigating how diversity management practices can impact on employee performance'. Then the researcher will inquire if they are ready for the interview or would arrange a suitable time if not previously arranged. Also, the researcher will reassure the respondent that the responses would be anonymous to encourage full participation in all questions. Moreover, the researcher will ask if they could record the conversation. If the respondent was not comfortable, notes were taken as they respond to the questions.

The researcher conducted face-to-face interviews with the management staff from the nursing home with each interview lasting between 40-60 minutes. Conducting a semi-structured interview allows for modification even during the interview process; therefore, such level flexibility allows the researcher to stay consistent, thus ensuring high levels of validity (Leech, 2002). Moreover, validation will also be conducted by checking for any chances of fraud, finding out if the research criteria were followed, and ensuring that all the questions were asked during the data collection process. Validation had to be done by sending the transcribed scripts back to the respondents for validation; however, because of time constraints, the transcribed copies were not sent to the respondents.

3.6.1.1) Advantages *and Disadvantages*

Importantly, the researcher will still choose to use interviews, although interviews are known to be a more expensive way of collecting data than questionnaire data collecting method. The interview was more appropriate than the questionnaire in this kind of project data requirement. It is also more adaptable than the questionnaire approach. It is also more flexible in that the researcher could engage in a one-to-one conversation or even group and derived instant face-to-face feedback or if not sufficient, take or obtain a follow-up question and feedback, all at one go, which makes it an appropriate data collection strategy to 'find-out-the facts' more accurately and objectively in this context(Gilbert, 2001; Robson,2002; Henn et al., 2009; Eguruze, 2016,2017).

Also, other scholars have provided different accounts on the advantages of the qualitative approach such as interviews. Some feel that interviews such as focus groups or discussion groups are so key to qualitative study as they offer enough room for in-depth conversations, during which members of the group interact freely and communicate their own experiences, fortunes, challenges, etc. whilst at the same time also learning from and/or exchanging with other participants/respondents of their own experiences(Silvermann, 1985, 1970, 2012; Eguruze, 2016, 2017). Others believed and added that such data obtained that is based on their own life experiences and knowledge are usually invaluable quality or value to data being collected and therefore an

ultimately better quality of the outcome of the study in terms of it leading to a better understanding of the phenomenon (Czinkota et al., 1992:339; Eguruze, 2016, 2017). Others argue that using the qualitative approach would ultimately enable the researcher to obtain or access the desired richer in-depth personal data from the health professionals themselves, who have the necessary practical knowledge and experience that the researcher is seeking to gain, and makes the qualitative data (Mann, 1985; Eguruze, 2016, 2017). The opportunity to ask to follow up questions by the researcher against respondents' feedback is in fact, a crucial way to ensure clarity of data or clarify things or doubts and, a great way of avoiding bias, in a qualitative research process (Densin and Linkoln, 2003; Eguruze, 2016; 2017).

Based on the above narratives, the researcher believes that interview would offer the much-needed flexibility and scope for quality interaction to take place between the researcher and participants, which would be most desirable. That way, the researcher would be more likely to achieve the specified research aims and objectives. And crucially, this would enable the researcher to make further contributions to the knowledge and saving lives and improving the wellbeing and quality of life of potential benefactors of the tools. So, the researcher believes that a qualitative approach, interview strategy is so vital in this project in terms of obtaining the qualitative data, the thoughts, perceptions, feelings, behaviours, and experiences directly from the health professionals.

3.6.2) Questionnaires

Besides, the researcher used the questionnaires for the quantitative data collection, in which self-completion or self-administered questionnaire instruments were used to obtain the necessary data. Self-completion questionnaire is: -

“a questionnaire that respondents answer without the aid of an interviewer” (Bryman and Bell, 2007:718) and cited by Eguruze, 2016: 74).

Questionnaires are mostly used in business and management within the survey strategy and should be designed to facilitate easy analysis. They are the most practical ways of collecting, extracting, and registering information (Bryman ad Bell 2007:718). Questionnaires are the most suitable tools used by researchers because of the anonymity they provide and because respondents can complete them at their convenience and enormous amounts of data could be collected. However, one aggravated aspect of questionnaire-based research is that an assertive finding quoted everywhere could be based on a thoroughly flawed or superficial piece of work using meticulously collected data and subjected to skilled analysis. When results are published, the methodology employed is likely to be invisible to readers; as a result, there is always a professional obligation on good researchers to maintain the highest standards (Davis & Nathan, 2014).

For the researcher to create the questionnaire, careful designing, checking, and revision was at the planning phase. After undertaking the literature review, looking at related research instruments, and discussing with the director of studies, the researcher drafted sections of the questionnaires. In section A, the respondents were

required to provide general demographic information. Section B and C were all in Likert scale format scored on a five-point scale that is 1 to 5, with (1) Strongly disagree, (2)-disagree – (3) neither agree nor disagree (4) Agree, (5) Strongly Agree. While the latter consisted of thirteen questions on diversity management, the former was made up of ten questions about diversity and performance, all questions were formulated based on searches on survey monkey. Thus a 23-item survey instrument was developed to obtain responses from the workforce in nursing homes.

The use of the Likert Scale from one to five has also enabled the researcher to obtain a more detailed and in-depth indication of the participant's feelings. Sarantakos (1993) states that Likert scales have been the most popular choice of social scientists, and results obtained are typically easy to input and analyse. Likert Scales helps respondents to 'point out the extent to which they agree or disagree with a range of statements' (Sekaran, 1992, p. 170). It is an ordinal scale 'that makes easy, the ranking of individuals in terms of the favourableness of the attitudes toward a given object (Kidder, 1981, p. 216). With a Likert scale, the respondent is forced to choose by indicating their degree of accord or discrepancy with a said statement.

The Likert Scale originated with five degrees of agreement, and although some researchers can use as much as seven, I decided to stick with five degrees as this was enough for the study. The reliability of the Likert Scale has been the reason it was chosen for this research (Davis, 1996).

The researcher started with friendly and less threatening questions relevant to diversity. Basic demographic questions related to sexuality, age, ethnicity might be considered personal questions that might demotivate the participant. Questions were straightforward and carefully designed to avoid ambiguous or overlapping questions. The researcher was also mindful of the number of unstructured questions used in the questionnaire as this might further complicate the analysis process or impact the results obtained.

After formulating the questionnaire and receiving final feedback from classmates and supervisors, the questionnaire was piloted in the university and analysed to obtain the internal consistency which according to Cronbach alpha would be between 0.7 to 1. The researcher used students from the faculty of health and social care, and this was because students in this section of the university are most likely to have or are working in the care sector. As a result, over 40 students were used in the pilot studies, 15 managers, and 25 health care assistants. The time taken by the slowest respondent to complete the questionnaire was about 20mins. Therefore, the approximate time during the actual data collection period was between 15-20mins. A soft copy of the original consent, as well as the participant information form, was sent to all respondent emails before data collection. These forms were sent by email to save time, cost, and the method is environmentally friendly. Questions were formulated based on the independent variable (age, gender, ethnicity, flexible work hours, and motivation schemes) as well as the independent variable (employee performance).

3.7) Designing research strategy.

Research design is a comprehensive plan implemented by a researcher to find answers to research questions. It contains a thoughtful structure of investigation or a list of specifications for directing and monitoring a research project (Heppner et al. 1992:15) to guide the researcher to achieve the goals of the entire study. Research designs usually include the research aim, objectives, problem, hypotheses, clearly defined variables, data collection, and analysis method suitable for gathering, analysing to the presentation of the findings of the project.

3.8) Mixed method approaches

The mixed methods approach integrates methods of collecting or analysing data from the quantitative and qualitative research approaches in a single research study (Creswell, 2003; Johnson & Onwuegbuzie 2010; Tashakkori & Teddlie 1998). Here the researchers collect and analyse not only numerical data, which is customary for quantitative research but also narrative data, which is the norm for qualitative research to address the research question(s) defined for a research study. Below is a representation of mixed research:

Figure 3. 1 Mixed Methods Approach (Source: Author)

3.8.1) The benefits of mixed-method research

First, it enables researchers to be flexible in their investigative techniques, as they try to address a variety of research questions that arise. Pragmatic researchers also are more likely to promote collaboration among researchers, regardless of philosophical orientation. Based on Newman and Benz's (1998) conceptualisation of the role of theory in quantitative and qualitative inquiries. The last sentence is incomplete and needs to be tied

in with the previous or next statement as appropriate. Pragmatic researchers are more likely to view research as a holistic endeavour that requires continued engagement, persistent observation, and triangulation (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). By having a positive attitude towards both techniques, pragmatic researchers are in a better position to use qualitative research to inform the quantitative portion of research studies, and vice versa. For example, the inclusion of quantitative data can help compensate for the fact that qualitative data typically cannot be generalised. The inclusion of qualitative data can help explain relationships discovered by quantitative data. Similarly, pragmatic researchers also are more able to combine empirical precision with descriptive precision (Onwuegbuzie, 2003). Combining quantitative and qualitative research helps to develop a conceptual framework, to validate quantitative findings by referring to information taken from the qualitative phase of the study, and to construct indices from qualitative data that can be used to analyse quantitative data.

Moreover, quantitative research is typically motivated by the researcher's concerns, whereas qualitative research is a desire to capture the participant's voice, pragmatic researchers can merge these two emphases within a single investigation. Because pragmatic researchers utilise mixed methodologies within the same inquiry, they can probe further into a dataset to understand its meaning and to use one method to verify findings from the other method.

3.8.2) Limitations of mixed-method research

There are several barriers associated with the use of mixed-method research. Conflicting results could arise due to the multiple forms of data collected and analysed, which usually need extensive time and resources to interpret and offer a valid conclusion or providing the recommended course of action. Also, most students find the language used in quantitative research is particularly difficult. Onwuegbuzie, DaRos, and Ryan (1997) found that, for many graduate students, statistics anxiety stems from the conventions of notation and terminology. These learners find the language and structure to be unusual. Also, some students report an uneasiness at being asked to accept certain assumptions, formulas, and concepts, as is common in statistical analyses.

Moreover, as noted above, the dearth of pragmatic researchers also appears to stem from researchers' faulty perceptions of a one-to-one relationship between epistemology and method. Recently, Gueulette, Newgent, and Newman (1999) analysed 339 randomly selected studies that were labelled by their authors as representing qualitative research and found that 44.1% of these articles involved the blending of qualitative and quantitative methodologies. This latter finding illustrates the existing blurred line between quantitative and qualitative research.

3.8.3) Justification for using a mixed method design.

Rather than focusing on positivism or interpretivism, the writer intends to focus on what works regarding the questions under investigation to avoid a one-sided view while carrying the studies. According to Saunders et al

(2012) pragmatists intend to carry out studies with the notion that they are free to interpret experiences in a way that they see fit. Although, it been great for the researcher to tackle this area of study in a pragmatic way because of the varying dimensions and different interpretations from organisation to organisation. This was not possible due to time constraints. Although the researcher used mixed methods at distinct levels in the study, and adopted an-open minded approach, the method used for collecting data was undertaken simultaneously, which could not make the researcher not to adopt a pragmatist stance for this study. The researcher used a directory comprising of all the nursing homes in London they are the ones in the position to have better knowledge on diversity practices as they were the ones implementing the diversity policies. The questionnaires were administered to other employees as well as managers. The researcher intended to interview managers, deputy managers, team leads, and top managers. The specific number to interview was not predetermined because the researcher had to stop when the saturation of information became obvious. Interviews were recorded then fully transcribed. Before an interview, participants were assured their replies would remain confidential, and they could withdraw anytime from the studies. 500 hard copy questionnaires were sent to the homes that were willing to participate in the studies. 361 participants returned the questionnaires, and among those returned, thirty-four were incomplete so they could not be included in the studies, leaving 327 questionnaires to be analysed.

3.8.4) Study population

One of the most important aspects of research is clearly defining the research population. According to Saunders et al. (2016) for a manageable population, it is possible to collect data from the entire population, and in this case, it is referred to as a census. According to the research area, it is impossible to study each care home in Middlesex London. As a result, the data collection will take place in the care homes that have allowed access to the researcher.

Moreover, within these organisations, data will not be collected from every single employee. With regards to questionnaires, the researcher visited these organisations on their team meeting days so that she could meet as many employees as possible. However, if this was not possible, the researcher made few visits to each organisation and collected data from the consenting staff. The study population for the interview was an employee in management who has worked for the firm for over two years. Clarifying the target population at the initial stage facilitated the process as time and budget constraints were some of the main hindrances in the studies.

3.8.5) Sampling/ Sample

In general, a sample is the selection of the part of the total population or products under examination. Samples are used to make inferences about an aspect of the total population without undertaking a census of the entire population (Pass et al. 1991:541). More specifically, a sample is a subset of the specific population under study derived by using techniques such as probability and non-probability sampling. According to Saunders et al.

(2016), choosing a sampling frame is vital because, without one, it will be impossible to use a probability sampling technique. As the researcher is investigating health and social care precisely in care homes, the sampling frame at this initial stage was the database of all care homes within the Middlesex area.

3.8.6) Sample size /selection of participants

Using probability sampling and generalising about the target population from which data was collected was based on statistical probability. The greater the participants, the less likely the error in generalising to the target population. However, according to Saunders et al. (2016), the choice of the sample size is governed by the:

- The ability to collect data that is representative of the target population. Data collected from these organisations was highly representative of the diversity in the health care sector (target population)
- The possibility of tolerating a margin of error.

For this thesis, the researcher started with a probability sampling method known as simple random sampling. Here, the sampling frame was a list of all nursing homes on a directory in Middlesex London. According to Davies & Hughes (2014), to be able to use simple random sampling, an accurate list of the population under study must be obtained. To ensure equal participation, the researcher sent emails to all the nursing homes on the list to offer an equal chance of participation of all the homes. The researcher received replies from some who were interested in participating and as a result, the access process, which later ended in data collection.

Not many nursing homes accepted to participate in the study, and this aspect was beyond the control of the researcher. However, for the researcher to have a balanced view of the diversity aspect under investigation, a non-probability sampling method, called quota sampling, had to be implemented (Davies & Hughes 2014). According to the researcher that concerning, it made sense to identify the specific groups to which the results will apply rather than interviewing disproportionately. For example, one of the areas of interest is minority representation in nursing homes and how this influences performance. In the writer's opinion, obtaining a correct quota of the diversity groups will ensure correct representation, which will allow generalisability of the findings. However, the researcher noted that this opens possibility to collect data from respondents available, receiving email replies only from those who use emails or interviewing only those who were friendly. To avoid this criticism, the researcher at the initial sampling stage used simple random sampling.

3.8.7) Ethical considerations

Research is not just about collecting information but concerned with the dignity, safety, rights, and wellbeing of anyone involved in the process. When considering the phenomenon of research ethics, it is important to state that the whole research process is far from being a neutral process. Unfortunately, research has not always had the best of records when it comes to ethical practice. Professional bodies and some organisations have established codes of practice and committees which scrutinise research proposals to ensure that the research conforms to

recognised standards of ethical practice. In the case of these studies, the University of the West of Scotland ethical committee had to do their checks to ensure the studies were valid and do not go against any data protection laws. For a student to obtain ethical approval, a summary of the research methodology, a participant information sheet, a consent form as well as questionnaires were sent to the ethics committee for approval. Approval was carried out in two phases. Initially, the Director of Studies (DOS) had to check the files submitted to the committee, sign, and then the ethics committee. After about eight weeks, the ethical team responded, however, in my case, the committee requested some minor changes before commencing data collection.

3.8.8) Validity & Reliability

Validity is the extent to which the survey instrument measures what it is intended to measure. According to Pelissier (2008), internal validity refers to the extent to which research findings match the reality that is whether the manipulation of the independent variable would cause and visible effects on the dependent variable. External validity refers to the extent to which findings are replicable in other environments and whether results can be generalised to a population.

The most basic type of validity is facing validity, which is a subjective type carried out by the researcher without applying any scientific approach. Construct validity is a type of validity testing with the involvement of a panel of experts. Content and sampling validity are similar in that the former refers to the effectiveness of the measure about providing information that can be used to improve specific aspects of a concept while the latter ensures a vast coverage of the area of study, not just a specific issue.

Reliability is a measure of the degree to which a research instrument yields consistent results over time (Mugenda, 2003). According to Garson (2006), reliability could be estimated using Cronbach's Coefficient Alpha, interpreted as the percentage of variance where the observed scale is a true scale composed of all possible items. In general, reliability less than 0.6 is considered poor, while a scale of 0.7 to 0.8 is considered acceptable. Any internal consistency score of less than 0.7 is considered poor and unacceptable.

Internal validity was applied during the construction and restructuring of the questions to address relevant issues on the topic. Demographic questions were in the last section after completely exploring the main idea (Effects of diversity on performance) of the thesis.

With regards to external validity, survey research is quantitative research, the strategy is strong compared to qualitative research strategies because a representative sample of the population is being analysed. Statistical generalisation suggests results that are based on analyses of a sample that could be generalised to the population. The question arises, however, regarding to what extent findings can be generalised. Studies on diversity management normally case studies in which survey research techniques are used to examine attitudes and behaviour of employees in different workgroups in one or more organisations. External generalisability is then

limited to the precise cause. Additionally, the organisational context is often only used post hoc to interpret the findings (Joshi and Roh 2009).

3.8.9) *Reliability test for primary constructs*

The researcher intends to measure the internal consistency of the constructs and hopes to achieve a Cronbach’s alpha of 0.7 to 1.0. After conducting this statistical test on SPSS, a reliability score of 0.75 was obtained, which is acceptable in most social science studies. For the individual items computed, the following alpha scores were obtained. Nunnally’s (1978) criteria require Cronbach’s alpha to be over 0.70 to indicate reliability; the results presented above matched that criterion.

Table 3. 2 Cronbach values for instrument reliability (test) using SPSS 20.0 Source: SPSS Output

Scale	Aspect investigated	Reliability as measured by Cronbach’s Alpha
1	Age diversity/performance	0.77
2	Cultural (Ethnicity)diversity /performance	0.76
3	Gender diversity/performance	0.70
4	Flexible working hours/performance	0.82
5	Motivational schemes/performance	0.79
6	Cross-Cultural training/performance	0.76

3.8.10) *Summary quantitative results Table 3.2*

The research questions have been tested at an alpha = 0.05 significance level

Rule: Accept research question if P-value is less than the significance level, on the other hand, if P-value is more than significance value, then reject the research question. Table 3. 3 Summary quantitative results based on the research questions.

Dependent Variable	Independent variable	P-value	Significance level	T	Implications

Employee performance	Gender	0.001	0.05	7.468	Accepted
	Age	0.840	0.05	0.157	Rejected
	Ethnicity	0.004	0.05	6.182	Accepted
	Flexible working hours	0.020	0.05	5.032	Accepted
	Motivational strategies	0.002	0.05	7.229	Accepted
	Cross-cultural training	0.040	0.05	2.792	Accepted

3.8.11) Ethical Issues

3.8.11.1) Access

Gaining access is a major issue in any research project (reference) because it can be more time-consuming and difficult than is predicted. The researcher needed to think carefully about who should be asked to take part in the study and, then the best way to collect information. In this study, the writer thought access issues would be easier as the primary data was to be collected from the places of work of the researcher. However, the researcher thought that it would be biased to conduct studies at their place of work, because questionnaires will be filled by work colleagues who might not be able to divulge information or completed maybe just for friendship's sake. As a result, the researcher sent out emails to over 150 different nursing homes around London Middlesex. Despite getting access to the nursing homes, the researcher, had to gain consent from employees before administering the questionnaires. Informed consent refers to the individual's right to decide whether they wish to participate in a specific research project or not (Davis, 2005, p. 460). Any researcher must ensure that procedures are in place to allow potential participants to decide. It is important to let participants understand that involvement is free and usually written informed consent is provided to all participants. Respondents had information before taking part in the research about diversity, its practices, and how some specific diversity management practices affect performance. All participants had to understand that their involvement in the research was completely voluntary. Equally, they could withdraw from the study at any point and without fear of retribution.

Moreover, participants were made aware that they could even withdraw data even after completing the questionnaires. According to Davis (2005, p. 460): -

"...the principle of informed consent does not remove from the researcher the duty to minimise undue intrusion in the lives of participants".

Before starting the process of data collection, respondents had to choose whether to participate in the study or not. The researcher explained to the participants that the studies were purely for academic purposes and that findings will be used to improve organisational practice. According to Saunders et al. (2014), It is important not to assume that people understand what is involved in a research project and that individuals can ask questions for clarifications.

Another important form in the research process was to ensure good practice is to include the participant information. This piece of paper allowed potential participants to know about the researcher and the reason for conducting the studies. Here, the researcher might want to consider explaining that there is a possibility of including participants who fall within the category of what the researcher is exploring but do not meet the criteria set out by the researcher. The information sheet for participants must included a description of the study; what it means for the participant; how long participants will spend answering questions/ filling in a questionnaire; information on confidentiality; whether taking part is compulsory and details of those to contact in case of any doubts. All the above information was stated in the participant sheet in very simple language because there was a possibility of involving employees with low literacy levels who might only agree to take part after fully understanding what was involved. There was an arrangement for verbal presentation so that potential participants were encouraged to answer all the questions asked.

3.8.11.2) Risk /harm involved in research.

Risk must be handled with care when undertaking any research, and it is because it might be difficult to define. It is important to recognise that harm can be psychological as well as physical. While physical harm needs little in the way of explanation; psychological harm can be more complex. For example, psychological harm might arise if participants are embarrassed or humiliated during a study. Less obviously, questionnaires that ask people to reveal demographic data about themselves concerning their attitudes or beliefs, or religious or political affiliations can cause anxiety for some respondents. While it is not always possible to anticipate all the possible consequences of participating in a research project, a specific issue – both risks and benefits – should be identified. To minimise the risk of harm, the university's ethical committee had to check consent forms and information sheets to ensure that the proposed research accords with accepted principles of good practice as much as possible. Moreover, the researcher explained to participants that research activity is quite separate from service provision, and their use of services is not related to whether they take part, and that confidentiality is taken into consideration.

3.8.11.3) Confidentiality and anonymity

The issue of confidentiality, in a research study, can be complex. The researcher will provide different names to the nursing homes where the study will take place. Data collected during a research study was in a locked cupboard, and only the researcher had access to the information. It is important to state the way confidentiality is dealt with varies based on the methodology, and this issue had to be considered when choosing a method for the studies. Sometimes these issues are straight forward, for example, in the case of the face-face interview. However, it should be noted that the issue of confidentiality might become slightly complex when dealing with focus groups as participants might not be sure of how opinions expressed in groups are managed. To overcome these issues, the writer administered questionnaires individually and interviewed participants separately. The researcher was able to explain to the participants that the information they provided will be protected and the GDPR (2018) legislation was taken into consideration.

Another area of concern to the participants was printing their names in the questionnaire. It is important to provide individuals with the assurance that their names will not be needed, and they should not by any chance provide the names during the studies used in anything written because of the research. However, individuals might feel that their demographic information can reveal information about them. This fear was taken care of during the analysis stage, and information was disguised in research reports when evaluating a specific service or services in a small geographical area.

3.9) Summary

As seen above, this chapter illustrated the reflexive narrative of the research methodology chosen in relation to this research. In its relevant and unique way by avoiding the unnecessary general aspects of methodology, it briefly explained the methodological approach that underpinned this study and why the mixed-method approach was adopted to resolve the research questions, which are outlined above, using a mixed-methods approach that helped the researcher respond to the key research question: What is the impact of diversity and workforce diversity management practices on the employee performance in nursing homes in the UK: *A Case Study of Care Homes in Middlesex-London?* Additionally, the chapter clarified practical aspects, including the challenges of conducting this research, and the issues that were experienced during fieldwork. Accordingly, as the methodology task has been completed, the researcher now moves on to the next chapter of the research: which would be chapter four; data analysis and interpretation.

CHAPTER FOUR

4) DATA ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

4.1) Quantitative data analysis & interpretation

4.1.1) Introduction

This chapter is divided into three parts for clarity. Part, one relates to quantitative data analysis/interpretation and comprises twenty-two questions in a questionnaire format which are related to diversity and workforce diversity management practices. Part two relates to qualitative data analysis/interpretations of twelve questions that reflect the interview guide/schedule. Copies of the questions are in Appendix.

Part One relates to the quantitative data collection which consist of 21 questions in the questionnaire which were as follows: -

4.1.1 PT1Q1 Your current role in this organization

4.1.2. PT1Q2 Your age group.

4.1.3 PTQ3 Gender

4.1.4. PT1Q4 Your length of service

4.1.5. PT1Q5 Your ethnicity?

4.1.6. PT1Q6 Your highest educational qualification?

4.1.7. PT1Q7, Do you consider yourself disabled?

4.1.8 PT1Q8 My organisation is an Equal opportunity promoter.

4.1.9 PT1Q9 A workforce diversity would have a more positive influence on performance than a negative influence.

4.1.10 PT1Q10: Diversity training is part of the organisation's mandatory training,

4.1.11 PT1Q 11 Prospective employees are interviewed by a diverse team.

4.1.12 PT1Q12 Mentoring programs are offered to all employees in the organization.

4.1.13 PT1Q13 I think women are better performers than men in the context of nursing home care provisions.

4.1.14 PT1Q14 I feel included when I am part of the decision-making process in my organization.

4.1.15 PT1Q15 My performance increases when I work in a diverse team.

4.1.16 PT1Q16 My performance increases when I am on a Flexible working contract.

4.1.17 PT1Q17 Cross-cultural training enhances my performance.

4.1.18 PT1Q18 I perform better when I am given a bonus.

4.1.19 PT1Q19 Career progression opportunities are offered to all employees regardless of their background.

4.1.20 PT1Q20 Employee absenteeism has a negative influence on performance.

4.1.21 PT1Q21 'Management offers flexible working contracts to employees when needed due to its many benefits'.

4.1.22 PT1Q22 BAME in frontline roles are better educated than their white counterparts.

Part Two relates to the qualitative data collection. It contains of a 12-item interview guide/schedule (questions) as follows: Responses to Interview Guide/Schedule, which comprises 12 questions as follows:

- 1) What do you understand by diversity?
- 2) What is your understanding of diversity management?
- 3) What is the composition of your top management team concerning gender, sex Black and ethnic minority (BEM)?
- 4) In what ways can gender diversity influence performance in nursing homes?
- 5) What do you think will be the results if a team of employees is made up of various employees of various age groups?
- 6) Are there any diversity management practices that encourage performance in your team?
- 7) Does staff have any specific diversity training (cross-cultural training)?
- 8) Do you think diversity training (cross-cultural training) will have any effect on performance?
- 9) In your opinion can motivation enhance performance in your organisation.?
- 10) In your opinion, what effects will flexible working hours have on the performance of the diverse team?
- 11) What are the challenges faced by the organisation working with diverse employees?
- 12) In your opinion, is diversity management good for business? (See appendix for complete interview questions)

Part three covers general interpretation of the quantitative and qualitative. Thereafter summary of the chapter follows.

4.1.2) Responses to Questionnaire - Part 1

Out of 500 questionnaires that were administered, 400 questionnaires were returned. It means that the response rate was over 80%, which is believed to be high participation/high engagement in the empirical process. However, 73 were incomplete, therefore were voided and not counted. Table 1 Showing analyses of the Questionnaire Response data.

4.1.3 PT1 Q1 Your current role in this organisation?

Table 4. 1 Summary of Questionnaire Response Data

	Frequency	Percentage %
Returned Complete Questionnaires	327	65.4%
Returned Incomplete Questionnaires	73	14.6%
Unreturned Questionnaires	100	20%
Total	500	100

□ Frontline staff (248) □ Managers (79)

Figure 4. 1 Showing the role of Participants in organization.

Figure 4.1 shows the total number of frontline staff who participated in the survey (327). Of this, 79 (or 24%) of the respondents were managers, whereas the number that represented the frontline staff were 248 (or 76%) of the respondents. Frontline staff are usually the first point of contact. In the case of nursing homes, they are made

up of nurses, carers, administrative staff, cleaners, and porters. As represented in Figure 4.1, there were more employees from diverse backgrounds in frontline roles compared to those at top levels. We live in a highly multicultural society, and this should be reflected at all levels in organisations. However, it was observed that at diverse levels within the organisation there was a dramatic difference in diverse representation, as staff moved higher up the employment ladder. There was little or no diversity in managerial positions yet greater diversity in bottom line roles. The Equality Act (2010, as amended) would be the most relevant legislation that covers a wide spectrum of diversity and workforce diversity management practices and organisational conducts, and nursing homes are no exceptions to this.

4.1.4) PT1Q2 Your Age Group

□ 18-27 □ 28-37 □ 38-47 □ 48-57 □ 58 plus

Figure 4. 2 Showing the age groups of participants.

Figure 4.2 shows the respondents by age distribution as it indicates many of the managers and frontline staff were between the ages 28-37 (or 38%). The age group with the second highest representation was within the ages of 18-27(or 28%). While the least number of employees that at the 58 years of age and over were just 8 (2.44%). Those between the ages of 38-47yrs made up the third largest of the total surveyed population (22.6%).

The data showed that a relatively high percentage of the workforce is in their active, productive years, which is about 47% or younger.

The above statistics are in line with other research findings. According to these study findings, physical activity is inextricably connected with aging, as changes in patterns and their relationship to health and function occur accordingly (DiPietro, 2001). And, according to Lehman (1953, 1956, 1966) and (Simonton, 1988) the younger age groups are more likely to be the greatest achieving age in a range of ways: creativity, energy, endurance, etc. So, they are more likely to be at their peak in terms of performance or productivity. It means that a person's workability declines with age. Both physical and mental function becomes more impaired. And chronic diseases and certain other health issues become exacerbated (DiPietro, 2001). One of the characteristics of physical activity with advancing age is the lower engagement of older employees and performance. However, these patterns may be highly dependent on the type of physical activity (Bijnen et al. 1998, DiPietro et al. 1989). In nursing homes where the job requires the use of considerable physical work especially in front-line roles, the results above could be used to justify this literature (DiPietro, 2001; Bijnen et al. 1998, DiPietro et al. 1989; Bijnen, Caspersen, and Feskens, 1998). As the employees get older their numbers reduce dramatically. As changes in physical activity because of aging, changes in work patterns and the relationship to health and function.

With these statistics, the implications for recruiting for a nursing home are clear: the age groups 28-37 (or 38%) and 18-27 (or 28%) should be more likely targets for the same purpose than others. But then they are also less experienced which means more training and development costs implications are to be noted. In contrast, the older age group with more experience than the younger groups. So, age diversity is an extremely relevant issue, which is inevitable and is important for organisations to manage (D'Netto, 1994, D'Netto and Sohal, 1999; ONS, 2010, 2017, 2019). According to ONS (Ibid), concerning the UK, the number of persons aged 65 and older grew by 15% from 2000 to 2010. By 2051, it is estimated that the older population will double by increasing to 88.5 million, a figure accounting for 20.1% of the entire population (The Guardian, 2010; ONS, Ibid). The older minority population will rise, as this group is expected to double over the next four decades (Ibid).

These are some of the critical diversity issues inherent in the diversity and workforce diversity discourse within the nursing homes in Middlesex-London, which are inevitable. So, using experienced recruiters and materials that reflect such important diverse balance and lastly communicating the importance of the value of diversity to all applicants to maintain a positive atmosphere among recruits could be helpful (Arthur & Doverspike 2005).

In addition to these, the Equality Act (2010, as amended) would be the most relevant legislation that covers a wide spectrum of diversity and workforce diversity management practices and organisational conducts, and nursing homes are no exceptions to this. In the UK, organisations cannot discriminate based on age, race, gender, disability, sexuality, or sexual orientation, etc., except otherwise explicitly stated. Moreover, cross-cultural

training addresses the differences in cultures, and to do this, training is the best method to reduce intercultural conflict (Naumann, 1992; Friedlander & Walton 2000).

4.1.5 PT1Q3 Gender

□ Male 181 □ Female 139; Others 7

Figure 4. 3 Gender

Figure 4.3 relates to gender. According to the quantitative response data for gender, as shown in Figure 5, a total of 327 responded to this question. Of this figure, 181 (or 55%) were female, while 139 (or 43%) were male respondents, and 7 (or 2%) constitute other respondents (who do not wish to specify their gender status).

It shows some contrasting statistics:

- (i) At the category of frontline workers females constituted a total of 146 (or 59%), as opposed to male counterparts at 96(or 39%), while 6 (or 2%) were others,
- (ii) At the management level, the representative figures were as follows: 35 (44.3%) were females as opposed to 43 males (54.4%) and (1.2%) did not mention their gender. These statistics seem to suggest that although there was fewer male than female workers in frontline roles, more males worked in top managerial roles.

Crucially, this result seems to reflect the reality in nursing homes with a disproportionate distribution of gender within the profession, even though there seemed to be more female patients and staff at nursing homes than males. According to literature evidence, the nursing profession has been associated with the female gender since Florence Nightingale’s era. Men find it difficult to advance in nursing because of stereotypes and individuals thinking that the profession is for females. Men think that it is unwise to choose a career with negative

perceptions working in frontline caring roles. This might be the reason why men prefer management position in health care hence their increased representation at top levels. Literature suggests, the movement of immigrants from diverse backgrounds into the UK has rapidly increased (Johnson,2003). According to Knippenberg et al, (2004) both male and female immigrants mostly occupy low paid jobs with UK female population, largely constituting the associated healthcare workforce. Scholars suggest it is important to avoid the consequences of gender pay imbalance (Golden, 1990) and/or important negotiate gender pay gap as tackling such gender pay imbalance is critical (Gerhart and Rynes, 1991; Golden, 1990).

Scholars have also pointed out that undertaking leadership initiatives that reflect these crucial aspects of gender balance and the need to keep monitoring the same concerning the management of nursing homes is critical (Richard, 2000; Cox, 2001; Hubbard 2004). As previously stated, using experienced recruiters and materials that include diverse individuals and lastly communicating the importance of the value of diversity to all applicants to maintain a positive atmosphere among recruits is necessary (Arthur & Doverspike 2005).

Although it may be a criticism or a barrier from a mentorship perspective, there is reluctance in sponsoring women or ethnic minorities by a white mentor, (Fitt and Newton, 1989; Blackburn, Chapman, and Cameron 1981; Bowers, 1984). This is seen from a mentorship perspective, and this perceived reluctance to sponsor female or an ethnic minority or person of colour, might have been due to perceived greater threat or greater risk from females or an ethnic minority or person of colour than would be from a 'fellow white male', (Fitt and Newton, 1989; Blackburn, Chapman and Cameron 1981; Bowers, 1984). Mentorship is critical to professional career progression or mobility. Mentors are said to be a higher ranking, experienced, knowledgeable, top-level, influential, and senior members of organisations who guide and groom junior workers through their career progression (Collins, 1983; Kram, 1985; Roches, 1979).

So, given that women and people from ethnic minorities are already disproportionately represented or numerically rare at the top-level management positions, they are less likely to get by mentorship. Lack of mentors and role models are barriers for many women and ethnic minorities. Mentors are extremely important for women and people of ethnic minority, especially since they need experience of mentors to nurture them. The guidance, encouragement, and advocacy that mentors can provide to overcome such obstacles as isolation, lack of credibility, and lack of political patronage or connection (Jeruchin and Shapiro, 1992; Morrison, 1992).

Not having a mentor who is trustworthy and knowledgeable about career mobility is a factor that further contributes to the problem of unwise career decisions (Morrison, 1992).

Yet, according to the latest report, Gender balance is fundamentally critical to success in tackling gender inequalities, race inequalities, and social inequalities. According to the latest research report (Sky News, 01/08/20), companies with female secretaries perform better (Sky News, 01/08/20). A balanced gender balance

team is always better, yet promotion is not reflecting this. Males are being promoted faster and consistently more frequently than women. S (Financial and Women Equality Campaigner, 2020, Skynews, 11.45 am).

4.1.6 PT1Q4 Your Length of Service.

Figure 4. 4: Length of Service (Service duration)

On one hand, □ 0-2year length of service (74 respondents); □ 3-5years length of service (104 respondents); □ 6-8years length of service (90 respondents); □ 90 plus length of service (59 respondents), a total of 327 respondents. On the other hand, of the 327 respondents to this question, female workers 186 (or 56%) compared to that of males at 134 (or 41%) and others 7 (or 2%).

Again, there a total of 327 respondents; of this 248 were frontline staff, while the managers were 79. The highest proportion of staff has worked in the organisation between 3-5years in either frontline or managerial roles. There was an insignificant difference in the service duration of total respondents who worked for 6-8 years either in frontline or managerial positions. The total number of respondents who had worked only 0-2 years and those over nine years was almost the same. Therefore, out of the 327 respondents, 200 of them have worked in nursing homes between 3-8years.

According to literature evidence, cross-cultural training addresses the differences in cultures, and to do this training is the best method to reduce intercultural conflict (Naumann, 1992). (Friedlander & Walton 2000). Besides, compliance with the Equality Act (2010, as amended), would be useful. This is because it is the overall legislation that covers a wide spectrum of diversity and workforce diversity management practices and organisational conducts, and nursing homes are no exceptions to this. There are differences in different age groups: this is mainly based on differences in motivational factors. Young people tend to be more motivated by

goals of personal achievements to the best of their potential, meaning-seeking more responsibilities and/or challenges, money, and enthusiasm, in contrast, unlike younger generations, older people are more likely to be pro-family and holidaying and engaging in nature or environmental activities, or losing appetite for additional responsibilities or less drive for achievement, etc. due to family commitments, etc. (Lehman, 1953, 1956, 1966, and Simonton, 1988, 1991). So, age is a factor of motivation. This could be because the older workforce is disillusioned due to previous treatment in the workplace where diversity and gender have not been recognized. They might have given up and have focused their energies elsewhere, other than the workplace, to achieve life fulfilment or a result of past experiences where the employers have allowed the aging employees to not feel valued leading to extra issue of age discrimination.

4.1.7 PT1Q5 Your Ethnicity?

Count of Ethnicity Roles	Column Labels		
	Frontline staff	Managers	Grand Total
Any other ethnic group		2	2
Asian British	44	12	56
Black/Black British African/ Carribean	80	14	94
Mixed Any other background	16	9	25
white Any other White Background	76	20	96
white British	32	22	54
Grand Total	248	79	327

Figure 4. 5: Ethnicity

There is a wide representation of various ethnicities across nursing homes. Asians constitute 44 (or 18%) of frontline workers; 12 (or 15%) of Managers. and 16 (or 17%) managers were black, while 80 (or 32%) of frontline workers; 14 (or 17 % of managers); and 94 (or 29%) of workers are from mixed other backgrounds;

Whites from any other backgrounds constitutes 76(or 31%) of frontline workers; 20 (or 25%) of managers, while British White; 32(or 13%) of frontline workers; 22(or 28%) were managers.

These statistics support the literature evidence available: according to scholars, ethnicity refers to the identification of a group based on perceived cultural uniqueness or as individuals belonging to a group of people with the same nationality or ethnic origin, race (Noon, 2007; Morgan & Vandy, 2009). Although others may perceive ethnicity differently, for example, this term is defined in multiple ways and has been identified to portray race, nationality, or ethnicity (Niederle, 2013). Other scholars see it as racial differences (Allport 1954, p. 192) while others see cultural diversity more in terms of nationality. And as previously stated, in these ethnically diverse situations, according to literature evidence, cross-cultural training is important; cross-cultural training addresses the differences in cultures, and to do this training is the best method to reduce intercultural conflict (Naumann, 1992; Friedlander & Walton 2000).

Also, compliance with the Equality Act (2010, as amended), would be useful. This is because it is the overall legislation that covers a wide spectrum of diversity and workforce diversity management practices and organisational conducts, and nursing homes are no exceptions to this.

The movement of immigrants from diverse backgrounds into the UK has rapidly increased (Johnson,2003). According to Knippenberg et al, (2004) immigrants mostly occupy low-paid jobs with its female population, largely constituting the associated healthcare workforce. Furthermore, there has been a steady increase in the use of nursing homes by Blacks, Asians, and minority ethnic groups (BAME) (Smith et al., 2007, 2008). As a result, nursing homes that are not diverse would probably find it difficult to adopt the required policies, practices, and service delivery systems to properly carter for minority residents (Betancourt et al, 2003).

There are experiences of racial discrimination based on race/ethnicity in migrant than non-immigrants health care workers (Harrison et al, 2007). According to Patrick (2010), and Simlin (2006), bureaucracies still exist in healthcare systems, and they become worse when clusters of workers from the same country work within a service. This is even more reason why undertaking leadership initiatives that reflect these crucial aspects of ethnicity where balance and the need to keep monitoring same concerning the management of nursing homes is critical (Richard, 2000; Cox, 2001; Hubbard 2004). Similarly, as previously stated, using experienced recruiters and materials that include diverse individuals and lastly communicating the importance of the value of diversity to all applicants to maintain a positive atmosphere among recruits is necessary (Arthur & Doverspike 2005).

From the above narratives, it could be deduced that these work-related diverse experiences within the health and social care sector may not be isolated management practices, but prevailing. It implies exploitation of differences at the expense and/or detriment of the weaker or disadvantageous positions or workers those at the lower end of the workplaces: these may be, for example, through the policies of offering gifts, promoting friendship affiliations within the workplace set up, etc., all of which may appear to suggest elements of the prevalence of

favouritism, manipulative or exploitation of workers using personal tools. All of these may be against the spirit of Equal opportunity legislation, which promotes the fact all workers be given or seen to be given equal chances and/or opportunities regardless of race, gender, disability, sexual orientation, religion, etc. Thus, better understanding the phenomenon of diversity in general but more particularly workplace diversity becomes even more imperative.

4.1.8 PT1Q6 Your highest Educational Qualification?

Figure 4. 6: Qualification

From the total of 248 employees that made-up front-line staff, 75 (or 30.2%) had associate degrees compared to 61 (or 24.5 %) who had attended some college. A total of 68 staff (or 27.4%) had bachelor's degree while 34 (or 13.7%) had master's and 17 (or 6.8 %) had high school certificates. The highest number of managers had some college degree 24 (or 30.3%) followed by 21 (or 26.5%) associate degree holders. A total of 19 (or %) had bachelor's while 8 (or 10.1%) and 7 (or 8.8%) had master's or high school certificates. It can be observed that the most educated did not top of the managerial positions while those with some college or associate degree made up the bulk of the employees in both managerial and frontline positions.

Similarly, as above, in any given situation, unless otherwise specifically stated, compliance with the Equality Act (2010, as amended), would be critical and useful. This is because, it is the overall legislation that covers a wide spectrum of diversity and workforce diversity management practices and organisational conducts, and nursing homes are no exceptions to this. Equally important to note, in the UK, organisations cannot discriminate

because of age, race, gender, disability, sexuality or sexual orientation, etc., except otherwise explicitly stated. In other words, whilst appreciating the importance of paper quantification, the spirit of the equality and diversity legislation points vehemently to the recognition of the use of all pertinent skills and experiences of all relevant variables, and not just a paper qualification, age group, race, or gender, etc. when it comes to dealing with issues of diversity/workplace diversity performances and productivity.

4.1.9 PT1Q7 Do you consider yourself disabled?

Figure 4.7: Disability

As noted in Figure 9 above, only a very few percentages of employees responded yes to the disability question i.e., 16 (or 6.4%) of frontline staff as compared to 2 (or 2.5%) of managers.

From a total of 248 frontline employees 230 (or 92.7 %) had no disability while 76 (96.2%).

Two frontline staff compared to one manager preferred not to sa.

As already noted above, according to literature evidence, cross-cultural training addresses the differences in cultures, and to do this training is the best method to reduce intercultural conflict (Naumann, 1992; Friedlander & Walton 2000). Also, as previously stated, compliance with the Equality Act (2010, as amended), is paramount and would be useful. This is because it is the overall legislation that covers a wide spectrum of diversity and workforce diversity management practices and organisational conducts, and nursing homes are no exceptions to this.

Besides, undertaking leadership initiatives that reflect these crucial aspects of ethnicity balance and the need to keep monitoring the same concerning the management of nursing homes is critical (Richard, 2000; Cox, 2001;

Hubbard 2004). Similarly, using experienced recruiters and materials that include diverse individuals and lastly communicating the importance of the value of diversity to all applicants to maintain a positive atmosphere among recruits is necessary (Arthur & Doverspike 2005).

4.1.10 PT1Q8 My organisation is an Equal Opportunity Promoter.

Responses as follow: Strongly disagree 34; Disagree 23; Neither agree nor disagree 24; Agree 77; Strongly agree 90:

Figure 4. 8: My Organisation as Equal Opportunity Promoter

As seen above, figure 10 relates to the question PT1Q8 relating to the researcher’s quantitative field survey data. It reflects that there was a total of 248 respondents to the question from among the participants, out of the total of 500 questionnaires that were administered. 90 respondents (or 36.2 %) strongly agreed and (or 31 %) agreed with the statement; ‘My organisation is an equal opportunities promoter and as such it recruits workers from all backgrounds regardless of their race, religion, gender, disability, sexual orientation while those who disagree were (or 9.2 %), (or 13.7 %) strongly disagree but the rest (or 9.6 %) neither agree nor disagree. This means this group of respondents to this statement constitutes and reflects quite a wide diversity of opinion, which needs deeper comprehension.

These statistics suggest that based on this quantitative response data, 67.2% of managers and frontline workers of Middlesex nursing homes believe that ‘their nursing homes in which they work are or can be deemed equal opportunities promoters. Importantly, this is because, they are perceived as if they do comply with the current

legislation and as such, they recruit workers from all backgrounds regardless of their race, religion, gender, disability, sexual orientation, etc. as far as practically possible.

To this, there is numerous empirical evidence: the idea that employers tend to promote favouritism based on individuals or people they know or look like them are well documented over the years (Avery, 1979; Bernmardin & Beatly, 1984; Brewer & Kramer, 1985; Cascio, 1982; Tisui-Egan & O'Reilly, 1992, Wexley & Nemeroff, 1974). However, according to current UK legislation covering diversity and equality issues sees such practices as favouritism as against the spirit of the Act of Parliament. According to the Equality Act of 2010 (as amended), it is discriminatory and offensive to recruit and/or treat employees based on race, gender, religion, sexual orientation, disability, etc., unless it is specifically exempted for the same purpose. Equally, there is also evidence of scholarship on this subject of promoting equal opportunity. This covers nursing homes, as well as the broader health and social care industry, including the NHS. As already stated, it is unlawful to discriminate against or exclude persons based on race (and ethnicity), religion, gender, age, disability, sexual orientation, etc. In support of this scholars have argued, it would boost performance if employers adopted inclusive or participative, involving, and engaging approaches rather than exclusive approaches (Armstrong, 2012; Dunnette & Motowidlo, 1992; Hymowitz, 1989; Rosener, 1986; Schwartze, 1989). So, there, once again, there seemed to be a linkage between quantitative data outcome and literature evidence.

4.1.11 PT1Q9 A workforce diversity would have a more positive influence on performance than a negative influence.

Figure 4.9: A Diverse Workforce

As seen above, figure 4.9 relates to the question PT1Q9 relating to the researcher's quantitative field survey data. It showed that there was a total of 178 respondents to the question from among the participants, out of the total of 500 questionnaires that were administered.

Of the 178 polls, 38 (or 20%) strongly agreed, and 45 (or 54%) agreed with the statement; 'workforce diversity would have a more positive influence on performance than negative influence'; while those who disagree were 22 (or 13%), 19 (or 11%) strongly disagree but the rest 54 (or 31 %) neither agree nor disagree. This means this group of respondents to this statement constitutes and reflects quite a wide diversity of opinion, which needs deeper comprehension.

It reveals the prevalence of issues relating to diversity and equality in the nursing home sector. As such, from an inclusivity perspective, the implications of these may be quite sensitive in terms of diversity management policy determination, policy formulation, and implementation. This clear division on opposite lines might have to be sensitised for the best interest of the organisation from a corporate policy perspective, as well as diversity and equality points of view. To this, the phenomenon of inclusivity and equal opportunity are relevant as policy determinant factors when considering policy formulation and policy implementation process, whilst attempting to balance the equation of the workforce diversity management continuum within the nursing homes sector of the health and social care industry. According to the principles of both "inclusivity" (Eguruze, 2016:135) and/or "Collaborative working together (Eguruze, 2017: 156), or "team-working" (Beardwell and Claydon,2017:10), ultimately there are practical benefits when there are inclusiveness and team spirit or collaboration amongst people within organizations. Less teamwork and less collaboration may be counterproductive. Importantly, the idea of "team-working" may be deemed a "best practice" (Beardwell and Claydon,2017:10; Armstrong, 2006, 2009, 2012).

As previously stated, the idea that some employers tend to promote favouritism based on individuals or people they know or look like them are well documented over the years (Avery, 1979; Bernmardin & Beatly, 1984; Brewer & Kramer, 1985; Cascio, 1982; Tisui- Egan & O'Reilly, 1992, Wexley & Nemeroff, 1974). These practices may be counterproductive. However, the law relating to diversity and equality in the UK that covers these issues, including employment contexts in nursing homes is the Equality Act of 2010 (as amended). It states it is unlawful to discriminate against or exclude persons based on race (and ethnicity), region, gender, age, disability, sexual orientation, etc. So, nursing homes should be mindful of these legislations that are fundamentally critical to their work settings. In support of this scholars have argued, it would boost performance if employers adopted inclusive or participative, involving, and engaging approaches rather than exclusive

approaches (Armstrong, 2012; Dunnette & Motowidlo, 1992; Hymowitz, 1989; Rosener, 1986; Schwartze, 1989).

Yet others argue that a diverse staff is crucial to competitive advantage and critical in workplace culture as a source of strength (Cook,2017). When people’s efforts are not recognised or appreciated at work, they feel rejected or unengaged. They are not promoted to the next level. They feel deprived and isolated or excluded which could be dehumanising. This may mean their fundamental human rights are taken away from them, they would continue to feel dehumanised, demoralised. It would be a breach of their fundamental human rights to be treated less humanly or rejected from freely associating with other people and achieving to their best of their abilities. The welfare and wellbeing of people are paramount (UNDHR, 1948).

4.1.12 PT1Q10: Diversity training is part of the organisation’s mandatory training.

Figure 4. 10: Diversity Training

As noted above, figure 4.10 relates to the question PT1Q10 relating to the researcher’s quantitative field survey data. It shows that there was a total of 142 respondents to the question from among the participants, out of the total of 500 questionnaires that were administered.

Based on the total of 142 polls, 11 (or 8 %) strongly agreed and 23(or 16%) agreed with the statement; ‘Diversity training is part of the organisation’s mandatory training’; while those who disagree were 40 (or 28%), 34(or 24%) strongly disagree but the rest 34 (or 24 %) neither agree nor disagree. Again, it implies this group of respondents to this statement constitutes and reflects quite a wide diversity of opinion, in the disfavour of training which specifically focuses on diversity within UK nursing homes settings, which needs deeper comprehension, to enable us to understand the phenomenon better. Why are nursing homes either not encouraging diverse-focused training or not already practicing the same as it should be per the legislation such as the Equality Act 2010 as amended), or as provided by the equal opportunity policy statement requirement? There is a need to explore this further as to why it is critical to follow the Act of Parliament. And if not, should implementation of the law be invoked? And if it turns out nursing home settings are not in compliance with the subsisting legislation, what should happen in terms of affirmative action or and/or breach of the law.

As such, based on these findings it can be suggested that more needs to be done, further research to specifically ascertain why diversity training is part of the organisation’s mandatory training ‘should be made part of nursing homes policy decision making processes.

As briefly stated previously, the principles of training and self-development the idea of diversity training at workplace settings have been robustly promoted or advocated by several scholars; crucially it had been seen to be a “best practice” (Bardwell and Claydon,2017:10; Armstrong, 2006, 2009, 2012). Ultimately training may lead to self-development and in turn may lead to increased individual performances self-motivational levels or improve self-actualisation and drive which may, in turn, impact organizational performance (Maslow, 1943, 1954, 1970; Training has also been valued as a useful, pertinent, and supportive tool towards workers, as other studies also suggest(McGregor, 1960; Herzberg, 1968).

4.1.13 PT1Q 11 Prospective employees are interviewed by a diverse team.

Figure 4. 11: Research’s Field Survey

As noted above, figure 4.11 relates to the question PT1Q11 relating to the researcher’s quantitative field survey data. It shows that there was a total of 172 respondents to the question from among the participants, out of the total of 500 questionnaires that were administered.

Based on the total of 172 polls, 43 (or 26 %) strongly agreed, and 40 or (23%) agreed with the statement; ‘prospective employees are interviewed by a diverse team’; while those who disagree were 28 (or 16%), 23(or 13%) strongly disagree but the rest 38 (or 22 %) neither agree nor disagree. Again, it implies this group of respondents to this statement constitutes and reflects quite a wide diversity of opinion, which is 49% as opposed to those disagreeing about 29%, whilst 22% neither remains neutral. So, this is in disfavour of the nursing homes practicing the requirement, notion, or perception that it is better for prospective employees being interviewed by a diverse team, which is in line with the spirit of UK legislature, such as the Equality Act 2010 as amended, which covers nursing homes settings, as much as other institutions, which needs deeper comprehension, to enable us to understand the phenomenon better.

From the mentoring perspective in the selection of an employee, the selection process may be biased or influenced by a discriminatory attitude and behaviour of an interviewer with either racial or gender bias tendencies, which might encourage them to select preferably a white instead of a woman or person of ethnicity or colour (Fitt and Newton, 1989; Blackburn, Chapman and Cameron 1981; Bowers, 1984;). This is because the major consideration when selecting a candidate for employment purposes is personal closeness, patronage, relationship, in fact, corruption, etc. So, if the interviewer considers or perceives the interviewee as a personal relation, he or she is more likely to be considered than others without such close affinity (Fitt and Newton, 1989; Blackburn, Chapman, and Cameron 1981; Bowers, 1984).

4.1.14 PT1Q12 Mentoring programs are offered to all employees in the organization.

Figure 4. 12: Research’s Field Survey

As indicated above, figure 4.12 relates to the question PT1Q12 relating to the researcher’s quantitative field survey data. It points to the fact that there was a total of 91 respondents to the question from among the participants, out of the total of 500 questionnaires that were administered.

Based on the total of 91 polls, 11(or 12%) strongly agreed and 21(or 23%) agreed with the statement; ‘mentoring programmes are offered to all employees in the organisation’; while those who disagree were 16(or 18%), 10(or 11%) strongly disagree but the rest 33 (or 36 %) neither agree nor disagree. Again, it implies this group of respondents to this statement constitutes and reflects quite a wide diversity of opinion, which 35% agreeing as opposed to those is disagreeing about 29%, whilst 23% neither agree nor disagree. So, this is quite evenly spread of belief that nursing homes are offering mentoring opportunities to their employees. Although this belief and practice seem evenly spread, at the same time, it does not appear to be a widely adopted practice amongst nursing home settings, according to the data. It would be important to know more as to why the practice is not popular.

As already stated, mentors are said to be higher ranking, experienced, knowledgeable, top-level, influential, and senior members of organisations who guide and groom junior workers through their career progression, who are predominantly whites (Collins, 1983; Kram, 1985; Roches, 1979). Given that women and people from ethnic minorities are already disproportionately represented or numerically rare at the top-level management positions, they may be a bigger risk to sponsor by a mentor, or less likely to get mentorship. Lack of mentors and role models are barriers for many women and ethnic minorities. Mentors are extremely important for women and people of an ethnic minority, especially since they need experience of mentors to nurture them, the guidance,

encouragement, and advocacy that mentors can provide to overcome such obstacles as isolation, lack of credibility, and lack of political savvy (patronage) (Jeruchin and Shapiro, 1992; Morrison, 1992).

Not having a mentor who is trustworthy and knowledgeable about career mobility is a factor that further contributes to the problem of unwise career decisions (choices) (Morrison, 1992). An inclusive diversity approach is most preferable, and this may include programmes such as equal opportunity in the process of recruiting and training (Armstrong, 2006, 2009, 2012).

4.1.15 PT1Q13 I think women are better performers than men in the context of nursing home care provisions.

Figure 4. 13: Research's Field Survey

As seen above, figure 4.13 relates to the question PT1Q13 concerning the researcher's quantitative field survey data. It confirms there were a total of 163 respondents to the question from among the participants, out of the total of 500 questionnaires that were administered.

Based on the total of 163 polls, 40 (or 25%) strongly agreed, and 45 (or 28%) agreed with the statement; 'I think women are better performers than men in the context of nursing home care provisions'; while those who disagree were 23 (or 14%), 33 (or 20%) strongly disagree but the rest 22 (or 13%) neither agree nor disagree.

Again, it implies this group of respondents to this statement constitutes and reflects quite a wide diversity of opinion, in which 53 % agreeing as opposed to those disagreeing with 34%, whilst 2% neither remains neutral. This is a significant majority agreeing and a sizable proportion disagreeing. This means this depicts critical

gender diversity issues within the UK nursing home setting. It also means that the nursing work setting is a potential assured place for more prospective female job applicants for those who might want to work in the health and social industry. It also means female workers are more likely to be considered than their male counterparts in terms of recruitment opportunities. It is also a sensitive subject that will need careful management skills.

However, it should be remarked that the potential legal implications as these facts need to be managed within the spirit of the Equality Act legislation of 2020 (as amended) which states employees or peoples should not be discriminated against due to differences in race, religion, disability, gender, sexual orientation, etc. It would be important to know more as to why the practice is not popular. An inclusive diversity approach is most preferable, and this may include programmes such as equal opportunities that offer opportunities to all in the process of recruiting and training will be critical (Armstrong, 2006, 2009, 2012). In contrast, other scholars have also advocated for an inclusive approach such as training and development programmes for all employees using the best practice approaches: recruiting, selecting, and training, etc. (D. Netto, 1994; D’Netto and Sohal, 1999).

4.1.16 PT1Q14 I feel included when I am part of the decision-making process in my organisation.

Figure 4. 14: Research’s Field Survey

As seen above, figure 16 relates to the question PT1Q14 in connection with the researcher’s quantitative field survey data. There was a total of 169 respondents to the question from among the participants, out of the total of 500 questionnaires that were administered.

Based on the total of 169 polls, 18 (or 11%) strongly agreed, and 20 (or 12%) agreed with the statement; *‘I feel included when I am part of the decision-making process in my organisation’*; while those who disagree were 54 (or 32%), 34(or 20%) strongly disagree but the rest 43 (or 25%) neither agree nor disagree. Again, it implies this

group of respondents who agree to this statement constitutes and reflects quite a wide diversity of opinion, in which 23% agreeing as opposed to those who disagreeing were a significant of 52%, which more than double those who agree, whilst 20% remained neutral. This points to a remarkable majority of managers and management assistants that feel it might be unpopular to conceive of the view to want to engage every nursing employee to be part of a policy decision making process. It may mean a dream which may appear far more to come true, according to the quantitative response data. Although, on the other hand, the feeling of belonging or lack of it might an emerging phenomenon that can become a threat to the management of the nursing home setting, if this perspective is being ignored or unresolved, as per the quantitative response data.

Having said that, exploring the relevant documentary evidence, scholars such as Maslow Hierarchy of Needs model as outlined in the study of motivation and personality study, have indicated that if employees' sense of feeling of belonging needs is not addressed, then, they (employees) are less likely to achieve to the best of their potential (Maslow, 1943, 1954, 1970). Maslow's learning outcome was supported by other studies; McGregor (1960), whose study in his Theory X and Y in the Human Side of Enterprise project equally exerted a profound impact on the learning of employment or leadership practices that may positively or negatively influence workplace setting such as nursing homes. It pointed out that according to theory X management employees may dislike work, have little ambition, and are unwilling to take responsibility. On the other hand, in contrast, theory Y management or leaders may perceive employees perform and produce exceedingly more than expected, if they are indeed supported and motivated and, in this case, if nursing employees are included in policy formulation and implementation processes (McGregor, 1960). Engaging employees actively may be a more practical approach. It is critical to know more as to why the practice is not popular within the nursing home setting in the UK.

4.1.17 PT1Q15 My performance increases when I work in a diverse team.

Figure 4. 15: My performance increases when I work in a diverse team

As seen above, figure 4.15 relates to the question PT1Q15. It reflects that there was a total of 149 respondents to the question from among the participants, out of the total of five hundred questionnaires that were administered. Of the 149 polls, 33 (or 22 %) agreed or 29 (or 19 %) strongly agreed with the statement; ‘*my performance increases when I work in an adverse team*’; while those who disagree were 18 (or 12%), 19(or 13 %) disagree but the rest 50 (or 34 %) neither agree nor disagree. This means this group of respondents to this statement constitutes and reflects quite a wide diversity of opinion, which needs deeper comprehension.

As such from an inclusivity perspective, the implications of these may be quite sensitive in terms of diversity management policy determination, policy formulation, and implementation. This clear division on opposite lines might have to be sensitised for the best interest of the organisation from a corporate policy perspective, as well as diversity and equality points of view. To this, the phenomenon of inclusivity and equal opportunity are relevant as policy determinant factors when considering policy formulation and policy implementation process, whilst attempting to balance the equation of the workforce diversity management continuum within the nursing homes sector of the health and social care.

This outcome highlights the importance of team spirit. According to the concept of teamwork, Similarly, according to the phenomenon of a diverse workforce it is about acknowledging, encouraging, recognising, and nurturing and connecting, appreciating, and reinforcing every skill structure within the entire workforce that

exists within the nursing homework environment (D, Neto, and Sohal, 1999; Armstrong, 2006, 2009, 2012). It helps reinvigorate and reassure individual skills, experiences, and knowledge because as people we are all very different and diverse (D, Neto and Sohal, 1999). This is what matters under the philosophy. It is imperative for people to work as a team to drive the best and synergy outcome (D, Neto, and Sohal, 1999; Armstrong, 2006, 2009, 2012), thereby maximising their productivity and performance based on the collectiveness of inputs (Elmutti, 1993). To this several scholars added their respective opinions which are based on their different studies over the years.

4.1.18 PT1Q16 My performance increases when I am on a Flexible working contract.

Figure 4. 16: My performance increases when I am on a Flexible Working Contract

As seen above, figure 4.16 relates to the question PT1Q16. It reflects that there was a total of 157 respondents to the question from among the participants, out of the total of 500 questionnaires that were administered. Based on the 149 polls, 15 (or 10 %) agreed or 12 (or 7 %) strongly agreed with the statement; ‘*my performance increases when I am on a flexible working contract*’; while those who disagree were 41 (or 26%), 44(or 28%) strongly disagree but the rest 45 (or 29%) neither agree nor disagree. Again, this means this group of respondents gave support to this statement which constitutes and reflects quite a significant majority of opinion, which is in favour of the practice that suggests an employee is more likely to do better in a nursing home that promotes or allows flexible working environment.

It suggests flexible working culture might boost an employee's performance potentiality. Based on this outcome it can be argued that it is important to consider flexible working culture within the nursing home setting

As such from an inclusivity perspective, the implications of these may be quite sensitive in terms of diversity management policy determination, policy formulation, and implementation. This clear division on opposite lines

might have to be sensitised for the best interest of the organisation from a corporate policy perspective, as well as diversity and equality points of view. To this, the phenomenon of inclusivity and equal opportunity are relevant as policy determinant factors when considering policy formulation and policy implementation process, whilst attempting to balance the equation of the workforce diversity management continuum.

Similarly, as previously accounted, according to the phenomenon of a diverse workforce it is about acknowledging, encouraging, recognising, and nurturing, and connecting, appreciating, and reinforcing every skills structure within the entire workforce that exists within the nursing homework environmental setting (D, Neto and Sohal, 1999; Armstrong, 2006, 2009, 2012). It helps reinvigorate and highlight the fact that understanding individual employees' needs and circumstances is fundamentally critical to increasing performance and workplace productivity. Similarly, it draws management attention to the fact that individual employees understanding individual employees' needs or circumstances are different. And more so, if these differences and skills are recognised and attended to it may make a difference in performance and productivity, as employees are all very different and diverse, as flexibility is critical (Hall and Parker, 1993; Herzberg, 1968).

The literature documentary states as follows:

“...build flexibility into the policy; avoid favouritism and/or discrimination when applying or implementing policies to different employees; there needs to be great consistency and transparency in policy and action/practice” (Equality Act 2010, as amended).

It might be very difficult to ignore employee-facing outside challenges and to avoid the interest of worker's welfare and wellbeing in conflict with a company's performance and productivity. Equally, it would make sense to be flexible with working hours and days off (Herzberg, 1968). From the results of the survey, it is important to accommodate employees' views and opinions at the workplace; as such suggestions may lead to an improvement in quality, performance, and productivity. This means there should be a need for adequate room for employees' requests/suggestions to be taken into consideration. It is important to appreciate that before the Covid 19 Pandemic, such ideas as working from home were developed only recently (Denny et al., 2020). This means new ways of work practices as working from home, as a work routine, and work format, which was not accepted, before Covid 19 pandemic has become an acceptable new way of work ethic in the post-Covid 19 era. It means being open to ideas and being flexible should be a sine qua non to organizational progress, better performance, and better productivity. Working from home has been hugely found to enhance better engagement, reduction in congestion and pollution, staff saving on commuting, and staff retention (Denny et al, 2020). Nevertheless, there is also the counterview that working from home permanently could create some burden on the mental and physical welfare, wellness, and wellbeing of people engaged in working from home (Denny et

al, 2020). What it implies is that there should be an adequate work-family balance, or balance of all different needs: physical, mental, and spiritual, etc.

4.1.19 PT1Q17 Cross-cultural training enhances my performance.

Figure 4. 17: Research’s Field Survey

As seen above, figure 4.19 relates to the question PT1Q17 in connection with the researcher’s quantitative field survey data. It suggests there were a total of 171 respondents to the question from among the participants, out of the total of 500 questionnaires that were administered.

Based on the total of 171 polls, 52 (or 31%) strongly agreed and 43(or 25%) agreed with the statement; ‘Cross-cultural training enhances my performance’; while those who disagree were 21(or 12%), 22(or 13%) strongly disagree but the rest 33(or 19%) neither agree nor disagree, which means they remain neutral. Again, it implies this group of respondents who agree to this statement constitutes and reflects quite a wide diversity of opinion, in which a significant majority, 56 % agreeing to the statement (that cross-cultural training enhances performance) as opposed to those disagreeing was a significantly less poll of 25%, which is more than double those who agree, whilst 19% remains neutral. This implies that nursing home managers who believe in this phenomenon and take a step to practice or implement it, are more likely to perform better than those nursing homes that do not apply such critical employee boosting and productivity facilitation tools. This points to the fact it may be a potentially popular practice, if adopted, according to the quantitative response data.

Although, on the other hand, the feeling of belonging or lack of it might be an emerging phenomenon that can become a threat to the management of nursing home settings, if this perspective is being ignored or unresolved, as per the quantitative response data.

Some scholars may argue training on diversity lines may lead to competitiveness and in fact, competitive advantages (Porter, 1985, 2008; Armstrong, 2012). Similarly, creating and providing opportunities for professional development, including training and development of employees is always a job-satisfier, according to Herzberg (1960;1968). Again, scholars such as Maslow Hierarchy of Needs model as outlined in the study of motivation and personality study, have indicated that if employees' sense of feeling of belonging needs is not addressed, then, they (employees) are less likely to achieve the best of their potential (Maslow, 1943, 1954, 1970).

Maslow's learning outcome was supported by other studies; McGregor (1960), whose study in his Theory X and Y in the Human Side of Enterprise project, equally exerted a profound impact on the learning of employment or leadership practices that may positively or negatively influence workplace setting such as nursing homes. It pointed out on one hand; according to theory X, management view may be that employees may dislike work, have little ambition, and are unwilling to take responsibility. On the other hand, in contrast, theory Y management leaders may perceive employees may perform and produce exceedingly more than expected if they are indeed supported and motivated. In this instance, it contributes to the necessity, of nursing employees to be included in policy formulation and implementation processes (McGregor, 1960). It is critical to know more as to why the practice is not popular within the nursing home setting in the UK. It is important to note that cross-cultural training addresses the differences in cultures, and to do this training is the best method to reduce intercultural conflict (Naumann, 1992; Friedlander & Walton 2000). Some scholars have pointed out the challenges and benefits of cultural diversity training (Grace, 1994). To comply with the Equality Act (2010, as amended), it is crucial as it is the overall legislation that covers a wide spectrum of diversity and workforce diversity management practices and organisational conducts, which was shown from the data represented above.

4.1.20 PT1Q18 I perform better when I am given a bonus.

Figure 4. 18: Research’s Field Survey Figure

As seen above, figure 4.18 relates to the question PT1Q18 in connection with the researcher’s quantitative field survey data. It suggests there were a total of 184 respondents to the question from among the participants, out of the total of 500 questionnaires that were administered.

Based on the total of 184 polls, 17 (or 9%) strongly agreed and 22 (or 12%) agreed with the statement; ‘I perform better when I am given a bonus’; while those who disagree were 33(or 18%), 45(or 25%) strongly disagree but the rest 67(or 36%) neither agree nor disagree, which means they remain neutral. Again, it implies this group of respondents who resonated with this statement constitutes and reflects quite a wide diversity of opinion, in which a significant majority, Which implies that nursing home managers who believe in this phenomenon – a bonus is given - and take a step to practice or implement it, are more likely to perform better than those nursing homes that do not apply such critical employee morale boosting and productivity facilitation tools.

But several scholars agree and disagree on this subject of how best to motivate employees or whether money itself is a motivator. Herzberg’s (1968) 2 factors motivation theory explains this confusion from opposing perspectives. He states that factors that lead to motivation/job satisfaction at workplace setting include recognition (of efforts praises, creativity, innovation, commitment), achievement (e.g., promotion, status), working conditions (creating an interesting work environment that everyone will love/respect/happy, supportive supervision), responsibility (delegation), growth (including providing opportunities for professional

development/training), etc. These are also referred to as intrinsic elements of the work. On the other hand, the extrinsic factors, Hygiene factors/Dissatisfaction, and frustration, include, salary (pay and benefits; honest salary), supervision, (supportive/effective), company policies, job security, relations with supervisors and with other employees, and status within the company, etc. (or extrinsic elements) relating to work.

4.1.21 PT1Q19 Career progression opportunities are offered to all employees regardless of their background.

Figure 4.

19: Research’s Field Survey

As seen above, figure 4.19 relates to the question PT1Q19 in connection with the researcher’s quantitative field survey data. It suggests there were a total of 184 respondents to the question from among the participants, out of the total of 500 questionnaires that were administered.

Based on the total of 151 polls, 20 (or 13%) strongly agreed and 14 (or 9%) disagreed with the statement; ‘*Career progression opportunities are offered to all employees regardless of their background*’; while those who agree were 30 (or 20%), 42 (or 28%) strongly agree but the rest 45 (or 30%) neither agree nor disagree, which means they remain neutral. Again, it implies this group of respondents who resonated with this statement constitutes and reflects quite a wide diversity of opinion, in which 30% agreeing to the statement (Career progression opportunities are offered to all employees regardless of their background) as opposed to those disagreeing were 14%, which is more than double those who agree, whilst 45% remains neutral. Which implies that nursing home managers who believe in this phenomenon – career progression opportunities- and take a step

to practice or implement it, are more likely to perform better than those nursing homes that do not apply such critical employee morale-boosting and productivity facilitation tools? This points to the fact it may be a potentially popular practice, if adopted, according to the quantitative response data.

4.1.22 PT1Q20 Employee absenteeism has a negative influence on performance.

Figure 4. 20: Research’s Field Survey

As seen above, figure 4.20 relates to the question PT1Q20 in connection with the researcher’s quantitative field survey data. It suggests there were a total of 150 respondents to the question from among the participants, out of the total of five hundred questionnaires that were administered.

Based on the total of 150 polls, 40 (or 27%) strongly agreed, and 44(or 29%) agreed with the statement; ‘Employee absenteeism has a negative influence on performance’; while those who disagree were 22 (or 15%), 12(or 8%) strongly disagree but the rest 32(or 21%) neither agree nor disagree, which means they remain neutral. Again, it implies this group of respondents who resonated with this statement constitutes and reflects quite a wide diversity of opinion, in which a significant majority, 56% agreeing to the statement (Employee absenteeism

has a negative influence on performance) as opposed to those disagreeing was remarkably less at 23% which is less than half! those who agree, whilst 32% remains neutral.

4.1.23 PT1Q21 Management offers flexible working contracts to employees when needed due to its many benefits

Figure 4. 21: Research’s Field Survey

As seen above, figure 4.21 relates to the question PT1Q21 in connection with the researcher’s quantitative field survey data. It suggests there were a total of 180 respondents to the question from among the participants, out of the total of 500 questionnaires that were administered.

Based on the total of 180 polls, 25(or 14%) strongly agreed and 19(or 10%) agreed with the statement; ‘*Management offers flexible working contracts to employees when needed due to its many benefits*’; while those who disagree were 33(or 18%), 48(or 27%) strongly disagree but the rest 55 (or 31%) neither agree nor disagree, which means they remain neutral. Again, it implies this group of respondents who resonated with this statement constitutes and reflects quite a wide diversity of opinion, in which a significant minority, 24% agreeing to the statement ‘*Management offers flexible working contracts to employees when needed due to its many benefits*’ as opposed to those disagreeing was the remarkable majority at 45% which is more than double those who agree, whilst 31% remains neutral. Which implies that nursing home managers who believe in this phenomenon – flexible working contracts - and take a step to practice or implement it, are more likely to perform better than

those nursing homes that do not apply such critical employee morale-boosting and productivity facilitation tools. This points to the fact it may be a potentially popular practice, if adopted, according to the quantitative response data.

As previously stated, according to literature evidence, work-life balance is about how individuals and managers employees, and employers may need to negotiate overwork and personal requirements to achieve mutual benefits at the workplace setting and/or avoid possible conflicts, or achieve mutual satisfaction (Bulger, Mathews Hoffman, 2007). According to several scholars, in the 21st- century working environment, working conditions and demands have been observed to have changed significantly mainly due to changes in technological, social, and economic, and other environmental factors, and therefore working patterns, (Russell, O’Connell and McGrinity, 2009; Armstrong, 2012). These are also backed by legislation (Joyce et al., 2010), such as the Equality Act for preventing discrimination based on the nine groups/categories of people. It has been shown also to help win competitive advantages (Storey,1995, Porter, 1985, 2008). This legislation covers policy and practices relating to discrimination. This suggests a relevant and positive link between quantitative data evidence and literature evidence.

4.1.24 PT1Q22 BAME in frontline roles have a degree compared to their white counterparts.

Figure 4.22: Ethnicity with bachelor’s degree

The analysis is the response to one of the research questions on the questionnaire and this was comparing educational qualification and ethnicity. Of the 98 respondents, 15 white British employees had a bachelor’s degree making up (15.3%). Those with a first degree from any other background constituted 23.4% (23) while

those from mix any other black background were 10.2% (10). The highest percentage of the employee with bachelor's degrees were from

Black/Caribbean backgrounds 30.6% (30) while Asians came second with 20.4% (20).

These statistics show that workers from an ethnic minority are relatively better educated. Despite that, they are placed in positions with fewer managerial responsibilities. They are placed more in the low paid frontline type of work within the health and care sector despite their qualification. This finding re-enforces several previous literature narratives that immigrants mostly occupy low paid jobs with its female population, largely constituting the associated healthcare workforce (Knippenberg et al, (2004). Additionally, it re-enforces, the literature which argues despite disproportionately low paid jobs, the health and social care work still attracts a steady increase in the use of nursing homes by Blacks, Asians, and minority ethnic groups (BAME) (Smith et al., 2007, 2008), as briefly stated earlier. This reflects employment practices that are based on racial discrimination based on race/ethnicity in migrant than non-immigrants health care workers (Harrison et al, 2007). Again, it may be breaking the law relating to discrimination within workplaces in the UK (Equality, Act, 2010, as amended). Thus, as other scholars suggested, there is a need to review their policies on diversity/workforce diversity practices (Betancourt et al, 2003; Simlin, 2006; Patrick, 2010). As previously stated, this is even more reason why undertaking leadership initiatives that reflect these crucial aspects of ethnicity where balance and the need to keep monitoring same concerning the management of nursing homes is critical (Richard, 2000; Cox, 2001; Hubbard 2004). Similarly, as previously stated, using experienced recruiters and materials that include diverse individuals and lastly communicating the importance of the value of diversity to all applicants to maintain a positive atmosphere among recruits is necessary (Arthur & Doverspike 2005).

4.1.25) Summary

As noted above, this was a very complex part of the research – the empirical part of it, which formed an important part of the study. The data relating to this originally had mixed data (a mixture of quantitative and qualitative data elements), hence, this chapter four was split into two parts. The purpose of it was to simplify the data analysis and to gain a better or more meaningful reading and clarity, as previously stated. Accordingly, in this part 1, the researcher only focused on the quantitative aspects of the data, which was based on the twenty-two item questionnaire variables. Based on the detailed analysis using these 22-item, the researcher believed there has been substantial evidence of linkages between the quantitative data and the literature evidence. There was important literature evidence supporting empirical data evidence, in specific relation to diversity and workforce diversity management practices as they impact employee performance.

Since the quantitative aspect of the data analysis has been completed, this researcher progresses to the next chapter, which will be qualitative data analysis and interpretation.

4.2) Qualitative Data analysis & Interpretations

4.2.1) Introduction

This section deals with qualitative analysis. Semi-structured interviews formed the method for the collection of data for this part of the research. From the nursing homes where the quantitative data was collected a random sample of ten participants were selected for the interviews. Interviews were conducted both in person and by telephone according to the preference of the participants. Although the sample size for the qualitative study was ten, only eight were finally interviewed. This was because two managers who initially agreed to take part in the study were on annual leave when the interviews were performed. Some interviews took place at their work settings (nursing homes) while others over the telephone. Before the interview, each participant was asked if they were happy for the interview to be recorded and once consent was gained, a place and time of meeting was pre-arranged. As interviewees had consented, the interviews were taped recorded, and/or were transcribed. Some of the participants declined recorded interviews but agreed that notes could be taken during the interview.

4.2.2) Coding (Appendix)

In this research, coding was applied to analyse the huge (empirical) data that was obtained from field interviews, into a meaningful state. Coding was described as a process in which huge text (data) that was obtained from the interviewees are categorised into common or similar themes, which are then coded (or labelled) with code/label names for easier analysis (Gibbs and Taylor, 2005; Strauss et al., 1990). But elsewhere the definition states

“...coding is the process of combining data for themes and categories and then marking similar passages of text with a code label so that they can easily be retrieved later for comparisons and analysis” (Eguruze, 2016:111).

Accordingly, in this research, the researcher uses codes based on keywords or concepts from the texts(data) obtained. These were decoded. Decoded transcripts were coded for common themes and themes assessed for main ideas about diversity management. Comparisons of the coded information enabled the researcher to achieve a greater understanding of how diversity management influences performance in nursing homes. A thematic analysis was undertaken, and results grouped following the research questions:

- Does ethnic diversity influence performance?
- What impact does a diverse gender workforce (males and females) have on performance in nursing homes?
- What is the impact of different age groups on nursing home employee performance?

- Do flexible working hours influence employee performance in nursing homes?
- How does cross-cultural training affect the employee performance of employees in nursing homes?
- Do you think motivational schemes enhance employee performance?

From the analysis of these questions, the following coding/themes were formulated. The themes from the coding/labels are highlighted, analysed, and interpreted below as follow:

- 01 Multicultural team performance (diversity & equality).
- 02 Exclusion & Inclusion
- 03 Demography quality sex
- 04 Demographic uniqueness mature
- 05 Work and domestic-life balance
- 06 Staff development
- 07 Encouraging hard work & discouraging absenteeism. Coding Appendix....

4.2.2.1) Multicultural team performance (diversity & equality)

Regarding the qualitative research data, the followings are some of the response's indirect quotes, which are taken from the minutes or transcripts of the qualitative research data (Appendix...) that emerged from the themes from managers and assistant managers that reflects the multicultural team performance (or diversity and equality).

Here are some specific responses from the interviewees to the question "How does ethnic diversity influence performance?" (This was in response to the prompt question: - "How would you enhance performance within the diverse ethnic workforce in your organization?") There were varying responses to this question with most of them indicating a positive relationship with employee performance.

The first Respondent stated that: -

"I believe that cultural diversity has an immense impact on team performance, and it is important for teams to be multicultural." Also, "I think that simply understanding others is no longer enough for either of us as

managers or employees. Working in a diverse society such as the UK I expect my employees to continue to interact with others from different background.

The 2nd Respondent said that: -

“I would say ethnic diversity can sometimes be difficult to manage. It takes time to learn how to work within a team of varying ethnicities. However, it is my duty as a manager to find methods to convert process loss such as communication problem and conflict to gain”.

The 3rd Respondent stated that: -

“I think the client base we are looking after is increasingly getting diverse therefore increase interaction leads to and enhancement in learning.”

The 4th Respondent stated that

“Well, as a manager, I speak openly and honestly about the importance of ethnic diversity and inclusion in my nursing home. Most often people are inspired by the vision, and they want a leader who appreciates the values that are important to them by speaking publicly about diversity issues, employees feel included thereby encouraged to produce better outcomes”.

And the 5th Respondent stated that

“We always make sure the diversity statement about what the organisation values, are provided to all employees. It is a formal document to current and future employees that the organisation will put all forms of anti-discriminatory practices in place and work to foster equal opportunity for all.” Also, “some of the nursing homes are encouraging ethnic diversity through their practices to encourage workers from different ethnicities to work together toward better outcomes”. Moreover, managers state that they are “making an effort to recruit and work with a diverse force though evidence from descriptive studies shows the highest ethnic diversity in frontline roles”. As a result, “the nursing home industry still has a long way to go with regards to incorporating diverse ethnic force at all levels of nursing care, although there is general acceptance diversity positively influences performance.”

According to scholars, the idea that employers tend to promote favouritism based on individuals or people they know or look like them are well documented over the years (Avery, 1979; Bernmardin & Beatly, 1984; Brewer & Kramer, 1985; Cascio, 1982; Tisui-Egan & O’Reilly, 1992, Wexley & Nemeroff, 1974). However, the law

relating to diversity and equality in the UK that covers these issues, including employment contexts in nursing homes is the Equality Act of 2010(as amended). In support of this scholars have argued, it would boost performance if employers adopted inclusive or participative, involving an engaging approach rather than an exclusive approach (Armstrong, 2012; Dunnette & Motowidlo, 1992; Hymowitz, 1989; Rosener, 1986; Schwartze, 1989). Most importantly, the concept of workforce diversity and/or diversity management practices that are good for promoting organisational performance have been noted over time (Yang and Konrad, 2011; 2016; Armstrong, 2012; Roberg et al., 2011). Some scholars have also promoted the business case for promoting diverse workforce management for better performance outcomes (Herring, 2009; Niederle et al., 2013). This legislation covers policy and practices relating to discrimination in workplace settings. These suggest there are links between adopting diversity management practices and the propensity for enhanced organisational performance.

In fact, as with other organisations, nursing homes are obliged to ensure there is equality in the workplace environment as far as practicable. Crucially, it is important to show they are making that critical difference to avoid discrimination under the equality law (Equality Act 2010, as amended).

Does ethnic diversity influence performance? This study has shown that ethnic diversity is important for employee performance. In a highly multi-ethnic society like the UK, different ethnicities are found in all organisations. In nursing homes, cultural differences could impact care delivery; therefore, the development of culturally sensitive programs can bridge the gap and positively impact care. Ethnic diversity does not only help boost the firm's competitive advantage over organisations with a more ethnically homogenous workforce but increases employee satisfaction, which most often increases positive outcomes.

4.2.2.2) Demographic quality (sex)

Again, as above, from the massive collection of qualitative response data (Appendix...), only a few were selected for analysis. These were part of the coding obtained from the responses to this specific question. What impact does a diverse gender workforce (males and females) have on performance in nursing homes? (This was obtained from the Prompt question: - Do you think a diverse gender workforce encourages performance)

According to the responses made by the managers regarding gender and performance as well as initial analysis from the quantitative study, gender diversity within this sector is one of the most important constructs that impact positively on employee performance in the nursing home workforce. Respondents state the following:

In the context of the demographic mix, more specifically, male and female diversity,

1st respondent said that: -

“Yes, I think gender diversity at all levels is important. When the workforce reflects the demography of the patient population, it caters for, I am an important part of the organisation. I strongly believe that if a manager has little in common with an employee, they cannot adequately advocate for them. So, I think that equal distribution of males and females within this workforce would enhance proper patient care. A more gender-sensitive environment is encouraged, which might promote an open culture among employees.”

From the 2nd Respondent stated that: -

“I think gender diversity is important and having female leaders in nursing homes can lead to higher engagement and better retention of a more diverse workforce.”

Besides, the 3rd Respondent stated that: -

“Women have great analytical skills and coordinate activities with much better ease than men while upholding company values and strategies”

The 4th Respondent stated that: -

“In my experience, women tend to score higher on aspects of social sensitivity than men do, and I think good team performance is linked with social sensitivity factor within the team, especially in a nursing care field”.

In contrast, the 5th Respondent stated that

“Diversity exists when people from diverse backgrounds who do not think as you work together. Although hiring women at all levels of the organisation is important, it is good to recruit competent women, especially in management positions else diversity will only be on paper and would be meaningless.”

And equally, from the 6th Respondent that

“A mix of gender diversity within teams is good for business. But organisations dominated by women should have women at all levels of the organisation because this is good for building meaningful relationships and creating successful work processes.”

In supporting this respondents' view (s), as well as in responding to the specific question; How does gender diversity impact employee performance? several literature pieces of evidence have been noted as follows. Melhem (2007) also found that women in public universities outperform their male counterparts even when they entered with lower grades. Additionally, George (2008) who studied nurses, carers, and community workers

stated that female employees struggle to be recognised as skilled workers. He also pointed out that female carers face difficulties that question the legitimacy of their work. Evidence from these studies also highlights the opinions of employees around gender issues and it is important to state that frontline female workers compensate for the shortcomings of the health system and most of them do this to the detriment of their families, health, and livelihood. Ignoring the collective concerns around gender, health systems will continue to function in a skewed manner, replicating inequalities within its system.

4.2.2.3) Demography uniqueness mature

Age was one of the demographic features that were investigated. The questions asked during the interview were as follows: What is the impact of different age groups on nursing home employee performance? (Prompt: Does employing older workers influence performance? Do you think employing younger workers encourage performance)? The respondents stated that:

Respondent 1 said that:

“I think older workers are sometimes not physically strong as the job sometimes needs lifting”. Younger employees, still have the physical strength but can be often distracted.

Respondent 2 said that: -

“I think old and young workers have different capabilities”. Also, “... older employee has been around for a while and can be more experienced than younger ones.”

Respondent 3 stated that: -

“In care homes, the more someone gets older the more difficult to do some tasks assigned to them”.

Respondent 4 said that: -

“I think older workers can transfer knowledge and experience so in a way I think this can enhance performance.”

Respondent 5 said that: -

“Yes, I think if an older worker can no longer perform in roles that require physical strength, they can be redeployed to other areas of less manual handling and physical task. If that happens productivity can be improved.” “Young people possess skill different from older especially when it comes to technology, as a result, there might be a difference in performance.”

Respondent 6 said that: -

“In my experience as a manager, there is a percentage of people in both categories who will not perform adequately”. “I think it is important to understand this than to make general conclusions on an age group.”

These findings from the qualitative data also supported the findings from the quantitative data. Referring to the quantitative data, it showed that managers and frontline staff between the ages 28-37 (or 38%) were the majority, closely followed by those within the ages of 18-27 (or 28%). Those aged 58 years of age and over were the least represented and employees between the ages of 38-47yrs made up the third largest of the total surveyed population (22.6%). The hypothesis results showed no relation between age and employee performance in nursing homes, although there is unequivocal evidence that suggests a link between age and employee performance. Forth et al (2020) also found a weak relationship associated with longitudinal studies they carried out among some employees in the UK. These researchers measured Workplace performance according to managers’ assessments of workplace labour productivity, quality of product or service, and financial performance. Researchers like Cleveland and Lim (2007) aimed at investigating conditions whereby positive and negative may dominate and based on their model they argue that the exact shape of the costs and benefits curves depends on what type of skills, production process, or business task an organization is characterized by. Although their results, were conflicting they stated that age heterogeneity could be applicable depending on the task performed. Nevertheless, it points to some links between literature and qualitative data as well as quantitative data.

4.2.2.4) Work and domestic-life balance (Flexible working patterns, hours, and contract)

As above, the followings are some of the direct quotes that fitted the coding theme of work and domestic-life balance (flexible working patterns, hours, and contracts). As with the previous ones, these themes were derived from the specific responses from some of the interviewees in direct response to the following questions. Do flexible working hours influence employee performance in nursing homes?

About the flexible working patterns,

The 1st Respondent stated that: -

“I think flexible working practices can enhance employee motivation and engagement because employees can benefit from the improved work-life balance as well as taking care of their health and wellbeing”.

In contrast, the 2nd Respondent states that: -

“With a flexible working arrangement, I think employees are made to believe that their employers recognise that individuals are different with needs both outside and inside work”. Again, “one of my employees has a special need child so offering a flexible working contract enables her to look after her daughter outside school

hours, and I believe this has improved her performance as she is aware the managers acknowledge her out of work responsibilities”.

Whereas, the 3rd Respondent said that: -

“Yes, I think most workers are likely to require flexible working hours at some point in their working career.”

Again, *“One of my employees stated that I basically work all the time but flexibly so I can pick up my kids and deal with the holiday onset times of the year which is very important for my family and me.”*

According to the 4th Respondent that: -

“My organisation offers part-time hours, annualised hours, or compressed hours. This is beneficial for both the organisation and the employee. However, at recruitment, the employee must state the type of contract they are willing to sign.”

According to the 5th Respondent that: -

“Yes, I think flexible working arrangements are beneficial to this nursing home because employees who might have left as a result of fixed contracts have stayed and as a result, greater continuity” Also, *“flexibility reduces sickness and absences, which, as a result, would positively affect performance.”*

Respondent 6 said that: -

“Flexible working contracts give employees the chance to fit other commitments and activities around work and make better use of free time”.

According to literature evidence, work-life balance is about how individuals and managers employees, and employers may need to negotiate overwork and personal requirements to achieve mutual benefits at the workplace setting and/or avoid conflicts or achieve mutual satisfaction (Bulger, Mathews Hoffman, 2007). In the 21st century working environment, working conditions and demands have been observed to have changed significantly mainly due to changes in technological, social, and economic, and other environmental factors, and therefore working patterns, according to several scholars (Russell, O’Connell, and McGrinity, 2009; Armstrong, 2012).

4.2.2.5) Encouraging hard-work & discouraging absenteeism (motivational-schemes & employee performance)

As above, the following are some of the direct quotes from the coding theme encouraging hard-work & discouraging absenteeism (motivational-schemes & employee performance). As with the previous ones, these themes were derived from the specific responses from some of the interviewees in direct response to the following questions -Do you think motivational schemes enhance employee performance?

Concerning motivational schemes,

1st Respondents states that: -

“I think, motivation encourages hard work and discourages absenteeism. When I motivate my employees, they help the organisation to grow. In this nursing home, I provide shopping vouchers to the best performed employee, and this is every month.”

Besides, the 2nd Respondent stated that: -

“Sometimes, it is difficult to know what motivates different staff because what motivates one staff might not be the same as another. To solve this problem, my nursing homes have financial and non-financial schemes, and employees are asked if they need for example an additional day off work because of good performance or money as a reward for a job well done.”

The 3rd Respondent said

“Yes, I do. However, in this nursing home, no specific motivational schemes are used. Instead, at the end of the year during the Christmas parties that the organisation arranges, employees are given gifts for performing well throughout the year. Employees are asked to bring their families along to the party, and this makes them feel happy and encouraged.”

The 4th Respondent stated that: -

“Unmotivated employees perform less. When I set goals; I provide an incentive which results in enhanced employee performance.”

In the context of this research, a range of studies has been carried out that support the fact that motivational schemes are positively impact on organisational performance. These may include both extrinsic (monetary) and/or intrinsic motivational aspects (non-financial) (Hertzberg, 1960; and it can be in a hierarchy format (Maslow, 1943, 1954, 1970). Some authors state that motivation is, a process of inspiring people to take a desired course of action or in other words, any act which inspires employees to work better or harder (Cole, 2004, 2005; Schein, 2010, Armstrong, 2012). According to Dailey and Kirk, (1992), Gupta, (1998) rewards could be in the form of cash or kind including social rewards. These motivational sources may even be resource based in that an enriched and well resource organisational diversity management practices may positively influence organisational progress (Barney and Clark, 2007), or institutionally based diverse managed practices, including organisational culture and organisational structure, may promote better performance (Lorbiecki & Jack, 2000).

4.2.2.6) Staff development and skills training on diversity characteristics (capacity building)

Similarly, as above, the followings are some of the direct quotes that have been categorized under the coding theme - Staff development and skills training on diversity characteristics (capacity building or cross-cultural training). As with the previous ones, these themes were derived from the specific responses from some of the interviewees in direct response to the following questions. This was in response to the Prompt question -How does cross-cultural training affect the employee performance of employees in nursing homes? The responses were as follows:

Regarding cross-cultural training, the 1st Respondents, stated that

“In a multinational society like the UK, I think cross-cultural training would make employees aware of their cultures.” But *“In this nursing home, there’s no specific training as such”*.

Similarly, the 2nd Respondents said that: -

“I have never heard about cross-cultural training, so I don’t know if it will have any influence on employee performance.”

In contrast, the 3rd Respondent, stated that: -

“We offer diversity training, which covers diversity characteristics.” But *“I have never come across any training course known as cross-cultural training.”* *“However, I can state that it might be useful as not only employees are from divergent backgrounds, but we have a wide client base that we serve. Therefore, training employees about differing cultures will go a long way to ease staff/staff interaction as well as staff/client interaction.”*

The 4th Respondent, simply stated that: -

“I don’t know.”

There have been many scholars that have argued in favour of cross-cultural training as a reliable source of boosting performance (Newman, 1992), or deemed as a strategy for enhancing performance (Desphante & Visweavaran, 1992). Also, other researchers point to the fact or suggests cross-cultural training has positive correlations with organisational performance under cross cultural circumstances (Adler, 19920). Similarly, cross-cultural training is observed to be a strong tool for organisations in the context of promoting cultural harmony or social integration or even used in addressing diversity, equality, and difference amongst workers in workplace settings (Newman, 1992). This may help in reducing intercultural conflicts (Newman, 1992). The business case for promoting or encouraging demanding work or reduces labour turnover, absenteeism, and/or

discrimination which are common problems of workplace setting have been advocated (Cox 1991; Morrison, 1992) So, once again there seem to be some links between literature evidence and qualitative response data.

4.2.2.7) Inclusivity & exclusion (Social exclusion, Isolation & Inclusion)

The above theme resulted from coding of responses to the question... Are there any diversity management practices that enhance performance in your team? Respondents to this question stated the following.

The first respondent said that:

“To be fair, I think some employees in my organisations achieve its strategic goals and objectives and when this happens, they are recognised and rewarded”.

The second respondent said that: -

“I think employees respect and value each other’s opinions”.

The third responded said that: -

“Some employees feel worried when expressing their true feelings... I think my opinion might not be considered but through communication I think they will be building a rapport with colleagues so I will be confident to be open and honest”.

The fourth respondent said that: -

“I think as a manager I should consider my management style approach and be vigilant, by fostering team accountability and effectively resolving conflicts and also implement mechanisms to report exclusionary behaviours as they happen”.

This research also noted issues relating to exclusion, isolation, and inclusion, which is about promoting people of diverse backgrounds in working together within nursing home environments, to encourage promoting humanity, unity, and cohesiveness.

Encouraging participation, involvement, and encouraging all to engage is extremely important. In the context of this research, the researcher noted all of the above narratives had something to do with the importance of the phenomena; participation, involvement, isolation, and inclusiveness, as solutions to the phenomenon of the issues that might have arisen out of the notion of lack of understanding of the importance of diversity i.e. the

idea of the value of recognising differences amongst people with different skills and talents or gender or sex or abilities or cultural or ethnic background, etc. and equality; the importance of treating people fairly and respectfully.

In this aspect, several scholars have argued differently: social exclusion, isolation may even be deemed unethical in policymaking, policy implementation, and leadership challenges in the context of young people and community organisations (Eguruze, 2016, 2017). Similarly, it might be detrimental in the context of labour and youth unemployment (Boro, 1982, Willies, 1984). Others suggested it might be counterproductive to isolate or exclude based on same (McNeish et al... 1999; 2002), and that active involvement and active participation or inclusiveness would be a preferable option (Bradford, 1999, 2007, 2012), as cited in Eguruze, 2016, 2017). Others suggested inclusiveness as a more viable solution (Amaoke, 2000, 2002; Anan, 2004; and cited in Eguruze, 2016, 2017). Again, these are some indicators of the links between inclusivity and organisational performance.

4.3) *Summary*

As shown above, this chapter was focused on analysis of the qualitative data, which is based on the interviews. While conducting the analysis, the links between literature evidence and responses from the interviews were noted and/or highlighted. The main points were that: it is believed that better teamwork among people of a different race, skills, age group, gender and in fact, better inclusive strategy, better access to staff training and development opportunities, etc. at workplaces may lead to more effective or improved accessibility and quality of services to health and social care services. Such an outcome would be good for all stakeholders through the collective endeavours of all different workers regardless of racial, gender, ages, sexual, etc., differences.

As this qualitative data analysis chapter has been completed, the researcher now moves on to the next chapter of the research: which would be chapter five where there will be discussion and interpretation of the collected and analysed data.

CHAPTER FIVE

5) INTERPRETATIONS / DISCUSSION OF QUALITATIVE AND QUANTITATIVE RESULTS

5.1) Introduction

This chapter focuses on the discussion and interpretation of the qualitative and quantitative research results. As well as achieving the interpretation and discussion, this will be done in conjunction relevant literature evidence. The reason for showing this linkage is to ensure and highlight the connection between the literature evidence and the themes that have emerged from the qualitative research results. To this, the qualitative analysis has allowed the identification of the following themes. These are stated as follows: demographic characteristic; multicultural team performance (diversity & equality); work and domestic-life balance (flexible working patterns, hours, and contract); staff development and skills training on diversity characteristics (capacity building); encouraging hard-work & discouraging absenteeism (motivational-schemes & employee performance; inclusivity (social exclusion, Isolation & Inclusion). While the quantitative results will be combined with the above to bring out similarities and or differences in the responses although obtained using questionnaires and interviews.

5.1.1) Demographic attribute

For this study, demographic quality was associated with, gender, age, and ethnicity. One of the qualitative data responses towards achieving the research questions: -

1.8.1) What is the impact of diversity on employee performance in nursing homes in Middlesex-London?

1.8.2) What is the impact of workforce diversity management practices on employee performance in nursing homes in Middlesex-London?

Through their qualitative data, it appears that it is critical to encourage employees and engage them to excel at work, which would benefit the organization in terms of improvements of their performance.

Qualitative research data evidence. The followings were some of the selected responses from some of the participants for the demographic traits as regards. In the context of the demographic mix, more specifically, in terms of male and female diversity.

1st Respondent stated.

“Yes, I think gender diversity at all levels is important. When the workforce reflects the demography of the patient population, it cares for, I feel that I am an important part of the organisation. I strongly believe that if a manager has little in common with an employee, they cannot adequately advocate for them. So, I think that equal distribution of males and females within this workforce would enhance proper patient care. A more gender-sensitive environment is encouraged, which might promote an open culture among employees”.

2nd respondent said that: -

“I think gender diversity is important and having female leaders in nursing homes can lead to higher engagement and better retention of a more diverse workforce.”

Besides, according to the 3rd Respondent stated.

“Women have great analytical skills and coordinate activities with much better ease than men while upholding company values and strategies”.

The 4th Respondent said that: -

“In my experience, women tend to score higher on aspects of social sensitivity than men do, and I think good team performance is linked with social sensitivity factor within the team, especially in a nursing care field.”

In contrast, the 5th Respondent stated that: -

“I think diversity exists when people from different backgrounds who do not think as you, work together. Although hiring women at all levels of the organisation is important, it is good to recruit competent women, especially in management positions else diversity will only be on paper and would be meaningless.”

And finally, the 6th Respondent said that: -

“A mix of gender diversity within teams is good for business. But I think organisations dominated by women should have women at all levels of the organisation because this is good for building meaningful relationships and creating successful work processes.”

Taking these diverse views into context: there seems to be a mixture of feelings among women workers to the paradox. The summary of these collective narratives from these responses is pointing to just a few statements, which could be interpreted to suggest that: among nursing homes (or care homes) in the Middlesex-London

region, a male dominant management culture is prevalent i.e., in the management level, the figures were as follows: 35 (44.3%) were females as opposed to 43 males (54.4%). This means males are in dominant positions (managerial levels), as opposed to females who dominate the frontline working positions. This is irrespective of the fact there are far more female workers in the sector than are males. This is both in terms of workers and clients. While this unequal distribution between females and male dichotomy seems a concern from the perspective of the qualitative and quantitative data research findings, there also appears to be a connection as regards the narrative or evidence, while it also remains hard to explain on the surface. This is why it is important to explore further to unfold what the literature evidence may suggest. As indicated by previous research, the inclusion of both males and females in the management of organisations would boost organisational reputation and job satisfaction, all of which are crucial for employee performance. Therefore, gender diversity should be integrated within corporate strategy so that females in organisations like nursing homes should not feel discriminated against since they often make up most of the workforce in most healthcare organisations.

It is crucial to correlate the above with the quantitative research data earlier analysed. According to the quantitative PT1Q3 Figure 3 as in 4.1.3, concerning the impact of gender. Gender was one of the crucial democratic characters chosen in this research. According to the quantitative response data, there were two levels of responses that were of interest for gender characteristics (4.1.3) above.

At one level, the total number of those who responded to this question analysis (4.1.3) above, were 327 respondents. Of these, 7(or 2%) of the respondents did not disclose their gender; 181 (or 55%) did disclose as female participants, whereas 139 (or 43%) were responding as male participants. This reflected that more females responded to this question, as well as there were more females as frontlines workers, whereas more males as managers. On the other level, even amongst those who responded as frontline workers' category, the 181 respondents: 146 (or 59%) were females as opposed to males 96(or 39%), while 6(or 2%) were did not disclose their gender. Clearly what these statistics revealed is a clear gender imbalance among nursing workers in the frontline worker category. However, despite the fact there are fewer males 'than are females work at nursing homes, when it comes to the managerial category of workers, the male gender dominates at the managerial levels. This is a significant paradox and entails or raises the gender or demographic imbalance or injustice. It, therefore, shows that more is needed to be done to redress the inequality.

Literature evidence concerning 4.1.3 PTQ1Q3 Figure 3, confirms the findings:

Despite the fact there many immigrants to the UK, and most of whom are females, a larger percentage of females occupy not only low paid jobs than their male counterparts but more crucially, they (females) happen to constitute a bulk of frontline health and social workforce (Johnson, 2003; Knippenberg, et al., 2004). These problems may be overcome or improved by undertaking more leadership initiatives on gender diversity awareness training (Richard, 2000; Cox, 2001; Hubbard, 2004). Alternatively, using better or experienced

recruitment experts as well as more targeted communication materials/messages (Arthur and Doverspike, 2005), subject to the limits of the Equality Act (2010, as amended), again, these challenges could be overcome or resolved.

Similarly, concerning the qualitative response data findings literature shows that the concept of gender balance, or better diversity or workforce diversity management practices in workplaces are almost more likely to lead to more competitive gains or competitive advantages in terms of performance micro employee levels as well as at better productivity at macro organisational levels (Konrads, 2011, 2016; Armstrong, 2009, 2012; Roberg et al., 201; or may even promote better performances by individual employees (Herring, 2009; Niederle et al., 2013). And, similarly, the Equality Act (2010, as amended) emphasizes anti-discrimination regulations by any organisation based on gender, race, sexual orientation, disability, religion, etc, in the UK, therefore it would be unlawful to discriminate, except where steps are taken to ensure the appropriate or possible exemptions are complied with. For example, if there is any need for exemption on grounds of gender or race or disability or religion etc, that exemption clause will need to be specified or articulated in the same communicated materials, as required by the law. As noted, through balanced demographic management, employees are more likely to perform better and this, in turn, may enhance on organisational productivity.

What does the literature evidence point to? In fact, as with other organisations, nursing homes are under obligations to promote to ensure there is equality in the workplace environment as far as practicable (Equality Act, 2010, as amended). Crucially, it is important to show they are making that critical difference to avoid discrimination under the equality law (Equality Act 2010, as amended), and Shannon (2005). This can be better achieved when this commitment to promoting and ensuring diversity and workplace diversity management practice is shown at the very top level of management of nursing homes to overcome the issues of diverse challenges (Harding, 2005). In fact, by contrast, not only merely are management of nursing homes are under a duty of care not to discriminate but that duty must ensure proportionality or balance of all ethnicities, or people with a disability or non-disabled persons, gender-mix, as well as religious mix, etc., (Hirst and Thornton, 2005).

As with wider context NHS, where under-representation of BAME background is rife, perhaps a possible remedy would be a mentoring scheme that helps tackle the problem. Consequently, over 900 top managers are now offering mentoring to BAME managers the take-up still varies by location ironically, there is some disagreement about the appropriateness of a program directed exclusively at BAME staff, but future schemes might target other groups (Cole, 2006). In contrast, the issues of why BAME people were underrepresented or not fairly represented on nursing courses compared to white people, became challenged through study (Snow, 2006). All these diverse views from different studies pointed to a similar conclusion: it is important to appreciate as well

as embrace diversity/diversity practices at workplaces for there could be more benefits than not. The benefits may include better individual performance as well as improvement in organisational growth and/or productivity.

Another remedy was suggested in a study in which an integrated approach for the management of aging nurses, including the introduction of special incentives, centred on all age group categories provides an opportunity to create a healthy workplace for all generations of nurses (Lavoie-Tremblay, Maelanie, et al, 2006). The lesson to learn is that the presence of an increasing proportion of aging workers presented a major challenge to the nursing profession is critical (Lavoie-Tremblay, Maelanie, et al., 2006). More so, the presentation of theories about the development of a healthy workplace leads to the identification of a framework on which managers can base their management decisions (Lavoie-Tremblay, Maelanie, et al. (2006). The study found and revealed that the majority were not sure that there were any differences between recruitment and retention of white and BAME nurses into cancer care (Sookhoo and Anionwu,2006). The key barriers cited here were identified as those relevant to general nursing shortages within the NHS. They included poor pay, not being valued, and emotional stress related to caring for terminally ill patients (Sookhoo and Anionwu, 2006). Factors cited concerning BAME nurses included language problems, cultural influences, stigma, and possibly racism. The degree of dissonance between the views of the students and the director of nursing is of interest, as in the dearth of papers on this topic within the nursing literature. It may indicate a possible lack of awareness among the care and nursing profession about whether BAME nurses are underrepresented within this specialty (Sookhoo and Anionwu,2006).

However, there has been some inconsistency. The extent to which the age-diverse workforce influences performance in nursing homes has conflicted. Whereas age diversity has been shown to have a negative influence on employee performance in nursing homes, contrary, many findings exist that state agediversity enhances employee performance, in the case of nursing homes, the analysis has shown a negative link to performance as an employee get older. This suggests there may be a need to conduct further research to clarify this contradiction.

5.1.2) Multicultural team performance (diversity & equality)

Again, another qualitative data response towards achieving the research questions.

1.8.1) what is the impact of diversity on employee performance in nursing homes in Middlesex London? And
1.8.2. What is the impact of workforce diversity management practices on employee performance in nursing homes in Middlesex-London? through their qualitative data it is critical to encourage employees and engage them towards excelling at work, which would benefit the organisation in terms of improvements of their performance. Through multicultural team performance (diversity & equality) employees are more likely to perform better and this, in turn, may spur on organisational productivity. There have been many scholars that have argued in favour of motivational support towards employees as a boost to performance (According to scholars, the idea that employers tend to promote favouritism based on individuals or people they know or look like them are well documented over the years (Avery, 1979; Bernmardin & Beatly, 1984; Brewer & Kramer,

1985; Cascio, 1982; Tisui-Egan & O'Reilly, 1992, Wexley & Nemeroff, 1974). Further, (Yang and Konrad, 2011; 2016; Armstrong, 2012; Roberg et al., 2011) some scholars have also promoted the business case for promoting diverse workforce management is good for better performance outcomes (Herring, 2009; Niederle et al., 2013).

4.1.5 PT1Q5 Figure 5 quantitative data analysis showed there is a wide representation of various ethnicities across nursing homes. Asians constitute 44(or 18%) of frontline workers; 12 (or 15%) of Managers. and 16 (or 17%) of workers were black managers, while 80 (or 32%) of frontline workers; 14(or 17 % of managers); and 94(or 29%) of workers are from mixed other backgrounds; Whites from any other backgrounds constitutes 76(or 31%) of frontline workers; 20 (or 25%) of managers, while British White; 32(or 13%) of frontline workers; 22(or 28%).

Literature Evidence suggests concerning Quantitative data analysis 4.1.5 PTQ1.

These statistics support the literature evidence available: according to scholars, ethnicity refers to the identification of a group based on perceived cultural uniqueness or as individuals belonging to a group of people with the same nationality or ethnic origin, race (Noon, 2007; Morgan & Vandy, 2009). Although others may perceive ethnicity differently or in multiple ways portray race, nationality, or ethnicity (Niederle, 2013). Racial differences, (Allport 1954, p. 192) while others see cultural diversity more in terms of nationality/cross-cultural training is important; cross-cultural training addresses the differences in cultures, and to do this training is the best method to reduce intercultural conflict (Naumann, 1992; Friedlander & Walton 2000). Also, compliance with the Equality Act (2010, as amended),

Looking at the qualitative Data analysis 5.1.2 (Multicultural team)

1st Response said that: -

“I believe that cultural diversity has an immense impact on team performance, and it is important for teams to be multicultural.” Also, “I think that simply understanding others is no longer enough for either of us as managers or employees. Working in a diverse society such as the UK I expect my employees to continue to interact with others from different backgrounds.” Another is “The client base that we look after is increasingly getting diverse, and as a result, increased interaction will enhance learning, which, as a result, increases employee performance”.

The 2nd Respondent

“I would say ethnic diversity can sometimes be difficult to manage. It takes time to learn how to work within a team of varying ethnicities. However, it is my duty as a manager to find methods to convert process loss, such as communication problem and conflict to gain.”

The 3rd Respondent stated that

“Well, as a manager, I speak openly and honestly about the importance of ethnic diversity and inclusion in my nursing home. Most often people are inspired by the vision, and they want a leader who shows concern for the values that are important to them by speaking publicly about diversity issues, employees feel included thereby encouraged to produce better outcomes”.

And the 4th Respondent stated that: -

“We always make sure the diversity statement about what the organisation values are provided to all employees. It is a formal document to current and future employees that the organisation will put all forms of anti-discriminatory practices in place and work to foster equal opportunity for all.” Also, *“some of the nursing homes are encouraging ethnic diversity through their practices to encourage workers from different ethnicities to work together toward better outcomes”.* Moreover, managers state that they are *“making an effort to recruit and work with a diverse force though evidence from descriptive studies shows the highest ethnic diversity in frontline roles.”* As a result, *“the nursing home industry still has a long to go with regards to incorporating diverse ethnic force at all levels of nursing care, although there is general acceptance diversity positively influences performance.”*

Literature Evidence suggests for qualitative analysis pointed - Although, Marx et al. (2015) found a lack of cohesion within a diverse ethnic workforce as workers often portray overt preferences about who they would like to work with, a lot more studies have been found with a positive link. Darwin (2014) asserts that ethnic diversity has a positive link with employee performance as a pool of skills is created as well as various learning opportunities that the organisation can tap into for positive performance. Similar findings by Parrotta et al. (2011) show that a diverse ethnic workforce would bring different perspectives, experiences that may influence organisational processes positively. More specifically, it has previously been stated in the literature review that the composition of the workforce in most organisations is rapidly becoming mixed; this is evident in cities like London because of immigration and globalisation. This had already been stated by Zgourides et al. (2002) who indicated that the growth of a multicultural workforce was the focus of the early '90s and the growth has persistently been gaining more momentum. Although this study establishes a link between ethnicity, diversity, and employee performance, the descriptive analysis showed that ethnic diversity could mostly be seen in the frontline roles compared to managerial teams. It is important to state that ethnically diverse teams working in relatively homogeneous organizations experienced performance deficits relative to the more homogeneous teams

(Joshi and Jackson, 2003) however this performance deficit is not usually obvious for ethnically diverse teams working in ethnically diverse organizations. In ethnically homogeneous organizations, the ethnic differences among members of diverse teams become more salient and are more likely to interfere with performance. In ethnically heterogeneous organizations the ethnic identities of team members may be less salient and thereby creating less disruption (Joshi and Jackson, 2003). This legislation covers policy and practices relating to discrimination in workplace settings.

Data Analysis from the perspective of Reliability and Validity Testing: From the responses analysed, most of the respondents agreed that; they would perform better when working in a diverse team or managed by a team from a diverse background. Moreover, the mean scores of responses to questions such as, *“my performance reduce when managed by a diverse team or my performance reduces when working within a diverse team was low”*.

Also, responses to questions on the extent to which individual ethnicities would influence performance were very low. This was further confirmed by the hypothesis testing as the t value is 6.182 P-value was 0.004 less than the significance value of 0.05 which implies that ethnic diversity is the third most significant independent variable within the study that influences employee performance in nursing homes.

Again, what the statistics have revealed is that there is a positive connection between quantitative, qualitative, and literature evidence, all of which point to the existence of the same influence between diversity and performance and productivity. These suggest there are linkages between adopting diversity management practices and the propensity for enhanced organisational performance.

In fact, as with other organisations, nursing homes are under obligations to promote good diversity practices to ensure there is equality in the workplace environment as far as practicable. Crucially, it is important to show they are making critical changes to avoid discrimination under the equality law (Equality Act 2010, as amended). and Shannon (2005). This can be better achieved when this commitment to promoting and ensuring diversity and workplace diversity management practice such as race equality schemes is shown at the very top level of management if nursing homes are to overcome the issues of diverse challenges (Harding, 2005). In fact, by contrast, not only merely are management of nursing homes are under a duty of care not to discriminate but that duty must ensure proportionality or balance of all ethnicities, or people with disability or non-disabled persons, gender mix, as well as religious mix, and sexuality Hirst and Thornton (2005).

5.1.3) Work and domestic-life balance (flexible working patterns, hours, and contract)

Another qualitative data response towards achieving the research questions 1.8.1; what is the impact of diversity on employee performance in nursing homes in Middlesex-London? And

1.8.2; what is the impact of workforce diversity management practices on employee performance in nursing homes in Middlesex-London? demonstrates that it is critical to encourage employees and engage them to excel at work, which would benefit the organisation in terms of improvements of their performance. Through flexibility, work, and domestic-life balance (flexible working patterns, hours, and contract) employees are more likely to perform better and this, in turn, may spur on organisational productivity.

The research noted letting workplace employees work flexibly is an important part of creating a modern and appealing employment culture across the nursing homes/care home setting, as much as across the healthcare and social care industry. It was noted that inflexible and unpredictable working patterns make it harder for people to balance their work and personal lives. It was noted flexibility work arrangements do enable ambitions to give people greater choices over their working patterns, as well as enable them to achieve a better work-domestic life, which enables the respective nursing home/care home, potentially become an employer of choice. The research results enabled the researcher to develop a robust framework that would enable positive changes to occur for the nursing homes sector within the health and social care industry.

Note that offering flexibility at the point of recruitment can widen your talent pool while improving access to flexible working opportunities for existing staff is a key component of a broader strategic approach to retention. This has also been stated by working family briefings (2020), from a survey carried out before and during the pandemic. These researchers stated that, although there was some sort of flexible work arrangement in organisations, the government should do more, suggesting the following policy changes:

- Where possible employers should commit to advertising jobs flexibly
- Ensure organisations are taking a strategic organisation-wide approach to better job design.
- Reform the outdated right to request flexible working.
- Ensuring all parents and carers have access to secure jobs with guaranteed, predictable hours and access to all parental employment rights (Working parents briefing, 2020)

Crucially, the wider practical benefit would be that many of the research results: ideas, tips, and principles shared in this new framework model are highly likely applicable to all sections of the nursing home/care homes sector as well as the wider health and social care industry. However, the research findings also specify clinical and operational constraints that exist across certain professions and needed to be tailored in certain parts of our resources as appropriate.

By contrast, according to the quantitative data analysis: PT1Q16: Figure 16; My performance increases when I am on a flexible working contract; As seen previously shown in chapter,

4.1.16 PT1Q16, figure; 16 relates to the question PT1Q16. It reflects that there was a total of 157 respondents to the question from among the participants, out of the total of five hundred questionnaires that were administered. Based on the 149 polls, 15 (or 10 %) agreed or 12 (or 7 %) strongly agreed with the statement; *'my performance increases when I am on a flexible working contract'*; while those who disagree were 41 (or 26%), 44 (or 28%) strongly disagree but the rest 45 (or 29%) neither agree nor disagree. Again, this means this group of respondents that support this statement constitutes and reflects quite a significant majority of opinion, which is in favour of the practice that suggests an employee is more likely to do better in a nursing home that promotes or practices or allows a flexible working environment. It suggests flexible working culture might boost an employee's performance potentiality.

Based on this outcome it can be argued that it is important to consider flexible working culture within the nursing home setting. Similarly, as seen above, Figure 15 relates to the question PT1Q15. It reflects that there was a total of 149 respondents to the question from among the participants, out of the total of five hundred questionnaires that were administered. Of the 149 polls, 33 (or 22 %) agreed or 29 (or 19 %) strongly agreed with the statement; *'my performance increases when I work in a diverse team'*; while those who disagree were 18 (or 12%), 19 (or 13 %) disagree but the rest 50 (or 34 %) neither agree nor disagree. This means this group of respondents to this statement constitutes and reflects quite a wide diversity of opinion, which needs deeper comprehension.

Literature Evidence: The literature states as follows: Build flexibility into the policy; avoid favouritism and/or discrimination when applying or implementing policies to different employees; there needs to be great consistency and transparency in policy and action/practice (Equality Act 2010, as amended). It might be very difficult to ignore an employee-facing outside challenge and for the interest of workers welfare and wellbeing visa-vis company's performance and productivity, it would make sense to have flexible working hours (Hertzberg, 1968). However, it must be noted there should be consistency in policy administration to not breach the Equality legislation for being accused of discrimination.

Through Work and domestic-life balance (Flexible working patterns, hours, and contract) employees are more likely to perform better and this, in turn, may spur on organisational productivity. There have been many scholars that have argued in favour of motivational support towards employees as a boost to performance (Bulger, Mathews Hoffman, 2007). In fact, according to literature evidence, work-life balance is about how individuals and managers employees, and employers may need to negotiate overwork and personal requirements to achieve mutual benefits at the workplace setting and/or avoid possible conflicts or achieve mutual satisfaction (Bulger, Mathews Hoffman, 2007). In the 21st century working environment, working conditions and demands have been observed to have changed significantly mainly due to changes in technological, social, and economic, and other environmental factors, and therefore working patterns too (Russell, O'Connell and McGrinity, 2009; Armstrong, 2012).

5.1.4) Encouraging hard-work & discouraging absenteeism (motivational-schemes & employee performance

This is another qualitative data response to the research questions 1.8.1; What is the impact of diversity on employee performance in nursing homes in Middlesex-London? And 1.8.2; What is the impact of workforce diversity management practices on employee performance in nursing homes in Middlesex-London? through their qualitative data, it is critical to encourage employees and engage them to excel at work, which would benefit the organisation in terms of improvements of their performance. By encouraging hard-work & discouraging absenteeism (motivational-schemes & employee performance) employees are more likely to perform better and this, in turn, may spur on organisational productivity. There have been many scholars that have argued in favour of motivational support towards employees as a boost to performance (Maslow, 1943, 1954, 1970; Hertzberg,1960). These may include both extrinsic (monetary) and/or intrinsic motivational aspects(non-financial) (Hertzberg,1960; and it can be in a hierarchical format (Maslow, 1943, 1954, 1970). The research also noted issues relating to staff engagement such as information and resources designed to help within a nursing home/care homework placement environment (management and organizations) to develop and improve staff engagement within their workplace environment.

5.2) Summary

As noted above in this chapter the researcher engaged the discussion and interpretation of the data based on the qualitative research results, including quantitative findings. Again, the main highlights that included the main themes that were extracted from the coding process: multicultural team performance (diversity & equality); work and domestic-life balance (flexible working patterns, hours, and contract); staff development and skills training on diversity characteristics (capacity building); encouraging hard-work & discouraging absenteeism (motivational-schemes & employee performance; inclusivity (social exclusion, Isolation & Inclusion), demographic uniqueness mature, demographic quality sex. Once again during the discussion and interpretation process, there was evidence of linkages between literature evidence and the qualitative data. Which substantially go to suggest or support the study objectives and research questions. Based on this outcome, the researcher was able to extract crucial findings that are pertinent to this study about the research objects and/or research questions. Accordingly, as the discussion and interpretation of this chapter have been completed, the researcher now progressed to the last chapter six, here conclusions were drawn based on findings. In addition, recommendations, and suggestions for further research were added in this section.

CHAPTER SIX

6) CONCLUSION, CONTRIBUTIONS, RECOMMENDATIONS AND FUTHER STUDIES

6.1) Introduction

This section contains the findings, how the objectives were addressed, how the challenges or limitations were overcome, highlighted elements of bias, contributions to knowledge, theory building, contribution to practice, and methodology as well as the recommendations for further research and study.

6.1.1) Overview

This research was set out to investigate critically the impact of diversity and workforce diversity management practices on employee performance in nursing homes in Middlesex London. (See, chapter 1.1).

This study investigates what frontline healthcare staff (nurses, carers/healthcare assistants, receptionists, and cleaners) and managers (managers, assistant managers, supervisors) perceive as the impact of diversity and workforce diversity management practices on employee performance in nursing homes in Middlesex-London.

Based on this aim and purpose the following research questions and research objectives were outlined: -

6.1.2) The Research Questions (see chapter 1.8)

- 1.) What is the impact of diversity on employee performance in nursing homes in Middlesex-London? (Section 1.8.1)
- 2.) What is the impact of workforce diversity management practices on employee performance in nursing homes in Middlesex-London? (See section 1.8.2)

6.1.3) Research Objectives (see chapter 1.9)

- 1.) To critically assess and analyse what is the impact of diversity on employee performance in nursing homes in Middlesex-London (see section 1.9.1)

- 2.) To critically examine and analyse what is the impact of workforce diversity management practices on employee performance in nursing homes in Middlesex-London? (see section 1.9.2)
- 3.) To identify and analyse ways in which policymakers (such as government officials, as well as nursing management and frontline workers agree on how to implement identified best diversity/workforce, workforce diversity management practices required to improve(maximise) employee performance and reduce, (minimise) employee turnover (see section 1.9.3)
- 4.) To formulate a set of recommendations (such as a new conceptual framework) to implement the new policies that may improve workforce diversity management practices on employee performance in nursing homes in Middlesex-London? (See chapter 1.9.4)
- 5.) To encourage the application of a combination of diversity and workforce diversity management practices in nursing homes within Middlesex-London

To achieve the research objectives, the researcher engaged in empirical research. Which was fieldwork where data collection was obtained from a group of volunteer participants who responded and expressed their perceptions and experiences. This research revolved around a case study of some selected nursing homes in the Middlesex area of London, using a reflective perspective based on a complete participant role. The primary study, adopted for this research was a mix-method research design, consisted of qualitative (semi structured 12-items interviews guide/schedule, engaging a group discussion approach) and quantitative (based on a 23-item self-completion questionnaire) methodology in which 500 frontline healthcare staff and managers were surveyed. The massive data collected was analysed, coded, and processed through SPSS software and Excel. Cronbach's Coefficient. (The validity of the research instrument was measured using content validity and most of the questions were in a Likert scale format. Alpha Model was used to measure the reliability). Following the data analysis and interpretations, the major findings were presented. The research improved on existing multidimensional workforce diversity management practices factors-knowledgebase by enlarging it (by introducing gender, age, ethnicity, cross-cultural training, flexible working hours, and employee motivational schemes and thereafter redesigned a new conceptual framework, which still retains the current structure). This new Multidimensional Workforce Diversity Management Practices Conceptual Framework (MWDMP CF) is inclusive, implementable, practicable, and sustainable, whilst still retaining a workplace friendliness feeling that may lead to reductions in feelings of inequality at nursing homes. This new insight (extension) was derived through a combination of literature, methodology, and conceptual development, by adopting a mixed-method approach.

6.2) Summary of the findings

Based on the analysis of the empirical data, the main findings of the research indicate that nursing home services in Middlesex-London have been lacking inclusiveness or diversity management practice

The main finding revealed that frontline healthcare staff employment support needs have been unmet within nursing homes in the Middlesex-London region (which negatively affects their performance levels (in the care workplace). A great deal of additional support is required. Results showed that while gender, ethnicity, and motivational schemes have a strong and positive link with employee performance, cross-cultural training and flexible working hours showed a positive but weak link with employee performance. However, the relation between age diversity and employee performance was negative.

The most significant causes of poor employee performance and low productivity amongst frontline healthcare staff may be attributable to inadvertent unequal distribution and intolerant attitudes and behaviours towards people of BAME background of the workforce in the nursing homes where there is greater diversity at lower levels of employment (nurses, carers, receptionist, and cleaners) compared to the management sector (which is predominantly non-BAME). There exists non-representativeness in terms of diversity characteristics such as gender, age, ethnicity and the sparingly uptake of workforce diversity management practices such as; cross-cultural training, flexible working hours, and employee motivational schemes within the selected care homes in Middlesex. This unequal distribution of employees' support-needs is likely to be problematic and can affect employee outcomes. It was also noted that these imbalances might be leading to structural formations within the workplace setting acting as barriers causing impediments to the smooth functioning or even operational dysfunction within nursing homes, thereby causing poor employee performances, which is avoidable.

It was also observed that the main common experiences or needs of frontline staff and managers include work-life balance or flexible working hours to cope with possible work-domestic life balance needs including: - childcare and spouse needs, current work-overload, and long hours. Lack of consideration of these factors is unhealthy for frontline staff, directly leading to high staff turnover and absenteeism, which can be disruptive. The problem of managing major demographic changes is more complicated than just having to cope with the retirement of elder workers. Young staff may have different sets of values, priorities, and aspirations/or expectations such as more, childcare, money, job training and development, further or technical education, promotion, and opportunities for progression at workplaces, with more management roles or challenges or job satisfaction. Without this potential for promotion or enrichment of younger staff are more likely to hop from one job to another in the anticipation of greener pastures. Older staff are likely to require; more time with spouse/partners, reduced-work time, holidays, charity donations including nature and environmental concerns. Retirement planning including re-use of their time and expertise or experience that they could deploy in a more

qualitative and productive pattern is also important to the older staff and opportunities to explore which would be welcomed.

It is important to note that all these differences that had arisen do create and/or may require new recruiting and retention issues, as well as create further management problems/challenges due to these changing demographic variables/essentials, which make things much more complicated than just absenteeism, retention, and retirement issues on the surface. Some deeper inherent issues/challenges need to be recognised. The research considers how this additional support might be provided. Importantly the research also revealed how poor diversity/workforce diversity management practices could be eradicated or eliminated and by persuading policymakers- to create a more equal distribution or more balanced distribution that is based on needs or more need-based friendly management structures that respond based on needs in terms of gender disparities, age, ethnicity, cross-cultural training, flexible working hours and employee motivational schemes requirements and refer to the needs of patients, frontline staff/and managers. Also, there is a need to attract a management team that is ready to engage in dialogue and/or negotiate by engaging with all stakeholders in a mutually more respectful and more beneficial manner as a practical way forward in terms of formulating and implementing the new policy decision process surrounding the new model (MWDMPFCF). As stated above; this will be particularly and strategically important for all stakeholders; and service users, frontline staff, policymakers, including management of nursing homes/wider health and social care industry leaderships and government and policy-implementers i.e., managers. Also included are the effects on the wider society, where young workers may need to invest in the experiences of the older workers in a phenomenon that may be known as bridging the intergeneration gap. Introducing a merit-based system of promotion and compensation may be helpful as well as introducing flexible working arrangements that support work-domestic life balance and make work more meaningful. By introducing fresh opportunities for peer-mentoring and/or coaching, opportunities for continuing education, whilst working are maintained. Providing tuition support or reimbursement for post-graduate learning as part of staff development programs would be beneficial, and for undergraduates introducing paid internship programs that may lead to permanent employment, as a result, would certainly be attractive to many.

Finally, the research revealed that actively involving frontline staff and managers in policy decision making and policy implementation processes, including setting new priorities to reflect areas such as encouraging some older workers that are due for retirement, to stay longer, introducing a culture of mentor practice, or redirecting resources to specific areas such as investing in employee career development, which nurture/cultivate/attract younger workers to come into the sector by ensuring/highlighting opportunities for progression as potential leaders, ensuring they have a sense of purpose, work-domestic life balance, as well as ensuring professional development guarantees. Including training around food preparation as some cultures have a specific way of handling food (Kosher, Halal training) and some individuals have special dieting needs, etc. are more likely to enhance the probability of eradicating inequalities at nursing homes within the Middlesex-London region.

6.3 How were the research objectives addressed?

6.3.1 Research Objectives (Chapter 1.8)

Research objective 1: To critically assess and analyse what is the impact of diversity on employee performance in nursing homes in Middlesex-London (see chapter 1.8.1).

Concerning the research objective 1.8.1, the research specifically found that:

6.3.1.1) What impact does a diverse gender workforce (males and females) have on performance in nursing homes?

Gender diversity is an important factor in employee performance. Achieving gender diversity is the right thing to do in a society in which gender equality is a major issue, and because, in a diverse gender workforce, internal and corporate objectives are usually attained with much ease. As indicated by previous research, the inclusion of males and females in the management of organisations would boost organisational reputation and job satisfaction, all of which are crucial for employee performance. Therefore, gender diversity should be integrated within corporate strategy so that females in organisations like nursing homes should not feel discriminated since they are often making up most of the workforce in most healthcare organisations.

6.3.1.2) Does ethnic diversity influence performance?

This study has shown that ethnic diversity is important for employee performance. In a highly multi-ethnic society like the UK, different ethnicities are found in almost all organisations. In nursing homes, cultural differences could impact care delivery; therefore, the development of culturally sensitive programmes can bridge the gap and positively impact care. Ethnic diversity does not only help boost the firm's competitive advantage over organisations with a more ethnically homogenous workforce but increases employee satisfaction, which most often increases outcomes.

6.3.1.3) To what extent would an age-diverse workforce influence performance in nursing homes?

Age diversity has been shown to have a negative influence on employee performance in nursing homes. Although many findings exist that state that age diversity enhances employee performance, in the case of nursing homes, the analysis has shown a negative link to performance as an employee gets older.

The quantitative response data to the research objectives were achieved by realising: PT1Q1 as shown in Figure 1 relating to the Roles played by both frontline and Manager level workers. It showed that frontline workers

(who are mainly nurses, administrative staff, cleaners or porters) who are more in greater numbers (248 or 78%) of the respondents, as opposed to managerial levels workers who are in fewer numbers and constitutes a minority group (79 or 24%), and yet it showed all of these different roles they play are deemed relevant and necessary at nursing homes. It shows no role is less or more valued. However, from an age perspective, most employees in nursing homes are young or youthful by age. It implies youthfulness is a critical factor. Most nursing employees appear to be within the age group (28-37 or 38%). It also showed the next age group in greater numbers is between the ages (18-27 or 28%), and the larger group is between the ages (38-47 or 22%), as opposed to the least represented age group (of over 58 years or merely 2%). Importantly, it showed that all these different age groups are needed and relevant to nursing homes, while it also pointed to the fact that a more youthful age group constitutes the crucial working force in nursing homes in the Middlesex-London region. It indicated that most nursing employees are in their prime ages or most productive age group bracket. Response data PT1Q1 pointed that a relatively high percentage of the workforce is in their most active productive years, which is (47 years of age or even below). This might be due to ageism or are there fewer applicants because of being disillusioned by the lack of consideration to their support needs? After all the older workers, while not being so fit perhaps, have the benefit of wisdom and hindsight, are usually more reliable as they have no children to care for, more flexible as they are not so bound by the constraints of running a household and make ideal mentors for the younger inexperienced staff. They are also creative and more used to using limited resources to 'make do and mend' for example. Finally, they are particularly useful in the selection of new staff as they usually have better perceptions of what is needed and what is offered by the prospective employee.

Similarly, through qualitative response data 5.1.1 another respondent, it was suggested that age, ethnicity, and gender are all important. This supports the quantitative response data. In fact, according to another, respondent "demographic characteristic is (such as age, gender, and ethnicity) is important." Another stated, it is important, when the workforce reflects the demography of the patient population it caters for.

Besides, these findings were similarly supported by literature evidence. According to literature physical activity and physical fitness, wellness and welfare and wellbeing, etc. are inextricably interconnected with age, as well as better functionality and stamina (Dipietro, 2001). This appears to be the pattern of evidence that youthfulness is critical amongst employees in a nursing home in the Middlesex-London region. It is argued that younger groups are likely to be achieving greater performance, are more creative, and more energetic, etc., (Bijinen et al., 1998; Dipietro, 2001, 1989). It was also noted that using experienced recruiters, however, maybe helpful and useful in identifying and getting the right mix of the group for a nursing home, which is critical (Arthurs and Dover spike, 2005).

6.3.2) Research Objective 2 (section 1.8)

To critically examine and analyse what is the impact of workforce diversity management practices on employee performance in nursing homes in Middlesex-London? (See section 1.8.2)

6.3.2.1) Do flexible working hours influence performance in nursing homes?

Flexible working arrangements have been shown to enhance nursing home performance as it enables employees to achieve a better work-life balance. The important message for managers might be that allowing employee choice over their working patterns may greatly influence employment relationships, which can translate into better organisational commitment and job satisfaction. Flexible working arrangements customised to meet employees' needs might positively affect employees' attitudes to work. This has been highlighted by this study from the analysis of the responses of the participants.

6.3.2.2) To what extent would employee motivational practices affect nursing home performance?

Motivation occupies a central place in the whole management process as the practice is used to encourage employees to make positive contributions for achieving organisational goals.

Motivation is useful in all aspects of life, and it is an integral part of the management process. When employees are motivated, they become more productive; therefore, an increase in employee performance directly reflects on the organisational performance.

6.2.2.3) How does cross-cultural training affect the performance of employees in nursing homes?

Cross-cultural training showed a positive but weak link to employee performance. From the qualitative analysis, most of the respondents admitted they have never heard of a specific training like cross-cultural training, although they acknowledged that cultural aspects were embedded in a more general training known as diversity training. Moreover, although they haven't heard of it, they agreed that it was a useful concept in the UK's highly multicultural society.

This study has shown that ethnic diversity is important for employee performance. In a highly multi-ethnic society like the UK, different ethnicities are found in almost all organisations. In nursing homes, cultural differences could impact care delivery; therefore, the development of culturally sensitive programmes can bridge the gap and positively impact care. Ethnic diversity does not only help boost the firm's competitive advantage over organisations with a more ethnically homogenous workforce but increases employee satisfaction, which most often increases outcomes.

6.3.3) Research Objective 3

To identify and analyse ways in which policymakers (such as government officials and nursing management and frontline workers agree on how to implement identified best diversity/ workforce diversity management practices required to improve (maximise) employee performance and reduce (minimise) employee turnover (see section 1.9.3).

Similarly, this objective was achieved by successfully formulating the 10-step Conceptual framework (as highlighted in chapter5).

Code Nos	Diversity variables
1	Diversity dimensions/diversity management practices
2	Diversity dimensions
3	Diversity management practices
4	Age
5	Gender
6	Ethnicity
7	Motivational schemes
8	Flexible working
9	Cross Cultural training
10	Enhanced employee performance

Source: researcher's construction 2019

The above was noted, disequilibrium of distribution, by engaging a range of diversity in gender, ethnicity, and diversity management practices such as motivational schemes, flexible working, etc. in diverse nursing/care homes that could lead to enhanced performance outcomes and/ better productivity. It was found that these could be achieved by recognising and appreciating differences in skills, experiences, knowledge relating to:

- (i) age differences in a positive way.
- (ii) gender differences in a positive way.

- (iii) ethnicity differences in a positive approach
- (iv) differences in skills, experiences, knowledge, relating to diverse workforce management practices such as a range of motivational schemes are different in a positive way.
- (v) By recognising and appreciating differences in skills, experiences, knowledge, relating to flexible working are different in a positive way.
- (vi) By recognising and appreciating differences among employees in nursing homes in a positive way.
- (vii) By recognising and appreciating differences in achieving enhanced performance and higher productivity positively.

To this, the linkages between literature with quantitative and qualitative response data have been evident: for example, the importance of getting nursing employees engaging in the relevant training e.g., cross-cultural, mentoring, etc. trained on how best to satisfy inclusivity requirements were highlighted. Quantitative and qualitative response data raised the issue of lack of money in diversity awareness or inclusivity awareness due to the diversity, which is supported by the literature.

6.3.4) Research Objective 4

To formulate a set of recommendations (such as a new conceptual framework) to implement the new policies that may improve workforce diversity management practices on employee performance in nursing homes in Middlesex-London? (see chapter 1.9.4).

As earlier suggested in chapter 5, the 8-step Conceptual framework (as outlined in chapters 3 and 4) could be adopted as a guide. If implemented and/or operationalised it would be a useful tool designed to overcome the disequilibrium in the distribution of the workforce in nursing homes where there is greater diversity at lower levels of employment (such as nurses, carers, receptionists, and cleaners) as opposed to the management levels (which is predominantly non-BAME) in terms of age, gender, ethnicity, cross-cultural training, flexible working hours and employee motivational schemes, etc. The constructive way forward, therefore, is to use persuasive methodology. By persuading policy decision-makers and practitioners to adopt and implement it as a policy, as well as use it as a tool for practical training of nursing staff. By the persuasion of policymakers and practitioners to change perspective is important. The Equality legislation (the Equality Act 2010, as amended) which already places a duty of care on individuals and organisations not to discriminate would be critical in this persuasion process. Therefore, operationalising the conceptual framework is important.

It is important also to note the Equality Act 2010 provides the necessary guidance as to fall back onto as it provides the vital protection against discrimination, harassment, or victimisation in employment either as users of private and public services related to the 9 protected variables or characteristics: race, gender(reassignment),

age, sexual orientation, religion (or beliefs), disability, marriage and civil partnerships, pregnancy, and maternity, etc. As previously stated, the Act imposes a duty of care to every person or organisation or local government (and/or agencies) not to discriminate.

6.4) Limitation of the study

This research has several limitations and/or constraints, as with most other studies. Below specific experiences are explained as follows:

6.4.1) Study area/region

This study concentrated exclusively only on the narrow sector of the industry as well as a region of London, which is – nursing homes (or care homes) within Middlesex-London, which means different nursing (or care homes) outside of this region are not covered or omitted in this research. However, the researcher is envisaging engaging in similar research or future study that would focus on other regions of the Greater London areas. That could be suggested as a future research commitment for those who may be interested.

6.4.2) Research Findings

As outlined above in connection with 1, the findings of this research relate only to investigating the impact of diversity/ workforce diversity management practices on employee performance in nursing homes for the Middlesex in London.

Again, which means that since it did not cover or extend to

- (i) other aspects of the health and care industry
- (ii) other regions of London and beyond, it automatically opens the possibility for interested future researchers to explore such potential and scope for further research on the same subject elsewhere.

6.4.3) Health & social care/NHS industry

This research is not about the entire health and social care industry, nor the NHS of the UK. Although nursing homes (or care homes) are part of the health and social care industry, this study does not extend to the entire industry, as already stated above. It is important to understand this closeness but at the same time the narrower specification of this area/region of research.

6.4.4) Perceptions and opinions

This study is predicated upon the perceptions and opinions of the respondents who participated in the empirical aspect of the study. It is important to note that perceptions and opinions are not the same as their actual actions and practices would be, so it is important to allow for such a difference between reality and perception. This

means it is important to respect and/or appreciate such limitations and constraints connected with opinion surveys.

6.4.5) Bias

It is important to appreciate the fact that bias is almost inevitable in research, which is a critical ethical matter inherently embedded in the pre-research process and needs to be identified. Bias could be either be from the perspective of the researcher, respondents, or participants. This may be in the context of making general statements by respondents or even the researcher himself or herself, which may be deemed subjective (Henn et al., 2009). Hence, it is crucial to avoid bias as much as practicable. One way of avoiding bias as suggested by scholars is to consistently focus on the subject matter and/or phenomenon being researched (Patton, 1990; Henn et al., 2009).

6.5) Research Contributions

6.5.1) To literature development

This research has contributed to literature development in the areas of diversity/workforce diversity management practices in the nursing homes in middle-London. This was achieved by specifically introducing/re-emphasizing the need for nursing homes in Middlesex-London to focus on three key diversity characteristics, including variables: age, gender, and ethnicity to reflect or highlight the current diversity structure of the middle-London community. And by re-articulating/re-directing attention to the three essential dimensions (or variables), it has contributed to the filling of the gap in literature that existed.

6.5.2) To methodology development

This research has also contributed to methodology development in the areas of diversity/workforce diversity management practices in the nursing homes in Middlesex-London. This was achieved especially through the design and development of a new and enlarged conceptual framework, as it incorporates not only the three diversity variables – age, gender, and ethnicity on one hand, but also contained the three-diversity workforce management practice variables namely: motivational schemes, flexible working hours and cross-cultural training). Again, by purposely redrawing attention to these six variables incorporated into the same meaningful purposive conceptual framework, this research has contributed towards methodology. This is as unique because these diversity variables were identified through the fieldwork data collecting and analysis process, as variables most important and most relevant in running nursing homes within the Middlesex-London region.

6.5.3) To future researchers

This research contributed to the enhancement of the body of knowledge and provides information that forms a basis for further research on workforce diversity and employee performance, and diversity/workforce diversity management practices in nursing homes in the Middlesex-London region. Just as this work was influenced by

the literature and methodology of previous researchers, so also this research has not only added to the same but also has created the base upon which future researchers could start from.

6.5.4) To practice; the management of nursing homes

The research provided additional insights into the relationship between workforce diversity practices and employee performance, more specifically in nursing homes in general. The researcher feels this is also an important contribution to knowledge in this field of diversity/workforce diversity management practices within nursing homes in the Middlesex London region.

6.5.5) To policymakers and policy implementers

This research also contributes to policy formulating in the diversity/workforce diversity management practices sector within nursing homes in the Middlesex-London region. From the integration of diversity characteristics and diversity management practices perspective, this contribution was made in the form of designing a new conceptual frame specifically for the nursing homes sector to improve diverse workforce management practices. This is because the new knowledge gained should provide insight into the debate on policymaking that could result in improving the quality of workforce diversity management processes. The study provides vital insights on how effective management could be, of different aspects of diversity within an organisational setting.

6.6) Research Rationale/Gap

As noted above research gap, therefore, arises from the fact that, despite the several previous studies on different aspects of diversity/workforce diversity management practices as they affect employees generally: on the challenges/ opportunities(Montes & Shaw, 2003; Choi & Rainey,2010); on inappropriate application /limitations in understanding of the concept (Grupta, 2015); on lack of understanding of the changes/dynamism of the concept in the mindset of stakeholders(Kaplan et al, 2015); and/or on lack of comprehension as diversity issues were rarely seen as part of corporate responsibility of stakeholders(Fleming & Jones), etc. Similar studies that focused on the nursing homes in the Middlesex-London region, were scarce. Similarly, the extant literature relating to the same were equally weak or scarce. Hence, the researcher opted to choose to undertake this research which focuses on diversity/workforce diversity management practices and their impact on employee performance.

6.7) Recommendations & Suggestions for Further Studies

Nursing homes should not only recruit a diverse workforce but also apply diversity management practices for better results. A mixture of the diverse characteristics and diversity management practices from the study will improve employee performance in nursing homes.

The level of diversity in the entire organisation should be improved because this increases the talent pool in organisations. Nursing homes should not only encourage diversity in frontline roles but have a diversity that truly reflects all the levels in organisations and the communities they serve.

It is suggested that management should develop mechanisms to promote and encourage diversity. This could be by conducting regular diversity training sessions among employees to create more awareness among the workforces.

The study, also, recommends that there should be the scheduling of work that will recognize individual differences, strengthen the weaknesses to enhance employee retention and subsequently employee performance.

A more robust and inclusive approach to managing nursing homes that embrace recognises and appreciates all peoples with their different skills, experiences, and knowledge, aspirations, etc., should be the way forward, which is what, hopefully, may make patients satisfied.

6.8) Further studies

This study needs to be replicated in different areas across the UK using the same dimensions so that results can be compared. A generalisation of results is important for any organisation; therefore, if this outcome is replicable in other areas, the nursing home industry would benefit, and there will be more believability in the findings.

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Appendix

Participant Consent Form

Title of the project:

WHAT IS THE IMPACT OF DIVERSITY AND WORKFORCE DIVERSITY MANAGEMENT PRACTICES ON
EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN NURSING HOMES? (A case study of care homes in Middlesex-London)

Main investigator and contact details: Dorothy W Mbangsi, [REDACTED]

Members of the research team: - Dorothy W Mbangsi

1. I agree to take part in the above research. I have read the Participant Information Sheet which is attached to this form. I understand what my role will be in this research, and all questions have been answered to my satisfaction.
2. I understand that I am free to withdraw from the research at any time, for any reason and without prejudice.
3. I have been informed that the confidentiality of the information I provide will be safeguarded.
4. I am free to ask any questions at any time before and during the study.
5. I have been provided with a copy of this form and the Participant Information Sheet.

Data Protection: I agree that the University processes personal data which I have supplied. I agree to the processing of such data for any purposes connected with the Research Project as outlined to me

Name of participant (print)..... Signed..... Date.....

Name of witness (print)..... Signed..... Date.....

YOU WILL BE GIVEN A COPY OF THIS FORM TO KEEP

If you wish to withdraw from the research, please complete the form below and return to the main investigator named above.

I WISH TO WITHDRAW FROM THIS STUDY

Signed: _____

Date: _____

Participant Information Sheet

Introduction

You are invited to take part in research into **what is the impact of diversity and workforce diversity management practices on employee performance in nursing homes: A Case Study of Care Homes in Middlesex-London.**

Before you decide whether to do so, it is important that you understand why the research is being carried out and what your involvement will include. Please take the time to read the following information carefully. Do not hesitate to ask me anything that is not clear or for any further information you would like to help you make your decision. Please do take your time to decide whether you wish to take part. Thank you for reading this

Section A: The Research Project

Title of project

What is the impact of diversity and workforce diversity management practices employee performance in nursing homes: A Case Study of Care Homes in Middlesex-London.

Purpose and value of study

This research is the main part of my doctorate programme in the University of the West of Scotland. Upon completion of the studies, I will be able to graduate with a doctorate degree and moreover will also be able to add to the body of knowledge in the field of diversity.

Invitation to participate

I will very much appreciate if you spare some time to fill in a Questionnaire or get involved in an interview. I am asking you the senior managers, managers, deputy managers and Care support workers, nurses

Who is organising the research?

I am Dorothy Mbangsi Wainsi, a student at the University of the West of Scotland. This is my final research project and I have developed the research plan, written the questionnaires and developed the interviews.

What will happen to the results of the study?

A thesis will be produced which will hopefully mean that I will achieve my doctorate.

Source of funding for the research

This is a personal thesis, and no funding has been given for its completion.

Contact for further information.

If you would like further information or would like to discuss any details personally, please get in touch with me, by email: [REDACTED]

Section B: Your Participation in the Research Project

Voluntary and withdrawals

It is completely up to you whether you decide to take part in this study. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this participant or information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. Agreeing to join the study does not mean that you must complete it. You are free to withdraw at any stage without giving a reason.

The procedure – questionnaire

If you decide to take part in this study, you will be asked your opinion around diversity in health and social care. The questionnaire will also ask you some questions about your demographic profile (such as your age group) but this information will be kept securely in password protected files on my Laptop. These questionnaires will be anonymous which means that you are not required to write down your name. The approximate time required to complete the questionnaire is between 15-20minutes.

Your Legal Rights

The research for this dissertation is fully compliant with the Data Protection Act so all your legal rights are protected.

What are the possible disadvantages, risks, or side effects of taking part?

There are no risks because your data will be treated confidentially. They will be used only for the purposes of this study and would not be distributed to third parties or organizations and the information provided will be destroyed after the study is completed.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

Participants will benefit from the study results as the results will add to the existing knowledge of the organisation and will possibly influence the way your organisation reacts to diversity.

How will my taking part in this study be kept confidential?

The personal data collected from the participants will be stored as a password protected file in my computer. Only my supervisor and I can access the personal data. The data will be used only for the purposes of the study and will not be distributed to third persons or companies. The personal data will be retained for two years after the study is completed and then they will be destroyed under secure conditions.

Who has reviewed this study?

This questionnaire as well as the interview questions have been reviewed by my supervisor as well as the university ethics committee.

Who can I contact if I have any questions?

If you would like further information or would like to discuss any details personally, please get in touch with me by email: [REDACTED]

Although I hope it is not the case, if you have any complaints or concerns about any aspect of the way you have been approached or treated during the course of this study, please write my supervisor at [REDACTED]

Thank you very much for reading this information and considering taking part in this study.

YOU WILL BE GIVEN A COPY OF THIS TO KEEP,
TOGETHER WITH A COPY OF YOUR CONSENT FORM

QUESTIONNAIRE

The researcher has explained the reason why this data is collected, and I understand what I am asked to do. I have freely agreed to take part in the study, and I will keep a copy of the consent form. I am also aware that I can withdraw from the studies at any time.

(Please tick as appropriate)

- I agree to participate in this study and allow my responses to be used for this research project.
- I do not agree to participate in this study

(Please tick as appropriate)

1) Your current role in this organisation.

- Receptionist Health care Assistant Team Leader Activities coordinator Nurse
- Cleaners Kitchen staff Other (Please specify)

2) Your age group 18-28 29-38 39- 48 49- 58 59- 68 69 plus

3) Gender Male Female Prefer not to say

4) Your length of service 0-2year 3-5years 6-8years 9 plus

- 5) Your ethnicity?** White- British white- Irish
- White -Any other white background Mixed- white & black Caribbean
 - Mixed- white and black African Mixed- white & Asian
 - Mixed- Any other mixed background Asian/ British- Indian

- Asian/British- Pakistani
- Asian/British- Bangladeshi
- Asian/Asian British (Any other Asian background.
- Black/Black British- Caribbean
- Black/Black British- African
- Black/Black British- Any other Black
- Chinese
- Any other ethnic background (Please specify)

6) Your highest educational qualification?

- Master’s Degree
- Bachelor’s Degree
- Associate Degree
- some College
- High School
- other, please specify.....

7) Do you consider yourself disabled? Yes No

Thank you for completing this section of the questionnaire

Section A - Diversity Management

8) Have you heard about diversity before? Yes No (please go to question 9) I don’t know (please go to question 9)

a) If yes, please indicate which of the following characteristics you would use to describe diversity

To what extent do you think the following demographic aspect of diversity are represented in Frontline roles

Ethnicity

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

Gender

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

Age

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

Religion

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

Disability

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

Education

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

To what extent do you think the following demographic aspect of diversity are represented in managerial roles

Ethnicity

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

Gender

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

Age

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

Religion

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

Disability

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

Education

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

Please circle the answer that best suits your opinion.

9) My organisation recruits a diverse workforce

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

10) Equal opportunity is offered to all employees in my organisation regardless of their background.

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

11) The following policies, procedure and practices are important to my organisation

(Tick as appropriate)

Diversity training

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

Recruitment and selection policy

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

Cross cultural training

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

Flexible working hours policy

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

Supervision/Appraisal framework

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)k

Employee Motivational schemes

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

leadership training

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

□ **Others (please specify)**

12) It is important for a company to have diversity management policy.

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

13) My organisation has a diversity/ equal opportunity policy.

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

14) My organisation makes employees aware of diversity policies and procedures.

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

15) Seminars on diversity are organised by my organisation

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

16) There are procedures in place for reporting discrimination?

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

17) Diversity training is part of organisation mandatory training.

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

18) Ethnic minorities and female employees are routinely identified and supported for career advancement.

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

19) Prospective employees are interviewed by a team that is diverse.

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

20) Mentoring programs are offered to all employees in the organisation.

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

21) Management talks openly about issues of diversity.

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree).

Thank you for completing section A, please move to section B

Section D: - Performance management

22) In your opinion, do you think employees of the following age groups have any effect on performance (please tick as appropriate)

18-27 (1) Strongly disagree (2)-disagree – (3)neither agree nor disagree) (4) Agree , (5) Strongly Agree

28-37 (1) Strongly disagree (2)-disagree – (3)neither agree nor disagree) (4) Agree , (5) Strongly Agree

38-47 (1) Strongly disagree (2)-disagree – (3)neither agree nor disagree) (4) Agree , (5) Strongly Agree

48-57 (1) Strongly disagree (2)-disagree – (3)neither agree nor disagree) (4) Agree , (5) Strongly Agree

58+ (1) Strongly disagree (2)-disagree – (3)neither agree nor disagree) (4) Agree , (5) Strongly Agree

23) I think women are better performers than men.

(1) Strongly disagree (2)-disagree – (3) neither agree nor disagree) (4) Agree, (5) Strongly Agree

I think women perform same as men.

(1) Strongly disagree (2)-disagree – (3) neither agree nor disagree) (4) Agree, (5) Strongly Agree

I think women perform less than men.

(1) Strongly disagree (2)-disagree – (3) neither agree nor disagree) (4) Agree, (5) Strongly Agree

24) My performance increases when a team from diverse background manages me

(1) Strongly disagree (2)-disagree – (3) neither agree nor disagree (4) Agree, (5) Strongly Agree

My performance decreases when a team from diverse background manages me

(1)Strongly disagree (2)-disagree – (3) neither agree nor disagree (4) Agree, (5) Strongly Agree

My performance stays the same when a team from diverse background manages me

(1)Strongly disagree (2)-disagree – (3) neither agree nor disagree (4) Agree, (5) Strongly Agree

25) I feel included when I am part of the decision making process in my organisation.

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- Agree, (5) Strongly Agree

26) My performance reduces when I work in a diverse team.

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

My performance increases when I work in a diverse team.

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

My performance increases when I work in a diverse team *1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)*

27) My performance increases when I am on a Flexible working contract

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

My performance remains the same regardless on the type of contract.

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

My performance reduces when I am on a Flexible-working contract

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

28) Cross-cultural training enhances my performance

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

Cross-cultural training reduces my performance

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

Cross-cultural training has no effect my performance

1- (*Strongly disagree*), 2 (*disagree*) - 3- (*neither agree nor disagree*) 4- (*Agree*) 5- (*Strongly Agree*)

29) I perform better when I am given a bonus

1- (*Strongly disagree*), 2 (*disagree*) - 3- (*neither agree nor disagree*) 4- (*Agree*) 5- (*Strongly Agree*)

I perform better regardless of a bonus

1- (*Strongly disagree*), 2 (*disagree*) - 3- (*neither agree nor disagree*) 4- (*Agree*) 5- (*Strongly Agree*)

My performance remains the same whether I am given a bonus or not.

1- (*Strongly disagree*), 2 (*disagree*) - 3- (*neither agree nor disagree*) 4- (*Agree*) 5- (*Strongly Agree*)

30) I am working in this organisation because of its workforce diversity practices

1- (*Strongly disagree*), 2 (*disagree*) - 3- (*neither agree nor disagree*) 4- (*Agree*) 5- (*Strongly Agree*)

31) My organisation motivates me to remain in the job through adequate pay and professional development

1- (*Strongly disagree*), 2 (*disagree*) - 3- (*neither agree nor disagree*) 4- (*Agree*) 5- (*Strongly Agree*)

32) Career progression opportunities are offered to all employees regardless of their background

1- (*Strongly disagree*), 2 (*disagree*) - 3- (*neither agree nor disagree*) 4- (*Agree*) 5- (*Strongly Agree*)

33) Employee abstentism has a negative influence on performance.

1- (*Strongly disagree*), 2 (*disagree*) - 3- (*neither agree nor disagree*) 4- (*Agree*) 5- (*Strongly Agree*)

1- (*Strongly disagree*), 2 (*disagree*) - 3- (*neither agree nor disagree*) 4- (*Agree*) 5- (*Strongly Agree*)

Employee absenteeism has a positive effect on performance

1- (*Strongly disagree*), 2 (*disagree*) - 3- (*neither agree nor disagree*) 4- (*Agree*) 5- (*Strongly Agree*)

34) Management offers flexible working contracts to employees when needed.

1- (*Strongly disagree*), 2 (*disagree*) - 3- (*neither agree nor disagree*) 4- (*Agree*) 5- (*Strongly Agree*)

35) Sickness rates have a positive effect on performance.

1- (*Strongly disagree*), 2 (*disagree*) - 3- (*neither agree nor disagree*) 4- (*Agree*) 5- (*Strongly Agree*)

Sickness rates have a negative effect on performance

1- (*Strongly disagree*), 2 (*disagree*) - 3- (*neither agree nor disagree*) 4- (*Agree*) 5- (*Strongly Agree*)

Sickness rates have no effect on performance.

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

36) The following are benefits of working within a diverse workforce. (Please tick as appropriate)

increase efficiency

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

Increased creativity

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

Improved problems solving

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

Improved motivation

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

Enhanced knowledge – Management

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

Reduced cost

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

37) Diversity would influence performance

1- (Strongly disagree), 2 (disagree) - 3- (neither agree nor disagree) 4- (Agree) 5- (Strongly Agree)

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SAMPLE SEMI-STRUCTURAL QUESTIONNAIRE

INTERVIEW QUESTIONS.

This study has been explained to me and I understand what I am asked to do. I have freely agreed to take part in the study, and I will keep a copy of the consent form. I am also aware that I can withdraw from the studies at any time.

(Please tick as appropriate)

I agree to participate in this study and allow my responses to be used for this research project (if yes go to the questions below).

I do not agree to participate in this study

1) What do you understand by diversity?

Prompt (deep-level characteristics)

(surface level characteristics)

2) What is your understanding of diversity management?

3) What is the composition of your top management team in relation to gender, sex Black and ethnic minority (BEM)?

Prompt (when I talk about a diverse management team I am talking in relation to males, females, BEM).

4) In what ways can gender diversity influence performance in nursing homes?

5) what do you think will be the results if a team of employees is made up of various employees of various age groups?

Prompt- In your opinion do you think it's a good/bad for employees of various age groups to work together and why.

6) Are there any diversity management practices that encourage performance in your team?

7) Does staff have any specific diversity training (cross cultural training)?

If yes (Please list)

-
-
-
-

8) Do you think diversity training (cross-cultural training) will have any effect on performance?

(Prompt: The UK is highly multicultural, and, in my opinion, I think knowledge about other people's culture will boost working relationship in the and improve performance)

9) In your opinion can motivation enhance performance in your organisation.

If yes-

What are some of the motivational strategies used by your organisation to boost performance?

10) In your opinion, what effects will flexible working hours have on performance diverse team?

Prompt: - List some flexible working hours. Some might exist which I don't know.

11) What are the challenges faced by the organisation working with diverse employees?

12) In your opinion, is diversity management good for business?

Prompt- can diversity management enhance performance?

Thank you for completing the interview